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Learning in Divided Times: Populism's Influence on Children's Well-Being and Educational Outcomes.

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ABSTRACT

This study provides empirical evidence on the interaction of populism with children's well-being and educational outcomes across 49 countries, from 2000 to 2022. While scholarly debates raise concerns over rising populism and societal consequences, its implications on children's well-being and educational outcomes remain underexplored. Therefore, this research aims to bridge that gap with empirical evidence. The conceptual framework draws insights from political science, psychology, and education to conceptualise and operationalise the justification for data analysis.

The study uses student-level data from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), (OECD, 2025) merged with macro-level populism data from the V-Party Dataset (Lindberg et al., 2022) and the Global Party Survey (GPS) (Norris, 2019). Measurement of populism and well-being is done via principal component analysis. Control variables include ESCS socioeconomic index, Gini coefficient for inequality, and social media usage measures.

The analysis employs cross-sectional OLS regressions, panel fixed-effects models, mediation analysis, and instrumental variable regression models. Results consistently show that higher populism levels are significantly associated with lower student well-being and weaker educational outcomes. Instrumental variable estimates, while using populism as an instrument, establish that well-being causally enhances educational outcomes, with strong instrument validity. Mediation analysis also attests to these results and confirms the mediating effect of well-being between education and populism. Additionally, the moderating variables also reveal statistically significant impact: the ESCS index and social media use are positively correlated with educational outcomes, whereas the Gini index is negatively correlated with educational outcomes.

Keywords: populism, education, well-being, inequality, political polarisation.

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“One knows the Truth only when the Truth is in his heart.”

- *Guru Nanak Dev Ji*

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the populist movement has surged across the globe (Inglehart & Norris, 2016). Populism, often characterised by its divisive political narratives and emotional appeal among audiences, thrives on socioeconomic and cultural insecurity. At the same time, the well-being of children is being challenged in an increasingly digital and interconnected world, as young people of today face unprecedented pressures, with potential consequences for academic achievement and mental health. This thesis empirically investigates the relationships between populism, children’s well-being and educational outcomes. Specifically, it examines how trends in populism, children’s well-being and patterns in academic achievement interact and seeks to understand how these forces influence one another in increasingly polarised societies.

To explore the research interest, this study integrates student-level data drawn from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (OECD, 2025) across eight waves (2000–2022). These are merged with country-level measures of populist party strength, derived from the V-Party (Lindberg et al., 2022) and Global Party Survey (GPS) (Norris, 2019) datasets, and macroeconomic indicators such as the Gini coefficient.

Figure 1

Map of Populism Intrapolated Standardised Values by Country in 2020 (GPS-V-Party)

Academic Relevance: A Call for a Multidisciplinary Approach

The academic inquiry of populism's impact on youth well-being and educational outcomes demands a greater intersection in contemporary scholarship. Research on populism has evolved over time, with many scholars and experts offering their nuanced understanding of it in specific contexts, whereas separate traditions in psychology and education have examined children's well-being, education and development. Yet, Soares et al (2024) remind us, despite the growing recognition of populism's impact on contemporary societies, especially in academic discourses, there is still a scarcity of theoretical and empirical evidence on populism's influence on education, especially formal education. Significantly, while there is awareness of the populism-education relationship, there is a greater need for systematic research. This observation highlights a pressing need for scholarly attention. In particular, empirically assessing the long-term impact of populism, education and children's wellbeing. The literature also reveals scholarly debates that remain unresolved, such as Estellés and Castellví (2020) highlighting their comparative interviews across five countries, where teachers are caught between two strategies: engaging with populism dialectically to promote democratic citizenship, or resisting its divisive ideologies. Other researchers add to the role played by teachers in helping students critically navigate through the negative emotions like fear and resentment (Zembylas,2020).

An important question arises; does the emotional appeal of the populist narrative penetrate the classroom and well-being experienced by children? The research gap thus originates with a weakened empirical understanding of how these dynamics translate into measurable effects on well-being and educational outcomes. This research attempts to address that gap by empirically testing the mediation effect of well-being between populism and educational outcomes., while also considering the roles of socioeconomic factors, inequality measures and social media use. The empirical foundation is motivated by synthesising insights from political science, psychology and education. Furthermore, because the nature of these variables is subjective and specific to context, a cross-national or cross-contextual study observing the long-term trends makes it highly relevant to push the academic understanding forward. Therefore, the main motivation of studying the proposed hypotheses is to understand the relationship of populism over time in different country constructs, quantitatively. The motivation for this is also justified by the need for evidence-based policy research.

Societal Relevance: Protecting Children Today for Protecting Peace Tomorrow

The societal relevance of this research lies in its direct engagement with some of the most pressing challenges of our time: peace, social cohesion and the future well-being of younger generations. As some scholars point out, populism is a means for political gains for the leaders while it alters the everyday experience of life for citizens. Especially, children who grow, learn and form their identity as citizens while internalising the narrative of "us versus them". This is not just a mere narrative; it is an evil that divides society, marginalises vulnerable groups, and legitimises division in society. After a point, populism goes beyond its abstract political debate; instead, it becomes a lived reality for those who experience hate, exclusion, and loss of dignity.

The key question then arises: will today’s children, shaped by these divisive narratives, grow up to reinforce them in adulthood?

A concerning feedback loop, in which declining well-being fuels support for populism, and populist support, in turn, amplifies negative emotions and social fragmentation (Soares et al,2024). The dangers of this ideology extend far beyond the classroom. As Frances Stewart (2011) explains, through the concept of *Horizontal Inequalities*, perceived inequality and differences between groups, based on the lines of class, religion, or ethnicity, are strong drivers of social tension, discrimination and even violent conflict. This is important to note because the populist narrative thrives on social divides and differences. This can lead to heightened risk of radicalisation, extremism and even wars. Over time, the consequences can escalate into economic disparities and significantly threaten peace and stability.

This trajectory has direct implications for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Objectives such as SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) are unattainable if societies continue to fracture along populist lines. How can sustainable development be achieved if the very fabric of society is fraying under the weight of polarisation and exclusion?

Figure 2

Implied United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

By examining the links between populism, children’s well-being and educational outcomes, this research attempts to shed light on the current scenario with numbers, facts and econometric evidence. Through the data-driven analysis, it attempts to inform educators, communities, and policymakers to guide evidence-

based policymaking. Ultimately, this work seeks to inform pathways towards unity, solidarity and sustainable peace.

These questions are even more pertinent as the national populism levels globally in 2020 are concerning, considering average standardised values from the V-Party (Lindberg et al., 2022) and GPS (Norris, 2019) studies, as shown in Figure 1 (see sections data - method and results for details).

2. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS

2.1. Definition and Conceptualisation of Populism, Children’s Well-Being, and Educational Outcome

2.1.1. Populism

2.1.1.1. Defining Populism

Populism, according to Cas Mudde (2012), can be seen as a ‘thin-centred ideology’. This ideology, at its core, is at the intersection of ‘pure people’ with a ‘corrupt, disloyal, or betraying elite’ (Noack & Eckstein, 2023). The conceptualisation of populism has gained attraction in academic discourse. The idea of ‘thin’ is likely to mean that it offers a limited set of perspectives, and this perspective can be combined with various other ideologies, which enables populism to manifest across the political spectrum, from the left to the right wing. Notably, the distinction between left-wing and right-wing populism is a subject of ongoing debate. As described by Zabala (2017), "the right-wing is associated with fear-evoking, whereas the left-wing influences hope." While both forms criticise elites and claim to represent "the people," their definitions of the adversary differ. Left-wing populists often target economic structures and advocate for inclusivity, whereas right-wing populists focus on cultural and ethnic identities, promoting exclusionary policies.

Mirroring Mudde’s framework, Norris (2020) has also explained populism as a political approach that emphasises the role of “the people” as the correct source of authority, often positioning them against a perceived “corrupt elite”. A key feature of the populist rhetoric is the portrayal of society being divided into two homogenous and antagonistic groups: (1) the direct flow of authority from “the people” who are virtuous and rightful in their rule, and (2) the “establishment” comprising elite groups, political opponents and institutions, who correspond to a corrupt, self-serving group, obstructive to the public will. The terms can be inherently vague and therefore adaptable to specific contexts. Populism portrays society as a struggle between 'the people' and their opponents.

Given the spectrum of applicability of the concept of populism, there is a central categorisation that is observed in political discourses. For example, Mudde’s framework applied in the context of Europe highlights right-wing populist parties often focusing on issues such as immigration and national identity (Mudde & Kaltwasser, 2012). Whereas, in the context of Latin America, the left-wing have emphasised economic inequality and anti-imperialism. Despite these differences, both types of populist narratives share the core elements of a divided society as identified by Mudde (2012) and explained by Norris (2020). This adds and throws light on the versatile and widespread appeal of populist ideologies, which also adds to its categorisations a ‘thin’ ideology.

2.1.1.2. Conceptualising Populism

Defining populism is a challenging task, given its variation across time and context. Historically and across countries, the term has been associated with shifting actors and moving agendas, making it difficult to

establish a single universal definition. However, it can be understood with scholarly work that populism as a political logic attaches itself to thicker ideologies of nationalism, socialism, or liberalism, depending on the content. For the purpose of this research, I adopt the framework conceptualised by Inglehart & Norris (2016), which captures populism in a way that can make it possible to measure it quantitatively. Norris identifies two main themes that explain the manifestation of the populist narrative: the economic insecurity thesis and the cultural backlash thesis.

The economic insecurity thesis highlights the role of income inequality in driving resentment and anti-establishment sentiment. It emphasises the strong rising trends in wealth inequality across industrial democracies, which have disrupted the established flow of labour, goods, and capital. This disturbance, when it intersects with the influx of migrants and refugees, causes a perception of scarcity and competition among those who are natives of a country and economically vulnerable. Especially, in Western Europe, where native individuals are in precarious socioeconomic positions, such as low-skilled workers, unemployed, or those dependent on social assistance from the state. These groups experience material difficulties and status anxiety, where the role of the populist narrative fuels their insecurity that opportunities are diminishing, especially in the labour market due to immigrant competitors. Populist leaders thus reinforce this framing by deploying an exclusionary rhetoric of ‘us’ against ‘them’. This dynamic can be observed across Europe, where employment, welfare chauvinism, and hostility towards immigrants are central mobilising themes. Similarly, noted in the United States, the economic grievances of deindustrialised regions have been politicised, linking globalisation, trade liberalisation and immigration to declining job opportunities. Therefore, populism resonates strongly among those who feel left behind and experience socioeconomic vulnerability, as research confirms the higher level of populist attitudes in especially economically disadvantaged and less educated older men (Piterová & Loziak, 2024).

Secondly, the cultural backlash theory extends the ideology further by explaining the emergence of populism as a reactionary response to long-term cultural transformations. These transformations are often described as the “silent revolution”, which is associated with the gradual spread of post-materialist values such as gender equality, multiculturalism, LGBTQ+ rights, secularism, and international cooperation (Inglehart, 2015). Over time, generational replacement of younger cohorts in the electorate is prompting such progressive norms. However, this process has proved a backlash or counter movement among older, less educated, and more traditional voters who perceive that their cultural dominance is eroding. For the latter group, these changing values in society are becoming a reason for resentment, nostalgia, and political disaffection, which is channelled through the populist narrative. This framework also resonates with a wide body of scholarship. For example, Betz (1994) also argued that the right-wing populism in Europe is strongly linked to xenophobic backlash against refugees and migrants. Similarly, Bornschier (2010) conceptualised populism as a new cultural cleavage, one nested in the tensions of globalisation and multiculturalism. Ignazi (1992) described the cleavages in society in terms of changes in the cultural domain and mass belief favouring radicalisation, which leads to an uprising of extreme right politics. The contemporary work by Bustikova (2014) highlights how right-wing populist movements mobilise the opposition to the political successes of minority groups. Taken together, the literature illustrates how the populist rhetoric is centred around the narrative or fundamental idea of an existing social division and therefore, it must be a political imperative to defend the “true people”.

The rhetoric then becomes a matter of restoring the mythical past, defending the cultural elites, and pushing away the outsiders. In my opinion, although the cultural backlash theory is complementary to the economic

insecurity thesis, in principle, it reflects the same kind of insecurity experienced by social groups that are fearful of a change in their society or community. This phenomenon is explained by the self-identity theory that explains how individuals derive a sense of belonging and self-worth from their membership in social groups defined by nationality, ethnicity, religion, or cultural tradition (Tajfel & Turner, 1979).. When these identities are perceived to be under threat, groups are likely to engage in defensive behaviours to preserve internal cohesion and resist external or internal changes.

From this perspective, populism is also manifested through deep cultural and social divides. The usage of indicators that can capture the attitude of political parties that make use of such divisive attitudes, such as hostility towards immigrants, ethnic minorities, opposition to gender equality, working women, religious principles, economic left or right position, cultural superiority and the like, are a few indicators that are particularly helpful to identify populist politics. Therefore, in this research, I conceptualise populism primarily through its divisive logic, where background differences, whether on cultural, ethnic, migratory, or sexual identity levels, are politicised to construct antagonistic boundaries, aligning with scholarly understandings of populism as society-splitting rhetoric.

Global surveys such as the V-Party Dataset, the Global Party Survey (GPS), or the Chapel Hill Expert Survey (CHES), have attempted to assess the extent to which ruling parties worldwide adopt populist discourse. This theoretical grounding is used to select the indicators of populism that have been used in this research to create a weighted index of populism, which can be used to quantitatively assess the measure of populism. The description of the indicators and the construction of the index will be discussed in the next chapters.

2.1.2. Children's Well-Being

2.1.2.1. Defining Children's Well-Being

Adolescent well-being is a multifaceted construct that consists of emotional, social, cognitive and physical dimensions, which all interact to underpin youths' capacity to thrive. (Pollard & Lee, 2003) UNICEF, through its campaign "OnMyMind: Better Mental Health for Every Child," defines children's well-being as encompassing their mental, emotional, and physical health, ensuring that every child grows in a nurturing and safe environment. It includes access to supportive relationships and quality, age-appropriate mental health care. The campaign emphasises that half of mental health conditions begin in childhood. However, cases often go undetected and untreated. In the case of adolescents, particularly around the age of 15, well-being is understood as the interplay between subjective life satisfaction, mental well-being, supportive relationships and the ability to cope with developmental challenges. According to OECD (2017), well-being in adolescence consists of both objective indicators, such as health, safety and material conditions. Whereas, subjective well-being covers their happiness, sense of belonging and purpose. The concept of subjective well-being ensures that a state of feeling well is not solely reduced to narrow measures of academic success, but it is actually a fundamental dimension of human development.

Children's well-being is important because it shapes both immediate developmental outcomes and lifelong trajectories. Positive well-being during adolescence is strongly associated with healthier lifestyles and stronger social integration (Proctor et al., 2009). Conversely, poor well-being, which manifests in anxiety

and depression, or low self-esteem, has been seen to be associated with higher levels of disengagement from school, social exclusion and lower adult life satisfaction (Viner et al., 2012). In this context, the developmental period of children around the age of 15 becomes crucial as it overlaps with key transitions in their lives.

The importance of children's well-being also lies in its close relationship with educational outcomes. For instance, children who experience higher life satisfaction tend to have more resilience in the face of academic setbacks (Salmela-Aro & Tuominen-Soini, 2010). As such, student well-being within the school environment is a broad construct that consists of emotional, social, and relational dimensions that influence both academic engagement and overall life satisfaction.

2.1.2.2. Conceptualising Children's Well-Being

The conceptualisation of 'well-being' in this study refers specifically to school-based well-being – how students perceive their social, emotional and psychological experience in their educational environment. Research in psychology, for example by Allen et al. (2018), suggests that well-being at school is not only shaped by individual characteristics but also by the quality of interactions students have with their teachers, peers and the broader learning environment. To operationalise this concept into a measure, a well-being Index has been constructed, which consists of ten indicators from the OECD PISA test. These indicators capture perceptions of teacher-student relationships, peer connectedness and feelings of belonging or exclusion. All of these have been consistently associated with positive educational and developmental outcomes (Wentzel, 1998). Therefore, this study utilises the self-reported indicators of subjective well-being experienced by children.

2.1.3. Educational Outcome

2.1.3.1. Defining Educational Outcome

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) is a comprehensive approach to assessing the educational outcomes of children. PISA measures 15-year-olds' ability to use their reading, mathematics, and science knowledge and skills. The test explores how well students can solve problems, think critically and communicate effectively, giving insights into how well education systems around the world prepare the youth for real-life challenges and future success. Measuring student achievement through standardised exams, as explored by Ritzen and Winkler (1977), provides a compelling proxy for human capital. It is a particularly interesting operationalisation because in this sense, standardised test outcomes not only reflect individual educational attainment but also provide insight into the long-term trajectory of societies, given that today's students will shape the economic and social structures of tomorrow. Therefore, linking education outcomes to standardised assessments can offer robust measures of human capital and its implications for both individual and societal progress.

2.1.3.2. Conceptualising Educational Outcome

For the aim of measuring educational outcomes in this research, mathematics and reading scores have been assessed. The rationale for choosing these tests is justified by the universal application and requirement of logical reasoning and lingual capacity. Mathematical literacy represents far more than computational ability; it assesses the student's capacity for logical, critical, and analytical thinking. Furthermore, numeracy skills are essential for success in the labour market and are transferable across multiple domains. Research has demonstrated that mathematical proficiency is associated with higher lifetime earnings, better employment prospects and improved capacity for civic participation.

Reading skills are the foundation of all learning and represent students' ability to understand, use, reflect upon and engage with written texts to achieve goals. Especially crucial for developing knowledge, potential and participating in society. The significance of these educational outcomes are also intricately linked to psychological well-being, as students who succeed in these foundations are more likely to develop a sense of academic competence, one of the three basic psychological needs identified in self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000) It can also imply conversely, when students struggle with mathematics and reading, they may experience diminished sense of competence and decreased motivation to engage with educational challenges.

2.2. Conceptual Framework

2.2.1. PISA Populism, children's well-being, and their educational outcomes

The relationship between populism and individual well-being has emerged as a critical area of inquiry in the academic discourse. It is, as such, also complex to justify, as the potential influence on well-being is not something that can be directly measured or observed in the short term. However, research has suggested the relationship between them. Silva (2024) discusses an inverse relationship between individual life satisfaction and self-reported support for populist parties, which indicates that populist environments may contribute to decreased subjective well-being. Additional research was conducted by Burger and Eiselt (2023) on longitudinal data on Dutch voters. It has been reported that decreased subjective well-being is associated with a tendency to vote for populists. Although the context of these studies is for adults, it is important to note that 15-year-olds are on the threshold of adulthood. It is reasonable to assume that the patterns observed among adults will also apply to these students. This point becomes more relevant in the light of recent policy shifts and debates, where some countries have already lowered the voting age to 16 years (*Should Children Vote?*, n.d.).

The causal mechanisms underlying this relationship are illustrated by Adena and Huck's (2023) experimental study. It documents a relationship from AfD support to reduced well-being for new and marginal AfD supporters. It challenges the conventional idea of the causal direction, where dissatisfaction leads to populist support. Instead, it reveals a bi-directional relationship where populist identification may itself harm psychological well-being. Since the idea of the populist narrative has so much to do with 'anti-immigration', 'anti-elitism', 'anti-equality' and the like, these negative perceptions mirror internal dissatisfaction, ultimately reflecting a poor state of well-being. A self-identity rooted in openness and

positive perceptions towards others and towards the environment is more likely to be linked with self-confidence and increased well-being.

Furthermore, the populist narrative, which frequently leverages negative emotions and fear, using a ‘victimized blame attribution’ against perceived elites, contributes to reduced well-being among people. These perceptions are speculated by some authors as a by-product of narcissism, theorising narcissistic rivalry as a predictor for supporting radical populist parties (Cichočka et al, 2023). At a group level, ‘collective narcissism’ with the idea that one’s group is great but unappreciated is again seen to be a predictor of prejudice, extremism and even violence.

For young people, these implications are profound, especially as children pass through their formative and pubertal maturation phase. It is in this phase that young adults also try to locate their social and political position. Because they are still searching, they are at a heightened level of susceptibility towards the populist narrative. Not to mention, if the surroundings of children, such as family, friends and school environment, are politically polarised, the effect will creep into children’s psychology. Despite the lack of research on youth and populism, psychologists have provided ample suggestions on how impressionable young adults can be to different narratives (Noack & Eckstein, 2023). Notably, the impact of political events is most pronounced on teenagers (Bartels & Jackman, 2014).

The consequences of populism on education on the first level can be seen in terms of education reforms, in terms of educational quality and efficacy. Especially because, if the narrative of social divide, insecurity, and extremism is used to also influence the school curricula, the very foundation of schools as a space for critical thinking, development, and growth will be impacted. For example, in Poland, experts have underlined that this new curriculum is underdeveloped and full of shortcomings. Children are treated as ‘objects’ and trained to be submissive and subordinated. These changes are also reflected in replacing subjects on sex education with “education for family life”, as well as shifting the emphasis on Christian ethics and conservatism, leaving little space for children’s critical thinking and forming their own beliefs.

Moreover, Rakusa-Suszczewsk (2021) further adds that children in Poland are being raised in an environment that increases nationalism and xenophobia. The transformation of schools from a place of learning to a place that invokes anxiety, fear, and moral panic can hardly be conducive to children’s best educational achievement. For instance, Gifford et al. (2025) argue that we can’t leave teachers out of the equation, as their lack of institutional trust and susceptibility to the emotional appeal of populist narratives will become conduits of such narratives in the classroom.

If the student-teacher relationship is also shaped by these ideological undercurrents, students will be increasingly exposed to populist framings even in educational spaces. If we imagine students’ home environments which are similarly influenced by politically charged discourses, combined with the role of social media, often described as “echo chambers”, children repeatedly encounter the binary construction of society as ‘us versus them’ divide. Such sustained exposure has long-term implications, influencing not only their mental states and modes of thinking during formative years but also the values and discourses they propagate as future members of society. Children who belong to family backgrounds that also resonate with such beliefs, especially subscribing to the populist narrative, will only reinforce the negative influence of populism on children’s state of well-being and educational outcomes. The compromised well-being of

children naturally interferes with the cognitive and emotional resources necessary for academic success, creating a pathway from the populist sentiment through youth well-being to educational outcomes.

However, the pathway linking educational outcome and well-being through populism is far more complex than it may initially seem. Simply focusing on the psychologically embedded bi-directional relationship between education and populism, which can be conceptualised as two sides of a complex equation. On the one side, as mentioned by experts, being less educated influences patterns of populist support. On the other side, populist political environments themselves shape educational outcomes. The position of well-being is around this relationship, as individuals with poor well-being are likely to subscribe to narratives that feed their fear and anxiety.

A range of influences facilitates this equation because confounding influences, such as a child's family or cultural and economic background, will also interplay with how young people perceive the anxiety, fear, and exclusion provoked by populism. For instance, viewing these relationships through the lens of *the economic insecurity* thesis by Inglehart & Norris (2016), children from economically weaker backgrounds will tend to experience greater consequences of fear and insecurity, as compared to children from economically stable backgrounds. This sense of deprivation will be compounded for children, especially from marginalised groups, such as immigrants and refugees, as cultural and social status shape vulnerability and exclusion.

In addition to family and school influences, children's exposure to social media also serves as a moderating platform in how they encounter information and potentially internalise populist narratives. Much of the populist narrative consists of a divisive set of ideologies that unfolds online, while connected young people are increasingly consuming content rooted in negativity, fear, and polarisation. Excessive exposure to such content can erode mental health and intensify feelings of exclusion and anxiety. This is particularly concerning because social media algorithms repeatedly surface content previously accessed, resulting in feedback loops (Noack & Eckstein, 2023). In this way, it can be much harder for children to identify reliable sources of information, and this, in turn, magnifies the psychological consequences of the populist discourse on children.

The literature points to an interconnected web of relationships where populist discourse, with its divisive narratives, fear-based messaging, and anti-establishment rhetoric, feeds psychological vulnerabilities that can influence children's well-being and subsequently impact their educational experiences and outcomes.

Recognizing the bidirectional relationship between populism and education with the interplay of well-being documented by experimental research, alongside the documented influence of populist education policies and the moderating influences of socioeconomic factors and social media exposure, I propose four interconnected hypotheses that capture and attempt to explore the multilayered relationships between populism, children's well-being, and educational outcomes, as shown in Figure 3:

- **H1: Higher levels of populism in a society are associated with decreased well-being indicators among children.**
- **H2: Higher levels of populism in a society are associated with decreased educational outcomes among children.**

- H3: Decreased well-being among children is associated with poorer educational outcomes.

- H4: The relationship between populism and educational outcomes is mediated by children's well-being

Moreover, for testing the above-mentioned hypotheses empirically, socioeconomic index, inequality, and social media use have been controlled for in the econometric analyses, as well as gender and geopolitical region. These control variables are introduced, conceptualised and technically operationalised in the data - method section below.

Figure 3

Author's Analytical Framework and Hypotheses Testing Design

3. Data – Method

3.1. Variables Choice and Dataset Construction

3.1.1. Variables Choice and Datasets

This chapter outlines the process of constructing the dataset used for this study, which mostly combines student-level data from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (OECD, 2025) with the Varieties of Party Identity and Organization (V-Party) expert-coded political party dataset (Lindberg et al., 2022). The primary goal is to study the relationship between populism, children’s well-being, and their educational outcomes over time. The PISA data include information about four dimensions: well-being indicators, education outcomes, the Economic, Social, and Cultural Status (ESCS), and social media use. The V-Party data examined not only factual data, vote and seat shares of most parties represented in parliaments worldwide during the period 1900-2019 (Lührmann et al., 2020) but also the policy positions and organisational structures of most lower chamber political parties across the world for the period 1970-2019 (Lindberg et al., 2022).

3.1.2. Dataset Construction

The dataset construction involved harmonisation of multiple waves of cross-national PISA survey data, while integrating macro-level political context using the V-Party dataset. This study also utilised the Global Party Survey (GPS) dataset (Norris, 2019) to conduct robustness checks with the V-Party dataset, as both sources provide an evaluation of the national level of populism. The GPS study used an expert survey to assess the ideological values, policy positions, and rhetoric of political parties worldwide in 2019. The Gini Index (World Bank, 2014), which measures the level of inequality, was also integrated into the dataset to serve as a control variable in analyses.

The chapter also throws light on executing meticulous cleaning, re-coding, variable construction, appending, and merging procedures, all of which will be described systematically. The final working dataset consists of observations from 49 countries, with the unit of analysis at the student level, embedded in a country-year panel structure. For each variable, Figure 4 displays an overview of variable type, label, original data source, requirements in terms of correction, update, or proxy item utilisation, indicator selection, value transformation, standardisation, and renaming operations, which are detailed in the sections below, variable by variable.

Figure 4

Dataset Construction and Operationalisation

3.1.3. Country Selection

Countries were selected based on data availability in both sources. In particular, the eligibility for selecting a country was based on whether the country had participated in at least six out of eight PISA waves: 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, and 2022 (i.e., 75% inclusion threshold). This ensured a reasonably large amount of longitudinal coverage for reliable fixed-effects regression estimates. Once selected, countries were made to match with those available in the V-Party dataset, ensuring adequate overlap over the same time frame.

The eligibility for selecting a country for the present work was based on the availability of multiple, sufficient, and reliable data across the required datasets. The first criterion was to have access to V-Party data assessing populism through specific indicators, which was the case for 178 countries. Out of these, 52 countries satisfied the second selection criterion as they have participated in at least six of the eight considered PISA editions (75% threshold). The third and fourth selection criteria were the availability of GPS and Gini Index data.

Eventually, as showcased in Figure 5 below, 49 countries met four eligibility criteria with sufficient and reliable data available in the four above datasets. The selected countries for the present study are: Albania (ALB); Argentina (ARG); Australia (AUS); Austria (AUT); Belgium (BEL); Bulgaria (BGR); Brazil (BRA); Canada (CAN); Switzerland (CHE); Chile (CHL); Czechia (CZE); Germany (DEU); Denmark (DNK); Spain (ESP); Estonia (EST); Finland (FIN); France (FRA); United Kingdom (GBR); Greece (GRC); Croatia (HRV); Hungary (HUN); Indonesia (IDN); Ireland (IRL); Iceland (ISL); Israel (ISR); Italy (ITA); Japan (JPN); South Korea (KOR); Lithuania (LTU); Luxembourg (LUX); Latvia (LVA); Mexico (MEX); Montenegro (MNE); Netherlands (NLD); Norway (NOR); Peru (PER); Poland (POL); Portugal (PRT); Romania (ROU); Russia (RUS); Serbia (SRB); Slovakia (SVK); Slovenia (SVN); Sweden (SWE); Thailand (THA); Tunisia (TUN); Türkiye (TUR); Uruguay (URY); United States (USA).

3.2. PISA Dataset

The PISA dataset (OECD, 2025) evaluates the competencies of 15-year-old students worldwide in key domains such as reading, science, and mathematics. It includes a wide array of contextual data collected through student, teacher, and school questionnaires. This study focuses on the four variable blocks constructed from PISA data, as listed below:

1. Well-being indicators – 10 harmonised items related to students’ well-being with regard to experience in school and teacher behaviour.
2. Educational outcomes – measured performance using Plausible Values (PVs) in reading and mathematics.
3. Social media use – measured by computing time spent on social networking websites and forums from the ICT student questionnaire. This is a control variable.
4. The ESCS Index (Economic, Social and Cultural Status) - a composite socioeconomic index provided by PISA. This is a control variable.

These student-level variables were harmonised across the survey waves, cleaned, renamed, and appended into a long-format dataset. Furthermore, they were merged with political context data from the V-Party Dataset, which provides party-level measures of political ideology, populism, and authoritarianism based on expert surveys. For each country-year, party-level scores were aggregated using seat-share weights to generate country-level macro-level populism indicators, which will be integrated into the analysis in later sections.

During the data construction, several data management challenges were encountered. For instance, due to differences in the questionnaire design across the survey waves, some items for social media use and the selected well-being indicators were not consistently asked, or the scale of recording answers was not consistent. In such cases, proxy variables had to be selected, and re-coding across variables was done to maintain thematic continuity. Detailed justifications for such substitutions are documented in the relevant sections of the variables below. Additionally, in 2015, not all participating countries administered the optional ICT questionnaire that includes social media questions, leading to partial missingness in that variable. Followed by no information collection on all the selected well-being indicators in 2006, and only teacher-related well-being information in 2009. The justification and method of processing data with their specific examples will also be explored in this chapter, as well as the limitations of these choices discussed in the next section.

The construction of this panel dataset lays the foundation for all subsequent empirical analysis. The next part of this describes in detail how each variable block was developed, cleaned, and made comparable over time, followed by the merging procedures across the two primary sources.

3.3. Well-Being Variable: Constructed Composite Index

3.3.1. General Introduction to the Well-Being Variable

This study constructs a composite index based on school-based student well-being indicators using data from the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) across eight survey cycles: 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, and 2022. While the PISA database is widely known for measuring cognitive skills of students in reading, mathematics, and science, it also includes an extensive set of background questionnaires capturing students' social and emotional experiences at school. These self-reported variables, although secondary in PISA's primary assessment design, have gained increasingly scholarly attention as proxies for mental health, socio-emotional development, and subjective well-being in school settings (Bücker et al., 2018).

3.3.2. Well-Being Indicators

Initially, the OECD's Child Well-being Dashboard was selected to capture multiple dimensions of student well-being (OECD, 2021). It is designed to monitor children's well-being through four core domains, such as material conditions, physical health, educational outcomes and social and emotional well-being, including aspects of family environment, school experience, community life, and online behaviour. However, due to inconsistencies in data availability across survey years and countries, it was difficult to construct a panel data model with these indicators, therefore it was ultimately dropped from the analysis.

Instead, relevant items from the PISA background questionnaires were included, as they provided more consistent and comparable measures across time and countries. While this shift improved cross national longitudinal comparability, the primary challenge remained the integration and alignment of well-being related variables across multiple PISA cycles. Nevertheless, the PISA background data offered a sufficiently rich and reliable source for exploring student well-being regarding educational, psychological and socioeconomic factors.

3.3.3. Well-Being Indicator Selection

The ten chosen indicators (considering the intersection with populism as established in the conceptual framework) from PISA fall into two main domains:

- Teacher related perceptions (4 questions): these assess how supported, respected, and fairly treated students feel by their teachers.
- Student Based emotional and social indicators (6 questions): these capture students' feelings of belonging, anxiety, loneliness and social integration at school.

Each of these 10 indicators were extracted from the student questionnaires administered during the relevant PISA cycles. However, due to inconsistencies in question design and availability and context across years,

Careful data harmonisation was required. The technical aspects of constructing a consistent set of indicators over time are detailed below, accompanied by a comprehensive table outlining the original questions and the proxy variables developed for each survey year. The following chapter then describes the implementation of Principal Component Analysis which was used to generate a composite index of student well-being for use in the subsequent regression analysis.

Table 1

Well-Being Indicators Questions from PISA

#	STATA Final Modified Indicator Name	Label	STATA Original Variable Name	PROXY / Variable Name	Question Text (original or paraphrased)	Original Response Scale/Coding	Original Direction for Well-being	Recoded Response Scale/Coding	Modified Direction for Well-being
1	TW1_getalong	Student and teacher get along	TW1_teacher_getalong	1.) 2018: "The teacher showed enjoyment in teaching." 2.) 2022: "Teachers are friendly towards me."	"Students get along well with most teachers"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
2	TW2_well	Teacher's interest in student's well-being	TW2_teacher_well-being	2018: "The teacher made me feel confident in my ability to do well in the course."	"Most teachers are interested in students' well-being"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
3	TW3_listen	Teacher really listen to students	TW3_teachers_listento_students	1.) 2018: "The teacher listened to my view on how to do things." 2.) 2022: "When my teachers ask how I am doing, they are really interested"	"Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
4	TW4_fair	Teacher treats students fairly	TW4_teachers_treat_fairly	1.) 2018: "The teacher shows an interest in every student's learning." 2.) 2022: "The teachers at my school are respectful towards me."	"Most of my teachers treat me fairly"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
5	SW1_outsider	Student feels like an outsider	SW1_feel_an_outsider		"I feel like an outsider (or left out of things)"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Negative	0 = Strongly agree 1 = Agree 2 = Disagree 3 = Strongly disagree	Positive
6	SW2_friends	Student makes friends easily	SW2_make_friends_easily		"I make friends easily"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
7	SW3_belong	Student feels belonging	SW3_feel_I_belong		"Feel like I belong"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
8	SW4_awkward	Student feels awkward or out of place	SW4_feel_awkward_outofplace		"I feel awkward and out of place"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Negative	0 = Strongly agree 1 = Agree 2 = Disagree 3 = Strongly disagree	Positive
9	SW5_liked	Student feels he/she is liked	SW5_think_Iam_liked		"Other students seem to like me"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Positive
10	SW6_lonely	Student feels lonely	SW6_feel_lonely		"I feel lonely"	0 = Strongly disagree 1 = Disagree 2 = Agree 3 = Strongly agree	Negative	0 = Strongly agree 1 = Agree 2 = Disagree 3 = Strongly disagree	Positive

As shown in Table 1, the first set of indicators captures information on teacher-student relationships, which research has shown to contribute to student motivation, efficacy and holistic learning (Cornelius-White, 2007). The item “*students get along well with most teachers*” (TW1_getalong) measures how students perceive harmony and mutual respect between students and teachers, while “*Most teachers are interested in students' well-being*” (TW2_well) underlines the degree to which students feel their personal welfare is valued by their teachers. Both indicators are associated with feelings of support and connectedness, which can reduce the risk of student disengagement at school. A third item, “*Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say*” (TW3_listen), reflects the perceptions of voice and agency in the classroom, aligning with findings that state active listening by teachers fosters a supportive learning environment for students

(Paramole, O. C., Adeoye, M. A., Arowosaye, S. A., & Ibikunle, Y. A, 2024). Similarly, “*Most of my teachers treat me fairly*” (TW4_fair) assesses whether students feel respected by their teachers.

The second group of indicators capture aspects of peer relationships and social integration, these dimensions are strongly associated with resilience, academic persistence, and emotional stability, as research demonstrates that students with stronger peer connections experience greater resilience and fewer depressive feelings. Conversely, young adults who may feel like an outsider or experience rejection from their peer groups, face heightened risks of poor psychological well-being. (Bukowski et al., 2009).

The measurement of well-being within this domain reflects distinct and interconnected aspects of social well-being. Items such as “*I feel like an outsider*” (SW1_outsider) and “*I feel awkward or out of place*” (SW4_awkward) capture experiences of social exclusion, which research associates with poor well-being. These feelings of marginalisation can impact both well-being and academic performance.

In contrast, “*Other students seem to like me*” (SW5_like) measures perceived social acceptance and network. Furthermore, items like “*I make friends easily*” (SW2_friends) “*Feel I belong*” (SW3_belong) assess the student’s capacity for social connection and their sense of integration in their school community. These indicators are particularly crucial for capturing well-being at school, as they reflect the fulfillment of fundamental human needs for relatedness and belonging, even in the context of a learning environment as it contributes to a conducive environment essential for holistic learning. (Cornelius-White, 2007)

The inclusion of “*I feel lonely at school*” (SW6_lonely) gives a counterbalance, acknowledging loneliness as a distinct state that can persist even in the presence of superficial social contact (Qualter et al., 2015). This item can also help capture the subjective quality of social relationships, rather than just quantity of relationships, recognising the existence of perceived isolation, regardless of actual social contact.

By combining teacher-student relationship measures with indicators of integration and belonging, this framework offers an operationalisation of school based well-being. It recognizes that well-being is not a singular feeling, rather an element of subjectivity and of sustained positive interactions across the school environment. This conceptualisation allows for cross-national and longitudinal analysis, enabling the exploration of well-being among 15 year olds across time and countries.

3.3.4. Data Harmonisation and Re-Coding Strategy

To maintain consistency and granularity of well-being information across cycles, all well-being indicators (including proxies) were re-coded into a 0 to 3 scale, this is done in order to preserve ordinal distinctions where possible.

- 0 = “*Strongly disagree*” (lowest mark on well-being, e.g., to “*I feel I belong at school*”)
- 1 = “*Disagree*”
- 2 = “*Agree*”
- 3 = “*Strongly agree*” (highest mark on well-being)

In cases where the direction of the response was negatively worded, e.g., ‘‘ *I feel an outsider at school*’’ where a response of ‘‘ *strongly agree*’’ would signify poor or lowest mark on well-being, thus it was coded as 0, whereas a response of ‘‘ *strongly disagree*’’ would signify highest mark on well-being, and it was coded as 3. Therefore, such items were reverse coded so that higher values consistently indicated better well-being.

3.3.5. Handling Inconsistencies and Usage of Proxies

Not all well-being related questions were consistently asked and included across all PISA cycles by OECD. For instance, in 2006, the student questionnaire did not contain these ten questions that directly addressed either student emotional well-being or teacher relationships (OECD, 2009). Despite the extensive review of the questionnaire, there was a failure in identifying valid proxies with comparable face or construct validity. As a result, well-being indicators for 2006 are coded as missing. Similarly, in 2009, only the four teacher-student relationship related questions were retained, whereas the six questions on student emotional well-being were not asked in that cycle. To mitigate the gap on the data, interpolation was performed on these indicators, as shown on Figure 6 below.

In contrast, in 2018 and 2022, the four teacher-student relationship questions had inconsistencies, as the exact same questions were not included in the questionnaire, instead the questions were modified by OECD. In these cases, as shown in Figure 7, proxy variables were employed, carefully in order to capture the same information on the teacher-student relationship. While the use of proxies is methodologically defensible, it can introduce the risk of measurement error, particularly when the proxy does not fully capture the latent construct intended (Bound, Brown, & Mathiowetz, 2001). These risks are salient for abstract constructs such as well-being, where differences in wording, cultural interpretation and response format may alter the psychological meaning of a response (Deaton & Stone, 2013). To mitigate these risks, all proxies were carefully documented, harmonised and tested for internal consistency.

The year 2015 also had anomalies in the way the ten questions were asked. While the six student related questions were asked in a consistent format similar to other years, the four teacher-student relationship questions were asked in a separate questionnaire e.g., Education career questionnaire. However, there were two major issues of this anomaly in 2015. First, the Education career questionnaire was administered to an optional list of countries, thus only selected countries had data on these four teacher-student relationship questions in 2015, resulting in a large amount of missing data. Secondly, the response format of these questions was different as compared to the usual format asked in the rest of the PISA years. For example, instead of a 4 point Likert scale of ‘‘ *Strongly disagree*’’ to ‘‘ *Strongly agree*’’, it was in a 3-point response format of ‘‘ *More likely in my regular school lessons*’’, ‘‘ *no difference*’’ and ‘‘ *More likely in my additional instruction*’’. Therefore due to these anomalies for this year, while analysing the trends of these indicators over items it can be seen on Figure 6 below the dip in teacher-student relationship indicators. Ultimately, these indicators for 2015 had to be dropped from the dataset and interpolation was performed thereafter to maintain the consistency of items. Figure 6 below showcases the scenario with original 2015 values, whereas Figure 7 showcases the scenario after intrapolation was performed in 2015, together with 2006 and 2009 data.

Figure 6

Trends of Well-Being Indicators (Original 2015 Values)

Figure 7

Trends of Well-Being Indicators (Intrapolation in 2015)

3.3.6. Educational Outcome Indicators and PISA Edition Years

Since these indicators are retrieved from PISA studies, the values' year is obviously the PISA edition year.

3.3.7. Well-Being Values Transformation

The standardisation (“Z” variable) and subsequent Principal Component Analysis (PCA) used to construct a composite index based on the above Well-Being indicators are discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.4. Educational Outcome Variable: Average Plausible Value

3.4.1. General Introduction to the Educational Outcome Variable

Then large scale educational assessments such as PISA, educational outcome is measured through a system of plausible values (PVs), which is a set of multiple imputations of students’ plausible and latent proficiency scores in different domains. Instead of reporting a single estimate of ability, PVs are generated using item response theory and information about the background of responses, therefore plausible values can’t be used to compare individuals. Instead, these can be used to estimate the characteristics of the population, such as subgroup means and standard deviations (OECD, 2017). This method acknowledges the intrinsic uncertainty of measuring the achievement of students in a limited test setting and also allows for unbiased estimates of population level parameters. (Mislevy, 1991). Essentially, “plausible values represent the range of abilities that a student might reasonably have, given their responses and background information” (Wu and Adams, 2002, as cited in OECD, 2009, p. 98).

To obtain reliable estimates, each plausible value should be used separately in analyses, and results should be aggregated across all PVs, with appropriate standard errors calculated to account for both sampling variability and measurement uncertainty (OECD, 2009). This approach helps address the challenge of measuring an unobservable latent ability, using a limited set of test items and prevents biased conclusions about population performance. (Rutkowski et al., 2010)

3.4.2. Educational Outcome Indicators and their Selection

For the purpose of this study, reading and mathematics proficiency were selected as the core indicators of educational outcomes. Both of these domains are central to students’ academic and lifelong learning, and they serve as strong predictors of extended educational attainment, labour market outcomes and broader social participation (Hanushek & Woessmann, 2012; OECD, 2019). Reading captures the ability to interpret and comprehend complex tasks, while mathematics reflects problem-solving, reasoning and analytical skills, these together provide a balanced representation of students’ cognitive competencies and underpinned academic outcomes.

3.4.3. Educational Outcome Indicators and PISA Edition Years

Since these indicators are retrieved from PISA studies, the values' year is obviously the PISA edition year.

3.4.4. PISA-Based Computation of Individual Educational Outcome Level

From 2000 to 2012, there are five plausible values for each student for mathematics and reading, whereas from 2015 onwards, the OECD has released 10 plausible values per subject domain. For this study, the plausible values were averaged within the domain to provide stable proficiency measures for reading and mathematics separately. Subsequent analysis revealed a strong positive correlation of 0.8677 between the average plausible values of mathematics and reading. Therefore, these were combined to generate a single averaged out score, consistent with previous research where plausible values of PISA are often combined to analyse academic achievements (Rutkowski et al., 2010). In this manner, the operationalisation of a single composite score of educational outcomes has been carried out.

Moreover, reading and mathematics outcomes in terms of average plausible values are highly correlated ($R = 0.868$), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Matrix of Correlations between the Average Plausible Values of Mathematics and Reading

Matrix of correlations		
Variables	(1)	(2)
(1) pv avg math	1.000	
(2) pv avg read	0.868	1.000

3.4.5. Educational Outcome Values Transformation

The standardisation (“Z” variable) process applied to the single composite scores of educational outcomes is discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.5. V-Party Data

3.5.1. General Introduction to the V-Party Dataset

This populism data was retrieved from the Varieties of Party Identity and Organization (V-Party) dataset, produced by the V-Dem Institute, examining not only factual data, vote and seat shares of most parties represented in parliaments worldwide during the period 1900-2019 (Lührmann et al., 2020) but also the policy positions and organizational structures of most lower chamber political parties across the world for the period 1970-2019 (Lindberg et al., 2022).

The technical details about the V-Party study are available in Appendix I.

3.5.2. V-Party Indicators

Fifteen indicators and two indices were generated on a party-year basis, along with gathered details regarding election results, party identification, and party structure. The fifteen 0–4-scale, 0–5-scale or 0–6-scale indicators, together with their respective STATA Modified V-Party Indicator Name, label, V-Party Indicator Original Name, Original Question to Answer, Original Response Scale/Coding, Original Direction for Populism, Re-coded Response Scale/Coding, and Modified Direction for Populism are available in Table 3. Wherever a higher original indicator score corresponded to a lower level of populism, the score was inverted through re-coding the answers to ensure a systematic correspondence between a high indicator value and a high level of populism.

Table 3

V-Party Indicators

#	STATA Modified V-Party Indicator Name	Label	V-Party Indicator Original Name	Original Question to Answer	Original Response Scale/Coding	Original Direction for Populism	Recoded Response Scale/Coding	Modified Direction for Populism
1	V-Party_Ind_01_Antielitism	Anti-elitism	v2paanteli	How important is anti-elite rhetoric for this party?	0: Not at all important. 1: Not important. 2: Somewhat important. 3: Important. 4: Very important	Positive	0: Not at all important. 1: Not important. 2: Somewhat important. 3: Important. 4: Very important	Positive
2	V-Party_Ind_02_Peoplecentrism	People-centrism	v2papeople	Do leaders of this party glorify the ordinary people and identify themselves as part of them?	0: Never. 1: Usually not. 2: About half of the time 3: Usually. 4: Always.	Positive	0: Never. 1: Usually not. 2: About half of the time. 3: Usually. 4: Always.	Positive
3	V-Party_Ind_03_Politicalopponents	Political opponents	v2paopresp	Prior to this election, have leaders of this party used severe personal attacks or tactics of demonization against their opponents?	0: Always. 1: Usually. 2: About half of the time. 3: Usually not. 4: Never.	Negative	0: Never. 1: Usually not. 2: About half of the time. 3: Usually. 4: Always.	Positive
4	V-Party_Ind_04_Politicalpluralism	Political pluralism	v2paplur	Prior to this election, to what extent was the leadership of this political party clearly committed to free and fair elections with multiple parties, freedom of speech, media, assembly, and association?	0: Not at all committed. 1: Not committed. 2: Weakly committed. 3: Committed. 4: Fully committed.	Negative	0: Fully committed. 1: Committed. 2: Weakly committed. 3: Not committed. 4: Not at all committed.	Positive
5	V-Party_Ind_05_Minorityrights	Minority rights	v2paminor	According to the leadership of this party, how often should the will of the majority be implemented even if doing so would violate the rights of minorities?	0: Always. 1: Usually. 2: About half of the time. 3: Usually not. 4: Never.	Negative	0: Never. 1: Usually not. 2: About half of the time. 3: Usually. 4: Always.	Positive
6	V-Party_Ind_06_Rejectionofpolitical violence	Rejection of political violence	v2paviol	To what extent does the leadership of this party explicitly discourage the use of violence against domestic political opponents?	0: Encourages. 1: Sometimes encourages. 2: Discourages about half of the time. 3: Generally discourages. 4: Consistently discourages.	Negative	0: Consistently discourages. 1: Generally discourages. 2: Discourages about half of the time. 3: Sometimes encourages. 4: Encourages.	Positive
7	V-Party_Ind_07_Immigration	Immigration	v2painmig	What is the party's position regarding immigration into the country?	0: Strongly opposes. 1: Opposes. 2: Ambiguous/No position. 3: Supports. 4: Strongly supports.	Negative	0: Strongly supports. 1: Supports. 2: Ambiguous/No position. 3: Opposes. 4: Strongly opposes.	Positive
8	V-Party_Ind_08_LGBTsocial equality (discarded)	LGBT social equality	v2palgbt	What is this party's position toward social equality for the lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) community?	0: Strongly opposes. 1: Opposes. 2: Ambiguous/No position. 3: Supports. 4: Strongly supports.	Negative	0: Strongly supports. 1: Supports. 2: Ambiguous/No position. 3: Opposes. 4: Strongly opposes.	Positive
9	V-Party_Ind_09_Cultural superiority	Cultural superiority	v2paculsup	To what extent does the party leadership promote the cultural superiority of a specific social group or the nation as a whole?	0: Strongly promotes. 1: Promotes. 2: Ambiguous. 3: Opposes. 4: Strongly opposes.	Negative	0: Strongly opposes. 1: Opposes. 2: Ambiguous. 3: Promotes. 4: Strongly promotes.	Positive
10	V-Party_Ind_10_Religiousprinciple	Religious principles	v2parelig	To what extent does this party invoke God, religion, or sacred/religious texts to justify its positions?	0: Always, or almost always. 1: Often, but not always. 2: About half of the time. 3: Rarely. 4: Never.	Negative	0: Never. 1: Rarely. 2: About half of the time. 3: Often, but not always. 4: Always, or almost always.	Positive
11	V-Party_Ind_11_Genderequality (discarded)	Gender Equality	v2pagender	What is the share of women in national-level leadership positions of this political party? Clarification: This question does NOT concern the share of women in the legislature.	0: None. 1: Small minority (about 1-15%). 2: Medium minority (about 16-25%). 3: Large minority (about 26-39%). 4: Balanced (about 40% or more).	Negative	0: Balanced (about 40% or more). 1: Large minority (about 26-39%). 2: Medium minority (about 16-25%). 3: Small minority (about 1-15%). 4: None.	Positive
12	V-Party_Ind_12_Workingwomen	Working women	v2pawomlab	To what extent does this party support the equal participation of women in the labor market?	0: Strongly opposes. 1: Opposes. 2: Ambiguous. 3: Promotes. 4: Strongly promotes.	Negative	0: Strongly promotes. 1: Promotes. 2: Ambiguous. 3: Opposes. 4: Strongly opposes.	Positive
13	V-Party_Ind_13_Economicleftright scale	Economic left-right scale	v2pariglef	Please locate the party in terms of its overall ideological stance on economic issues	0: Far-left. 1: Left. 2: Center-left. 3: Center. 4: Center-right. 5: Right. 6: Far-right.	Positive	0: Far-left. 1: Left. 2: Center-left. 3: Center. 4: Center-right. 5: Right. 6: Far-right.	Positive
14	V-Party_Ind_14_Welfare	Welfare	v2pawelf	To what extent does the party promote means-tested or universalistic welfare policies?	0: The party does not support either type of policies and opposes any public welfare policy. 1: The party solely promotes means-tested welfare policies. 2: The party mainly promotes means-tested policies, but a significant portion (e.g. 1/4 or 1/3) is universalistic and potentially benefits everyone in the population. 3: The party roughly equally supports means-tested and universalistic welfare policies. 4: The party mainly promotes universalistic policies, but a significant portion (e.g. 1/4 or 1/3) of its policies are means-tested. 5: The party solely promotes universalistic welfare policies for all groups of the society.	Negative	0: The party solely promotes universalistic welfare policies for all groups of the society. 1: The party mainly promotes universalistic policies, but a significant portion (e.g. 1/4 or 1/3) of its policies are means-tested. 2: The party roughly equally supports means-tested and universalistic welfare policies. 3: The party mainly promotes means-tested policies, but a significant portion (e.g. 1/4 or 1/3) is universalistic and potentially benefits everyone in the population. 4: The party solely promotes means-tested welfare policies. 5: The party does not support either type of policies and opposes any public welfare policy.	Positive
15	V-Party_Ind_15_Clientelism	Clientelism	v2paclient	To what extent do the party and its candidates provide targeted and excludable (clientelistic) goods and benefits - such as consumer goods, cash or preferential access to government services - in an effort to keep and gain votes?	0: Not at all. 1: A minor extent. 2: A moderate extent. 3: A large extent. 4: As its main effort.	Positive	0: Not at all. 1: A minor extent. 2: A moderate extent. 3: A large extent. 4: As its main effort.	Positive

3.5.3. V-Party Indicator Selection

All V-Party indicators but two were selected. Both indices were discarded.

The first generated index in the V-Party study was the Anti-Pluralism Index (v2xpa_antiplural), computed as a transformed weighted average of the Political opponents (v2paopresp), Political pluralism (v2paplur), Minority rights (v2paminor), and Rejection of political violence (v2paviol) variables. The second generated index was the Populism Index (v2xpa_popul), computed as the harmonic mean of rescaled Anti-elitism (v2paanteli) and People-centrism (2papeople) variables variations. Both these indices were discarded as all their composite indicators were used individually in the present study. Moreover, including any of these indices would have led to a redundant use of some selected, partial information.

Both the V-Party_Ind_08_LGBTsocialequal indicator (LGBT social equality) and the V-Party_Ind_11_Genderequality (gender equality) indicator were discarded. As showcased on Figure 6, a detailed review of the gender equality indicator values, including a modified (positive) direction for populism, reveals a drop from 2000 to 2022, which contrasts with the other indicators' variation over time. Therefore, to prevent contamination of the overall populism level and to ensure more coherence in the measurements, this indicator was discarded. Moreover, comparative Principal Component Analyses (see below) were conducted with and without these two indicators, showing no difference.

Figure 6

Drop of LGBT & Gender Equality Values

It is hypothesized that the share of women in national-level leadership positions does not reflect the level of populism as much as it did in the 20th century in a context of a higher patriarchal society. Furthermore, cases are not rare of women leading parties assessed as highly populist since 2000, while women's

emancipation and empowerment have become stronger and more popular since then. Since the LGBT social equality also regards gender, analyses were run with and without it to assess its impact on the results of the present study. Since there was no significant difference between these two options, the indicator was also discarded.

All used expert-coded variables save the political pluralism indicator (“v2paplr” in the V-Party dataset) converged according to strict V-Dem convergence criteria (no more than 5% of any set of parameters had Gelman-Rubin diagnostic values greater than 1.01). It appears that much of the lack of convergence in the political pluralism indicator is due to great expert disagreement in several countries. Nevertheless, this variable was kept as a valuable estimate for this study.

3.5.4. V-Party Indicators and PISA Edition Years

The V-Party populism data used for the analysis in a given PISA edition year and a given country is the one related to the latest election in this country before that PISA edition year. This choice is motivated as follows, considering that the PISA tests take place from March (as from 2003) or April (only in 2000) to May (all selected editions). The assessed populism level potentially linked to education outcome and well-being level of youth is the one that was present during a certain lap of time (at least a few months) in the country before the PISA tests, not the one measured during simultaneous elections, nor very recent elections (i.e. haven taken place only a few months before the PISA tests). Education outcome and well-being both reflect processes in time, not instantaneous phenomena. The table of V-Party election years and PISA edition years (Appendix A) gives an overview of which election results (in terms of seat shares) were used for each PISA edition year data.

Furthermore, a short explanation is required regarding the 2014 election in Thailand (THA). Indeed, on March 21, 2014, Thailand's Constitutional Court annulled the February House of Representatives general election. The Constitutional Court ruled in a 6-to-3 verdict that the results would be invalidated due to disruptions at polling stations on Election Day and because voting could not be held in all districts on the same day (<https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/2442>).

3.5.5. Update of the V-Party Dataset Related to the Time Limitation of the V-Party Study

Specific updates were brought into the V-Party dataset for two reasons. On the one hand, this was needed as the V-Party study was stopped in 2019. On the other hand, some incoherences and mistakes were found in the dataset.

The details of the numerous updates of the V-Party dataset due to the time limitation of the V-Party study are available in Appendix B.

3.5.6. Updates of the V-Party Dataset Related to Incoherences or Possible Mistakes

Regarding incoherences or possible mistakes found in the V-Party database, a detailed review of the conducted updates is available in Appendix C. The V-Party team will be humbly and kindly informed about these updates regarding the 2016 Russian election and the 2018 election in the USA.

3.5.7. V-Party-Based Computation of National Levels of Populism per Indicator

The V-Party national level of populism for a given indicator (among 13 selected V-Party indicators), in a given country and a given year, was calculated by weighing each party's given expert-assessed populism level according to the party's seat share among the total cumulated seat share of all assessed parties in the same country and year. The seat shares were not rounded like they were (to the tenth) in the V-Party study, which required calculating them all again. Appendix K provides details relating thereto.

3.5.8. V-Party Values Transformation

The variable version used was the model estimate variable (*e.g.* v2elmulpar), which provides country–party–year point estimates from the V–Dem measurement model (Pemstein et al. 2020). The measurement model aggregates the ratings provided by multiple country experts and, taking disagreement and measurement error into account, produces a probability distribution over country–party–year scores on a standardized interval scale. The point estimates are the median values of these distributions for each country–party–and year. The scale of a measurement model variable is similar to a normal (“Z”) score (*e.g.* typically between -5 and 5, with 0 approximately representing the mean for all country–party–years in the sample) though it does not necessarily follow a normal distribution. As mentioned by the authors of the survey, for most purposes, these are the preferred versions of the variables for time series regression and other estimation strategies.

These scores were subsequently standardized into a “Z” variable with a distribution characterized by a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, based on all values of a given indicator across all parties and years for the selected countries, although this distribution could be different from a perfect Bell distribution. The standardized variables were renamed in the “z_VDem_Ind_01_Antielitism” format. This operation ensures a similar scale for all indicators, before proceeding with the principal component analysis (PCA), which allocates the respective weight to each indicator into the overall populism assessment. Indeed, although the model estimate is already similar to a normal score, without ensuring a normal distribution, each indicator has its own mean and standard deviation in terms of model estimate. Hence, standardization was used to ensure each indicator has a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The standardized indicator value for a party in a given country and a given year measures the level of populism of this party at that time in terms of standard deviations above (if positive) or below (if negative) the mean populism level of all parties across selected countries over time.

The standardisation (“Z” variable) and subsequent Principal Component Analysis (PCA) used to construct a composite index based on the above V-Party populism expert-assessed indicators are discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.6. Populism Variable: Global Party Survey (GPS)

3.6.1. General Introduction to the GPS Dataset

The Global Party Survey (GPS – Norris, 2019) was an independent academic research project based at Harvard University. It used an expert survey to assess the ideological values, policy positions, and rhetoric of political parties worldwide. It generated a party-level dataset covering 1,043 political parties in 163 countries, based upon estimates from 1,861 experts on political parties, public opinion, elections, and legislative behaviour. Starting on November 19, 2019, these experts evaluated parties in the country where they had their main expertise.

The technical details about the GPS study are available in Appendix J.

3.6.2. GPS Indicators

On the one hand, eighteen indicators (V4 to V21) were coded on a party-year basis, evaluating ideological values, policy issues, and populist rhetoric, along with gathered details regarding election results, as well as the identification and structure of each party. On the other hand, three indicators (V1 to V3) were coded, but not used in this study, regarding the expert’s familiarity with each assessed party, an evaluation of the party’s unity, and the degree of its program precision (detailed versus vague).

The eighteen 0–10-scale indicators, together with their respective STATA Modified GPS Indicator Name, label, GPS Indicator Original Name, Original Question to Answer, Original Response Scale/Coding, Original Direction for Populism, Re-coded Response Scale/Coding, and Modified Direction for Populism are available in Table 4. Wherever a higher original indicator score corresponded to a lower level of populism, the score was inverted through re-coding the answers to ensure a systematic correspondence between a high indicator value and a high level of populism.

Table 4

Global Party Survey (GPS) Indicators (Part I)

#	STATA Modified GPS Indicator Name	Label	GPS Indicator Original Name	Original Question to Answer	Original Response Scale/Coding	Original Direction for Populism	Recoded Response Scale/Coding	Modified Direction for Populism
4	Original_GPS_Ind04_Left-Right_Economic_Issues	Ideological values - Economic issues. Left-Right	V4 Economic left-right	Parties can be classified by their current stance on economic issues. (...) Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (extreme economic left) to 10 (extreme economic right)	-	Continuous scale: from 0 (extreme economic left) to 10 (extreme economic right)	-
5	Original_GPS_Ind05_Left-Right_Economic_Issues_Saliency (Discarded)	Ideological values - Economic issues. Left-Right. Saliency	V5 L-R saliency	How important are economic issues for each of the following parties? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (no importance) to 10 (great importance)	-	Continuous scale from 0 (no importance) to 10 (great importance)	-
6	Original_GPS_Ind06_Liberalism-Conservatism_Social_Values	Ideological values - Social values. Liberalism-Conservatism	V6 Social Liberalism-Conservatism	Parties can also be classified by their current social values. (...) Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (very liberal) to 10 (very conservative)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (very liberal) to 10 (very conservative)	Positive
7	Original_GPS_Ind07_Liberalism-Conservatism_Social_Values_Saliency (Discarded)	Ideological values - Social values. Liberalism-Conservatism. Saliency	V7 Social values saliency	How important are liberal/conservative social values for each of the following parties? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (no importance) to 10 (great importance)	-	Continuous scale from 0 (no importance) to 10 (great importance)	-
8	Original_GPS_Ind08_Populist_Rhetoric	Ideological values - Populist rhetoric	V8 Populist rhetoric	Parties can also be classified by their current use of populist or pluralist rhetoric. (...) Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (Strongly favors pluralist rhetoric) to 10 (Strongly favors populist rhetoric)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (Strongly favors pluralist rhetoric) to 10 (Strongly favors populist rhetoric)	Positive
9	Original_GPS_Ind09_Populist_Rhetoric_Saliency (Discarded)	Ideological values - Populist rhetoric. Saliency	V9 Populist saliency	How important is populist rhetoric currently for each of the following parties? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (no importance) to 10 (great importance)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (no importance) to 10 (great importance)	Positive
10	Original_GPS_Ind10_Immigration_Policies	Policy Issues - Immigration	V10 Immigration	(...) Where do parties currently stand on immigration? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors liberal immigration policies) to 10 (strongly favors restrictive immigration policies)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors liberal immigration policies) to 10 (strongly favors restrictive immigration policies)	Positive

Table 5

Global Party Survey (GPS) Indicators (Part II)

#	STATA Modified GPS Indicator Name	Label	GPS Indicator Original Name	Original Question to Answer	Original Response Scale/Coding	Original Direction for Populism	Recorded Response Scale/Coding	Modified Direction for Populism
11	Original_GPS_Ind11_Public_Spending_vs_Taxation (Discarded)	Policy Issues - Public spending versus taxation	V11 Spending v. Tax	Where do parties currently stand on public spending versus taxation? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors increased public spending) to 10 (strongly favors reduced taxation)	-	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors increased public spending) to 10 (strongly favors reduced taxation)	-
12	Original_GPS_Ind12_Environmental_Protection	Policy Issues - Environmental protection	V12 Environment	Where do parties currently stand on the issue of environmental protection? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors environmental protection) to 10 (strongly opposes environmental protection)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors environmental protection) to 10 (strongly opposes environmental protection)	Positive
13	Original_GPS_Ind13_Nationalism	Policy Issues - Nationalism	V13 Nationalism	Where do parties currently stand on nationalism versus multilateralism? (...) Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors nationalism) to 10 (strongly favors multilateralism)	Negative	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors multilateralism) to 10 (strongly favors nationalism)	Positive
14	Original_GPS_Ind14_Rights_of_Women	Policy Issues - Rights of women	V14 Women's rights	Where do parties currently stand on women's rights? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors women's rights) to 10 (strongly opposes women's rights)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors women's rights) to 10 (strongly opposes women's rights)	Positive
15	Original_GPS_Ind15_Ethnic_Minority_Rights	Policy Issues - Ethnic minority rights	V15 Ethnic minority rights	Where do parties currently stand on ethnic minority rights? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors ethnic minority rights) to 10 (strongly opposes ethnic minority rights)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors ethnic minority rights) to 10 (strongly opposes ethnic minority rights)	Positive
16	Original_GPS_Ind16_Liberal_Democracy	Policy Issues - Liberal democratic principles	V16 Liberal democracy	Where do parties currently stand on liberal democratic principles, norms and practices? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly respects liberal democratic, principles, norms and practices) to 10 (strongly undermines liberal democratic principles, norms and practices)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly respects liberal democratic, principles, norms and practices) to 10 (strongly undermines liberal democratic principles, norms and practices)	Positive
17	Original_GPS_Ind17_Clientelism	Policy Issues - Clientelism	V17 Clientelism	On clientelism, where do parties currently stand on (...) giving universally to all citizens or else primarily to their own supporters? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors universal distribution to all citizens) to 10 (strongly favors distribution mainly to their own supporters)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors universal distribution to all citizens) to 10 (strongly favors distribution mainly to their own supporters)	Positive

Table 6

Global Party Survey (GPS) Indicators (Part III)

#	STATA Modified GPS Indicator Name	Label	GPS Indicator Original Name	Original Question to Answer	Original Response Scale/Coding	Original Direction for Populism	Recoded Response Scale/Coding	Modified Direction for Populism
18	Original_GPS_Ind18_Will_of_the_People	Populist rhetoric - Will of the people	V18 Will of the people	Next we seek to understand the type of rhetoric commonly used by each party, such as in their leadership speeches, rallies, press releases, party platforms, and campaign communications. Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly emphasizes that politicians should follow the will of the people) to 10 (strongly emphasizes that politicians should lead public opinion)	Negative	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly emphasizes that politicians should lead public opinion) to 10 (strongly emphasizes that politicians should follow the will of the people)	Positive
19	Original_GPS_Ind19_People_Should_Decide	Populist rhetoric - People should decide	V19 People should decide	How would you characterize the rhetoric commonly used by various parties on whether the people or leaders should decide important issues? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly emphasizes that ordinary people should decide important issues) to 10 (strongly emphasizes that leaders should decide important issues)	Negative	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly emphasizes that leaders should decide important issues) to 10 (strongly emphasizes that ordinary people should decide important issues)	Positive
20	Original_GPS_Ind20_Politicians_Corruption_Emphasis	Populist rhetoric - Politicians' corruption emphasis	V20 Politicians corrupt	How would you characterize the rhetoric commonly used by various parties on whether most politicians are honest or corrupt? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly emphasizes that most politicians are honest and trustworthy) to 10 (strongly emphasizes that most politicians are dishonest and corrupt)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly emphasizes that most politicians are honest and trustworthy) to 10 (strongly emphasizes that most politicians are dishonest and corrupt)	Positive
21	Original_GPS_Ind21_Strongman_Rule	Populist rhetoric - Strongman rule	V21 Strongman rule	How would you characterize the rhetoric commonly used by various parties towards checks and balances on executive power? Where would you place each party on the following scale?	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors checks and balances on executive power) to 10 (strongly opposes checks and balances on executive power)	Positive	Continuous scale from 0 (strongly favors checks and balances on executive power) to 10 (strongly opposes checks and balances on executive power)	Positive

3.6.3. GPS Indicators Selection

Some GPS indicators were discarded. First, the GPS saliency indicators V5, V7, and V9 were discarded as they only measure the importance of economic issues, liberal/conservative social values, and populist rhetoric for each party, whereas the selected GPS indicators V4, V6, and V8 assess the party's stance on these issues. Ideally, for each pair of indicators {V4-V5}, {V6-V7}, and {V8-V9}, a computed combination of both indicators would give a more detailed evaluation. Indeed, a higher saliency *per se* can be supposed to reinforce the party's position, whereas a low saliency *per se* will limit the impact of the same position. Nevertheless, high saliency can be found at any level of populism. It is the combination of both stance and saliency that gives detailed information about the party's identity. However, no indicator was generated in the GPS study to combine each pair of these indicators. In conclusion, the GPS saliency indicators alone do not seem to provide much information about the level of populism. Hence, only the GPS indicators V4, V6, and V8, assessing the party's stances on economic issues, liberal/conservative social values, and populist rhetoric, were selected.

GPS indicator V11 was discarded in the present study because, as reported in the GPS codebook (GPS – Norris, 2019), the correlation between, on the one hand, the GPS V11 indicator assessing where the party stands on public spending versus taxation, and, on the other hand, the PopuList populism classification of parties from 31 European countries (only), was not significant ($R=0.052$). The PopuList study (Rooduijn et al., 2019), contemporary to the GPS study, consisted of thirty populism scholars' classification of 127 parties across Europe with a minimum 2% vote share in a national parliamentary election since 1998. Binary codes (0/1) were used to evaluate parties on four levels (populism, far right, far left, and, for the parties that belong to one of these categories at least, Euroscepticism). Furthermore, the dimension of public spending versus taxation assessment is included in the GPS indicator V4 value, evaluating the party's position on economic issues (left-right). The latter indicator was selected for this study, despite a non-significant correlation with the PopuList populism classification, to keep a GPS measurement of left-right position in the robustness check between GPS and V-Party expert-coded populism levels.

All other GPS indicators were selected.

3.6.4. GPS Indicators and PISA Edition Years

The main limitation of the GPS 2019 study lies in its one-time assessment of the political situation in 2019. Although a second GPS study was initiated in early 2023, the present study covers the time period 2000-2022.

3.6.5. Update of the GPS Dataset Related to Approximations, Missing Values, Incoherences, or Possible Mistakes in the GPS Study

Some GPS data update was required regarding the seat share and the GPS indicator values. The missing values for some countries were fetched from various data sources, as detailed in Appendix D.

The seat share values provided in the GPS dataset are rounded to the tenth (*e.g.* 10.3). Due to this approximation, the cumulated total percentages of lower chamber representation sometimes exceeded 100.0% (100.1% in the case of Australia (AUS) and Austria (AUT), among many other countries, or even 100.2% in the case of Indonesia (IDN)). This was corrected by creating and using unrounded seat share values.

In the case of Germany (DEU), the cumulated total percentage of lower chamber representation reached 118.5%. This was corrected by updating the GPS data as detailed in Appendix E.

For some parties in selected countries, some indicator values were missing in the GPS dataset, a complete list of which can be found in Appendix E. The worldwide mean value systematically replaced the missing indicator value in these cases (estimation towards the mean). Among parties that won more than 10% of the seats, four were incompletely assessed, with a maximum of four missing GPS values in this case.

3.6.6. GPS-Based Computation of National Levels of Populism per Indicator

The GPS national level of populism for a given indicator (among 14 selected GPS indicators), in a given country in 2019, was calculated by weighing each party's given expert-assessed populism level according to the party's seat share among the total cumulated seat share of all assessed parties in the same country in 2019. The seat shares were not rounded like they were (to the tenth) in the GPS study, which required calculating them all again. Appendix L provides details relating thereto.

3.6.7. GPS Values Transformation

The variable version used was the model estimate variable (*e.g.* V4_Scale or V10), which provides country-party point estimates on a 0–10 scale. Wherever a higher original indicator score corresponded to a lower level of populism, the score was inverted through re-coding the answers to ensure a systematic correspondence between a high indicator value and a high level of populism.

These scores were subsequently standardized into a “Z” variable, with a distribution characterized by a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, based on all values of a given indicator across all parties worldwide, although this distribution could be different from a perfect Bell distribution. The standardized variables were renamed in the “*GPS_Ind04_Left-Right_Economic_Issues*” format. This operation ensures a similar scale for all indicators, before proceeding with the principal component analysis (PCA), which allocates the respective weight to each indicator into the overall populism assessment. Indeed, each indicator has its own mean and standard deviation in terms of model estimate. Hence, standardization was used to ensure each indicator has a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The standardized indicator value for a party in a given country measures the level of populism of this party in 2019 in terms of standard deviations above (if positive) or below (if negative) the mean populism level of all parties across countries worldwide.

The standardisation (“Z” variable) and the Principal Component Analysis used to construct a composite index based on the above GPS populism expert-assessed indicators are discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.7. Control Variables

In quantitative analysis, it is important to control for relevant variables to reduce the risk of omitted variable bias (OVB), which can occur when a variable that influences the predictor and the outcome variable both is excluded from the estimation model (Stock & Watson, 2015). Failing to account for such confounding variables can lead to biased estimates while undermining the validity of the results. Therefore, so that the results could have unbiased relationships of interest, the regression models in this study control for four control variables:

1. Social media use;
2. Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) index;
3. Gini index (income inequality);
4. Gender;
5. Geo-political region.

3.7.1. Social Media Use Variable from PISA ICT Questionnaire

3.7.1.1. Conceptualisation, Operationalisation, and Rationale for Control

Social media has profoundly reshaped the contemporary political scenario, influencing the spread of ideologies like populism and subsequently influencing various societal aspects, including education and well-being of youth. Therefore it becomes imperative to recognize social media and control it in the regression analyses, particularly when education and well-being are modelled as dependent variables (White, 2024). This is because social media platforms are not just mediums of carrying information, but they actively mediate, amplify and share the reception of political and populist messages. This can directly influence individuals’ cognitive processes, emotional states, and access to diverse perspectives, all of which are important for children’s development and well-being. (Kapoor et al., 2018).

As emphasized by Mudde (2012), populism’s characterisation as an ideology that pits a “virtuous and homogeneous people” against a “corrupt elite” or “dangerous others”, thrives on social divisions and public disillusionment with traditional political systems. This narrative often simplifies complex issues into emotionally charged slogans, posing the risk of discouraged nuanced understanding. This risk is especially heightened and compounded with the inherent algorithm of social media platforms, which often prioritizes sensational and emotionally stimulating content over well sourced information. Populists also seem to target intellectual elites, and they are often portrayed as disconnected from the people. This undermines the

principles of pluralism and critical thinking. In this scenario, the consumption of specific social media content which reflects a specific group's opinion can severely impact an individual's decision making and perspective regarding political leaders and parties.(Ferreira, 2025). Furthermore, social media fosters the environment of "echo chambers" or "ideological silos" where individuals are predominantly exposed to content that aligns with their pre-existing beliefs which further insulates them from opposing perspectives. This selective exposure leads to the reinforcement of opinions and also contributes to radicalisation and a weakened ability for fact based debates.

Thus, social media's significance as a control variable is embedded in its usage and role in amplifying populist narratives and polarisation. White (2024) further explains how social media algorithms amplify provocative, emotionally stimulating and polarizing content, actually facilitating a feedback loop that promotes sensationalism over rational debate. Additionally, as noted by Groshek ja Koc-Michalska (2017) fake news was reported to be intensified with social media platforms during the 2016 U.S presidential elections. This online environment contributes to the spread of misinformation and fake news, especially when such news confirms biases or provokes strong emotions. Another example is also from the studies on the 2016 presidential election in the United States, where false election stories generated more engagement on social media than real content from credible news platforms (Allcott, H., & Gentzkow, M, 2017). All of these examples explain the erosion of factual basis and how it undermines democratic participation and crucially, the very foundations of fact based education.

The growing body of literature and research on social media use has also revealed effects on the mental well-being of young people, highlighting both risks and benefits. While online engagement can provide opportunities for connection and self expression for young people, excessive time spent on digital platforms is associated with lower life satisfaction and reduced happiness among young adults. This duality is echoed in recent research by Faverio et al. (2025), it documents the double edged influence of social media among teenagers in the United States. 48% of surveyed teens in the study reported social media has a negative effect on people their age and 14% reported experiencing them personally. Furthermore, 45% of the teens reported spending "too much time" on social media. The report also mentions heightened levels of anxiety, pressure to maintain online presence and disrupted sleep, all associated with high levels of social media usage. These numbers are especially important to note, as the longitudinal study of this research also demonstrates that the amount of time teenagers spend online has risen sharply over the past decade, and it is increasingly associated with poor psychological well-being Twenge and Campbell (2019). Excessive exposure during the formative years only affects well-being but also naturally shapes how young adults process information, approach learning and especially how they engage with social and political issues, as social media platforms as carriers of populist narratives interact with the increasing digital exposure of young adults. This in turn positions young adults in a particularly vulnerable situation, as the intensity of their social media use when interacting with populist narratives on digital platforms can fetch them into polarized and emotionally charged perspectives. As a result, this can spill over into their education, development and overall well-being.

Therefore, when studying the impact of populism on education and well-being, social media is not just a covariate but a critical control variable. Its interaction with populist narratives means that it acts as a confounding factor while exploring the relationship between the influence of populism on children's well-being and educational outcomes. Hence, controlling for social media can better isolate the direct influence of populist rhetoric, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of how populism impacts educational

achievement and well-being, as without controlling for it, any observed correlations may fail to reflect genuine relationships and pathways between populism and education and well-being in an increasingly digitalised world.

Unfortunately, social media use data was missing for four countries: Argentina (ARG), Indonesia (IDN), Montenegro (MNE), and Romania (ROU). These countries were still selected for this study.

3.7.1.2. Data Harmonisation and Re-Coding Strategy

In this study, the operationalisation of social media use among young adults is constructed by selecting a composite variable based on the responses from the ICT questionnaire included in all eight waves of PISA. The question capturing information on the time spent on online communication platforms has been selected, as it provides the most consistent measure of children's exposure to digital interaction across time. The responses, although differ in wording, aim to capture aspects of digital communication that converges the broad phenomenon of social media use, into a single indicator.

The interpretation of these responses are to be understood in the light of evolution of digital communication. For example, in the early 2000s, the primary use of communication platforms was done through chatrooms or MSN Messenger, on desktop computers, the degree of engagement was also modest compared to current times. The emergence of major social platforms happened in the 2000s (Alhabash & Ma, 2017), such as Facebook (2004), Twitter (2006), Instagram (2010), Snapchat (2011), or Youtube (2005) (Mostafa et al. 2023), as well as the release of Iphone in 2007 (Merchant, 2017) and Android phone in 2008, respectively (Sheikh et al. 2013).

These differences lead to an obvious change in the nature of how the ICT questionnaire captured information on children's social media or digital communication exposure. Keeping this into consideration, items that would allow understanding children's exposure to digital platforms in the early 2000 PISA years were chosen. The frequency responses were coded into a 5-point 0-4 scale, where 0 represents the lowest mark on the exposure to social media, whereas 4 being the highest. Additionally, the ICT familiarity questionnaire in 2015 (OECD,2017) was only administered to students from an optional list of countries, therefore for Argentina, Romania, Indonesia and Montenegro, there are missing values, as no data is available.

3.7.1.3. Social Media Use Value Transformation

The standardisation ("Z" variable) process applied to the social media use indicator is discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.7.2. Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) Index Variable from PISA

3.7.2.1. Conceptualisation, Operationalisation, and Rationale for Control

The Economic, Social and Cultural Status index from PISA is a crucial control variable in our regression analysis, as established through the literature regarding populism's operation through socioeconomic channels. The ESCS index by PISA was created on the basis of the following indicators: International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status (ISEI); the highest level of education of the student's parents, converted into years of schooling; the PISA index of family wealth; the PISA index of home educational resources; and the PISA index of possessions related to "classical" culture in the family home.

It is natural and intuitively understandable that the parents' social, economic and cultural status has an impact on the child's upbringing, attitude and perception. Also revealed by Ritzen and Winkler's (1977) study, where socioeconomic background is positively associated with student achievement. Therefore, adding this multidimensional index can capture interaction of economic resources and social position of a child's family with his/her educational and development outcomes. Furthermore, as discussed in the literature, the influence of populism thrives on societal divides, therefore it can be understood that the influence of the populist narrative will vary from one family to another. Therefore, controlling for ESCS helps isolate the underlying socioeconomic stratification that may confound the relationship between populism, education and well-being.

3.7.2.2. Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) Index Value Transformation

The standardisation ("Z" variable) process applied to the Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) index is discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.7.3. The Gini Index Variable

3.7.3.1. General Introduction to the Gini Index

Named after Corrado Gini, the Italian statistician, the Gini Index (World Bank, 2014) assesses the level of inequality. More specifically, it "measures the extent to which the distribution of income (or, in some cases, consumption expenditure) among individuals or households within an economy deviates from a perfectly equal distribution. A Lorenz curve plots the cumulative percentages of total income received against the cumulative number of recipients, starting with the poorest individual or household. The Gini index measures the area between the Lorenz curve and a hypothetical line of absolute equality". It is expressed as a percentage of the maximum area under the line. Hence, a Gini Index of 0 represents a perfect equality, while a value of 100 measures a perfect inequality. The Gini Index values are available for a given country in a given year.

Unfortunately, due to the unavailability of Gini Index values for Hong Kong (HKG), New Zealand (NZL), and Taiwan (TWN), these three countries were discarded from the present study.

3.7.3.2. Gini Index Transformation

The Gini Index values were standardized into a “Z” variable, with a distribution characterized by a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, based on all values across all selected countries, although this distribution could be different from a perfect Bell distribution. The standardized variables were renamed in the “z_Giniindex” format. This operation ensures a similar scale for the Gini Index scores and the other variables in the present study (V-Party populism values, GPS populism values, etc.). The standardized Gini Index value measures the level of inequality in the given country and year, in terms of standard deviations above (if positive) or below (if negative) the mean inequality level of all countries over time.

The standardisation (“Z” variable) process applied to the Gini index is further discussed in the Empirical Strategy section below.

3.7.4. Gender Variable

Gender was used as a control variable in the cross-sectional regression analyses. Global and worldwide descriptive summaries for the gender variable are provided below. Gender was very much balanced in all years, with a maximum difference of 1.22 % between groups (in 2009 - more girls (50.61%) than boys (49.39 %)).

Table 7

Global Gender Variable Values (Aggregate Values for All Selected Countries and all Years)

All PISA Edition Years

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	2,550,344.00	50.26	50.26
Male	2,524,208.00	49.74	100.00
Total	5,074,552.00	100.00	

Table 8*Worldwide Gender Variable Trends Over Time (Aggregate Values For All Selected Countries)***Year 2000 (V-Party)**

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	59,002.00	50.60	50.60
Male	57,592.00	49.40	100.00
Total	116,594.00	100.00	

Year 2003 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	262,690.00	50.44	50.44
Male	258,098.00	49.56	100.00
Total	520,788.00	100.00	

Year 2006 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	349,898.00	50.41	50.41
Male	344,156.00	49.59	100.00
Total	694,054.00	100.00	

Year 2009 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	395,286.00	50.61	50.61
Male	385,768.00	49.39	100.00
Total	781,054.00	100.00	

Year 2012 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	391,352.00	50.44	50.44
Male	384,472.00	49.56	100.00
Total	775,824.00	100.00	

Year 2015 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	341,832.00	50.20	50.20
Male	339,098.00	49.80	100.00
Total	680,930.00	100.00	

Year 2018 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	379,732.00	49.99	49.99
Male	379,860.00	50.01	100.00
Total	759,592.00	100.00	

Year 2019 (GPS)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	379,732.00	49.99	49.99
Male	379,860.00	50.01	100.00
Total	759,592.00	100.00	

Year 2022 (V-Party)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulated Percentage
Female	370,552.00	49.69	49.69
Male	375,164.00	50.31	100.00
Total	745,716.00	100.00	

No standardisation (“Z” variable) was needed for the gender control variable.

3.7.5. Geo-Political Region Variable from the V-Party Study

Geo-Political region was used as a control variable in the cross-sectional regression analyses. The values for this variable are as follows:

1. Eastern Europe and Central Asia;
2. Latin America and the Caribbean;
3. The Middle East and North Africa (including Israel and Türkiye);
4. Sub-Saharan Africa (no selected country for the present study belongs to this category);
5. Western Europe and North America (including Australia);
6. Asia and Pacific (excluding Australia - see 5).

No standardisation (“Z” variable) was needed for the geo-political region control variable.

3.8. Final Dataset

As explained above, after the construction each variable in the dataset, the eight years of PISA were re-coded, harmonised, cleaned and then 8 years of PISA years were appended to create a longitudinal panel structure, these longitudinal values were then merged on a country year level with party Populism data, GPS populism data and Gini index. The dataset was then used as 8 waves of cross-section for OLS regression models where education and well-being were regressed on populism followed by controls, eight

times for each year, furthermore the dataset was later collapsed for all key variables on country year averages to establish consistency for running fixed effects panel multivariate regressions. Table 000 below summaries the statistics of all variables.

For panel analysis purposes, except for the GPS data, the dataset was enriched with linearly intrapolated values for all years between two subsequent PISA editions years between 2000 and 2022. Intrapolated values were computed for the following years: 2001; 2002; 2004; 2005; 2007; 2008; 2010; 2011; 2013; 2014; 2016; 2017; 2019; 2020; and 2021. Hence, the consolidated dataset, after these interpolation operations, consists of 23 yearly sets of values. All analyses using the intrapolated values are based on the hypothesis that these values reflect a smoothly changing situation year by year that could have been observed in case election process and assessment had been conducted on a yearly basis. The related variable names in STATA include an “_i” extension to differentiate them from original variables and values. This aspect will be kept in mind while analysing the results of any test using such values and reminded in the discussion.

4. EMPIRICAL STRATEGY

4.1. Principal Component Analysis

Three composite indices have been created for this study that was later used in the regression analysis. The construction of these indices have been done by employing Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a widely used technique to reduce dimensionality and index construction. PCA is a multivariate method that transfers a set of possibly correlated variables into a smaller set of uncorrelated variables known as principal components (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016).

Furthermore, PCA can be used for weight computation for principal components which enables robust index construction. Particularly, it is useful in the context where research is aimed to synthesize information from multiple indicators into a single index, while minimizing the redundancy and measurement errors (Abdi & Williams, 2010). This makes the method highly appropriate for producing indexes of constructs such as populism and well-being which are inherently multidimensional. Therefore, usage of PCA is primarily helpful in dimensionality reduction and elimination of multicollinearity, as PCA generates orthogonal components, thereby mitigating the risks of multicollinearity (Hotelling, 1933). Lastly, for empirical transparency, by generating weights based on variance maximisation. It ensures that the final index reflects the true data structure rather than researcher imposed arbitrary weights. As explained by Vyas & Kumaranayake (2006), each component as expressed below, is a linearly weight combination of the former variables. In the equation expressed below, where a_{mn} = weight for the m th principal component and the n th variable.

$$\begin{aligned} PC_1 &= a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + \dots + a_{1n}X_n \\ &\vdots \\ PC_m &= a_{m1}X_1 + a_{m2}X_2 + \dots + a_{mn}X_n \end{aligned}$$

Implementation in this study

PCA was performed separately for three sets of variables in this thesis;

- V-Party Populism Index (VPoPI)
- GPS Populism Index (GPSPoPI)
- PISA Student well-being Index (wBI)

The following steps have been performed in order to reach the final index;

1. Z- score standardisation: The initial processing of data involves performing a z-score standardisation on all indicators used in PCA, to ensure that all indicators are on the same scale, which helps in mitigating the risk of having one indicator weighing stronger than the other (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016). This standardization enables a smoother comparison between indicators, resulting in a mean equal to 0 and standard deviation of 1.

Where;

X = Raw Value

\bar{X} = Sample Mean

S = Standard Deviation

$$Z = \frac{X - \bar{X}}{s}$$

2. Intercorrelation and examining the indicators before PCA

The selected indicators for Populism; from GPS and V-PARTY and PISA student well-being have been stated in detail in the previous section followed by the justification of this choice.

Prior to the implementation of PCA, it is important to make sure that the chosen indicators do exhibit a degree of multicollinearity and intercorrelation, this ensures that the indicators are indeed fit to proceed for the next steps. Two methods have been used; a) to ensure the intercorrelation between the indicators, Bartlett's test of sphericity and b) Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure to determine the sampling adequacy of indicators, as this approach measures the homogeneity of variables (Kaiser, 1974).

- a) Barlett's test examines whether the correlation matrix of the selected indicators significantly differs from the identity matrix; it would mean that the indicators are not correlated and thus not suitable for dimension reduction. A statistically significant test result with a p-value < 0.05 helps signify that sufficient correlations exist among the indicators which is a prerequisite for proceeding with the implementation of PCA (Williams et al., 2010). The p-value for all the observed indicators of V-Party, GPS and PISA student well-being comes out to be 0.000.
- b) Kaiser - Meyer - Olkin (KMO) statistics assess whether the partial correlations among the indicators are small relative to the total correlations, meaning it helps confirm that the correlations are compact enough to generate reliable factors. The measure takes a value between 0 and 1. A higher KMO value indicates that the data is suitable for PCA (Kaiser, 1974). Table 9 below outlines the different measures. The KMO value for V Party Populism indicators is 0.800, for GPS it is 0.837, and for well-being indicators is 0.802 . According to Kaiser (1974) these are 'meritorious' and suitable for the usage of PCA.

Table 9

Kaier-Meyer-Olkin Measure

0.00 to 0.49	unacceptable
0.50 to 0.59	miserable
0.60 to 0.69	mediocre
0.70 to 0.79	middling
0.80 to 0.89	meritorious
0.90 to 1.00	marvellous

Principal Components Retention

After running the PCA, Kaiser-Guttman criterion is used to extract principal components, this is done by retaining factors with an eigenvalue greater than 1, as factors with an eigenvalue less than 1 contribute to less variance than a single indicator, therefore deemed insignificant and dropped (James et al, 2013). The Table 10 below shows the retained principal components, followed by a visual representation on Figure 6; as there are four factors for GPS and V-Party each and two factors PISA, all of which have an eigenvalue greater than 1.

Table 10

Retained Principal Components for well-being Indicators

Principal Component	Eigenvalue
PC1	4.36506
PC2	2.69774

Figure 6

Scree Plot of Eigenvalues after Factor

Table 11

Retained Principal Components for V Party Populism Index

Principal Component	Eigenvalue
PC1	5.73207
PC2	1.6928
PC3	1.11789
PC4	1.04339

Figure 7

Scree Plot of Eigenvalues after Factor

Table 11

Retained Principal Components for GPS Populism Index

Principal Component	Eigenvalue
PC1	6.5107
PC2	2.02367
PC3	1.33997
PC4	1.00832

Figure 8

Scree Plot of Eigenvalues after Factor

Rotation of Factor Matrix

Factor rotation is done for improving the interpretability of the factor structure, as agreed by most researchers. After retaining components with eigenvalue greater than 1, Varimax rotation (a form of orthogonal rotation with Kaiser normalization), makes the factor loadings simplified by maximizing the variance of squared loading within each factor. Rotation redistributes the variance across factors and produces simpler clusters of indicators. (Hair et al., 2018).

Generating a weighted Index for Populism (V Party and GPS) and well-being

The construction of the well-being Index (wbl), V-Party Populism Index (VPoPI) and GPS Populism Index (GPSPoPI) was generated by computing the proportion of variance explained by the observed principal components and the predicted factor loadings. Equation 1, 2 and 3 explain how this method was carried out.

(1) Well-being Index **wbl = 0.4112×F1+0.2951×F2**

(2) V Party Populism Index **VPoPI = 0.2546×F1 + 0.1770×F2 + 0.1742×F3 + 0.1316×F4**

(3) GPS Populism Index **GPSPoPI = 0.2804×F1 + 0.2694×F2 + 0.1306×F3 + 0.0907×F4**

4.2. Cross sectional data and Panel Data Analysis

The empirical framework of this study required careful consideration of choosing the right models for studying the relationship between key variables, while considering the multilevel structure inherent in the merged dataset. The PISA dataset that captures variables on educational outcomes, well-being index, social media use and ESCS index fundamentally comprises student level observations, all of which vary across country year dimensions (e.g., across 49 countries across 8 years of PISA waves) Each PISA wave captures

individual student performance within specific countries during each assessment cycles, which creates a natural hierarchical data structure where student-level observations are nested within country year contexts. After the recording and harmonisation of key variables, the 8 PISA waves were appended into one PISA dataset, but this does not imply a longitudinal dataset, as the students observed across the PISA waves are not the same students. The complexity of the data structure is amplified when PISA student-level data is merged with country-year level variables such as populism (V-Party), populism (GPS) and macroeconomic control - Gini index. This integration created a hierarchical data structure, where individual level dependent variables (educational outcomes) are analysed in relation to both individual level features and country-year level institutional and economic factors. This data structure has profound implications for econometric methodology. The absence of consistent individual tracking across PISA waves eliminates the possibility of using the within individual variation over time, which is the foundation of traditional panel data estimation methodology. Therefore, using PISA appended waves as a standard longitudinal panel would violate the assumptions about data structure that underpins fixed and random effects estimates.

The Moulton Problem

Moulton (1990) confronted a fundamental econometric challenge in his seminal work on estimating the effects of aggregate variables on micro units. He throws light on economic research work where researchers have attempted to measure the effect of aggregate or public policy variables on micro units, and then using multiple regress or similar statistics to measure the effect of aggregate variables on micro units. However, the assumptions with these methods are usually based on independent disturbances, which is not suitable for data populations for grouped structures.

My research context presents the same challenge, as student-level PISA outcomes (micro level) would be analysed in relation to country level populism measures. This creates a data structure that Moulton warns against. In the words of Moulton (1990) “incorrectly using ordinary least square can lead to standard errors that are seriously biased downward” and “the danger of spurious regression from this kind of misspecification”.

Therefore, standard regression methods applied to my mixed-level data structure would underestimate standard errors and lead to inflated significance levels and spurious conclusions. This very problem has been documented in econometric literature, particularly the lack of reliability of estimation methods applied on hierarchical or mixed level data structures (Bryan & Jenkins, 2015.)

Given these constraints, the analysis is done by adopting a dual strategy approach that address the challenge of handling multi level data

Ordinary Least Square Regression Model for Cross Sectional Analysis by Year

The first approach treats each year as a separate cross sectional analysis, while conducting eight regressions across the eight PISA waves: 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018 and 2022. This method effectively addresses the panel data complications arising from inconsistent observed individuals in time.

Country Fixed Effects Model for Panel Data

The second approach addresses the mixed level challenge through an aggregation technique, as student level variables are collapsed into the means of country-year level, which creates a balanced panel data of 49 countries observed over 8 years (N=982). Doing so, results in a genuine country year level panel, where both predictor and outcome variable, as well as the controls operate on the country-year average level.

To examine the correlation of populism with educational outcomes and well-being over time, country fixed effects (FE) model has been used in this study. As fixed effects models are particularly appropriate and suited for panel data where observations are embedded within both time and country (Stock & Watson, 2015). This method accounts for unobserved heterogeneity, which is constant across time but varies between units (countries), as well as shocks or impacts that are constant across countries but differ across time (Baltagi, 2008). The inclusion of country fixed effects controls for unobserved, time-invariant heterogeneity across countries, such as cultural, institutional, or structural differences that may otherwise bias the estimates.

The models are specified as follows, whereas the justification, processing and construction of the dependent, explanatory and control variables has been carried out in the previous section.

Following equations are used, where:

‘i’ denotes country,

‘t’ denotes time,

μ_i = country fixed effects

ϵ_{it} = error term

Model 1 :

$$\text{Educational Outcome}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Populism Index}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{Wellbeing Index}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{ESCS Index}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{GINI Index}_{it} + \alpha_5 \text{Social Media}_{it} + \mu_i + \epsilon_{it}$$

Model 2 :

$$\text{Wellbeing Index}_{it} = c_0 + \beta_1 \text{Populism Index}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Educational Outcome}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ESCS Index}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{GINI Index}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Social Media}_{it} + \mu_i + \epsilon_{it}$$

In this Framework, α is the intercept, β_1 is of prime interest, as it quantifies the correlation of populism on the outcome variable (educational outcome and well-being) after controlling for both observed control variables and unobserved time invariant country specific factors, and ϵ is error term.

As a further robustness check, the models are tested by replacing the V Party Populism Index with GPS Populism Index. This analysis is cross sectional in nature and done for assessing the correlation of populism with well-being and education in 2022, as GPS is only available for 2019.

4.3. Baron and Kenny Mediation Analysis

A mediator variable helps understand the ‘‘how’’ and ‘‘why’’ of the relationship between a predictor variable and a criterion variable.(Moran, 2025) In our hypothesis, well-being has been hypothesized to mediate the relationship between populism and educational outcomes, as populism can influence the well-being of children which ultimately affects their educational achievement, as explained in the previous section.

Figure 8 bis

Well-being as a Mediator of the Relationship between Populism and Educational Outcome

Therefore, to examine this mediating role, mediation analysis by Baron and Kenny (1986) is used. This approach has been used by researchers to test the mechanism through which independent variables affect dependent variables. As represented on Figure 8 bis above, where the mediation is analysed through paths a, b, and c.

The four step approach to mediation analysis

To begin with, it is important to establish that mediation analysis, like regression analysis does not imply causation, however can help understand the correlational relationship between variables. The Baron and Kenny method involves testing mediation through a series of three regressions, followed by using either Sobel test or bootstrapping for significance testing.

$$Y = \text{Educational Outcome}; X = \text{Populism}; M = \text{well-being}$$

1. In the first step we regress the educational outcome on populism. Although this step is suggested by Baron and Kenny (1986), this step is also criticized and suggested to be skipped by some researchers Hayes (2009). In this step, we try to understand whether there is a significant relationship between the X and Y. Moreover, social media, Gini Index and ESCS index have been added as controls for reliable estimates.

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X + e$$

2. The second step involves regressing well-being on populism, as the mediation only makes sense if the independent variable affects the mediator.

$$M = b_0 + b_2X + e$$

3. In this step, we try to understand whether the coefficient of populism is non-significant or smaller. For mediation to exist, the effect of populism on educational outcomes will either disappear or weaken due to the introduction of the mediator variable, as the effect of populism on educational outcomes is supposed to be mediated through well-being.

$$Y = b_0 + b_4X + b_3M + e$$

In case the effect of populism on educational outcomes completely disappears, the mediator - well-being fully mediates the effect of populism on well-being. Whereas, if the effect of populism is smaller in magnitude as compared to step 2, well-being partially mediates the relationship between populism and educational outcomes.

4. The final step involves testing whether the mediation effect is statistically significant; this can be done by two approaches, the Sobel test or Bootstrapping (Preacher & Hayes, 2009). In this study, bootstrapping method is employed because it is strongly recommended in recent years (Lee et al.,2021)

It involves a resampling approach where observations are repeatedly computed with replacement from the dataset to estimate the sampling distribution of a statistic. By generating hundreds of such resamples, researchers can get approximations of indirect effects in mediation analysis. The Preacher–Hayes (2009) approach applies this method to derive point estimates and confidence intervals for mediation effects. Importantly, when the bootstrap confidence interval does not include zero, the mediation effect can be considered statistically significant. Therefore, I implemented bootstrapping with 200 resamples, which produced a 95% confidence interval for the indirect effects (a*b) that excluded zero for the robustness of the mediation effect.

4.4. Instrumental Variable Regression

Instrumental variable (IV) regression is used as an additional robustness measure to assess whether well-being mediates the relation between populism and well-being. This approach is a complement to the Baron and Kenny mediation analysis carried out cross sectionally across eight years: 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018 and 2022. IV regression provides an alternative identification strategy that addresses potential endogeneity concerns that could bias the mediation results.

Rationale for IV Regression

The complex relationship between populism, well-being and educational outcomes present endogeneity concerns that require instrumental variable estimation. The relationship between these key variables could suffer from multiple sources of endogeneity bias; while populism is hypothesized to influence educational outcomes through well-being, this influential relationship is potentially bidirectional or can suffer from simultaneous causality. Populism can influence children's well-being directly, while also influencing educational outcome through multiple ways such as, national curricula policy reforms, impact on parental attitudes, social behaviour and broader political environment effects. This makes it difficult to isolate the mediation effect of well-being in a standard regression framework. Conversely, children's well-being can be significantly impacted by their educational experiences and achievement, creating a simultaneity problem. Furthermore, omitted variable bias can occur with unobserved factors such as cultural values, interpersonal relationships of children with their family or friends, historical events and socioeconomic conditions which may simultaneously affect populism, well-being and educational outcomes.

Thus, to address these endogeneity concerns, well-being is treated as an endogenous variable and populism is introduced as an instrument to isolate the exogenous variation in well-being. This approach, although exploratory in nature, can help understand the true causal effect of well-being on educational outcomes purged of simultaneity and endogeneity bias.

Instrument Validity Requirements

The validity of populism as an instrument must satisfy the following two conditions:

5. Relevance: Populism must be significantly correlated with well-being (testable through first stage F-statistic)
6. Exclusion Restriction: Populism must not directly influence the error term of educational outcome. Although not directly testable, this step uses theoretical assumptions as populism doesn't directly influence the educational performance of children. Its main impact is on social trust, cohesion, and household security, which in turn can shape children's well-being (Nowakowski, A, 2021). Moreover, the inclusion of country fixed effects controls for institutional or policy differences across education systems, while the slow-moving nature of educational attainment relative to political cycles further supports the claim that short-run populist dynamics cannot directly shift test outcomes. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that populism affects education exclusively through the well-being channel, satisfying the exclusion restriction.

Two Stage Least Square Estimation 2SLS

The 2SLS approach involves two sequential regression stages:

1. First Stage: this estimates the relationship between the endogenous variable (well-being) and instrument (populism).

$$\text{Wellbeing Index}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Populism Index}_{it} + \alpha_2 \text{ESCS Index}_{it} + \alpha_3 \text{GINI Index}_{it} + \alpha_4 \text{SocialMedia}_{it} + \gamma_i + \epsilon_{1it}$$

(Where, i is for Country, t is for Time, γ_i = country fixed effects and ϵ_{1it} = first-stage error term)

From this stage, we obtain the predicted value for well-being.

2. Second Stage: The second stage regresses the outcome variable (educational outcomes) on the predicted values of well-being from the first stage, along with the same set of exogenous controls.

$$\text{Educational Outcome}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \hat{\text{Wellbeing Index}}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{ESCS Index}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{GINI Index}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{SocialMedia}_{it} + \gamma_i + \epsilon_{2it}$$

(Where, i is for Country, t is for Time, γ_i = country fixed effects and ϵ_{2it} = second-stage error term)

The coefficient β_1 represents the local average treatment effect of well-being on educational outcomes, through the instrumental variables approach.

Key Identification Assumption: we preserve the variations in well-being that we are interested in, by using predicted well-being from the first stage (relevance condition). Because populism explains the variations in well-being, the predicted well-being is as good as actual well-being in “explaining” educational outcomes in the second stage. Since populism is uncorrelated with the second stage error term (exclusion restriction), populism contains no information about educational outcomes beyond its effect through well-being. When we predict well-being using populism, the predicted well-being also contains no information about educational outcomes or the error term, this assumption is utilised in accounting for no endogeneity.

The identification strategy also relies on the assumption that populism creates exogenous shocks to societal well-being that are not directly correlated with educational outcomes through channels other than well-

being. This assumption is theoretically grounded in the literature suggesting that populism primarily affects children's well-being, which subsequently affects their educational outcomes.

5. RESULTS

5.4. Descriptive Statistical Summary

Results are divided into two sections. This first section contains descriptive statistical summaries of the 7 standardized (“Z” scores) variables used in this study, excluding gender (described above), in the form of either tables or figures, whether graphs, rankings, maps, or heatmaps, together with short observations about the main trends. This comprehensive variable overview is structured on six levels:

- (1) A global level, displaying aggregate values for each variable for all selected countries and all PISA edition years;
- (2) A worldwide level over time, displaying aggregate values for each variable for all selected countries;
- (3) A national level over time, displaying values for all variables per country over time;
- (4) A single-variable level for detailed descriptions (one variable at a time);
- (5) An individual level for inter-variable correlation analysis (by pair of variable);
- (6) A national level for populism inter-variable (V-Party and GPS) correlation analysis.

The second section contains the statistical results of the models testing the hypotheses.

5.4.1. Global Variable Values (Main Variables) (Aggregate Values for All Selected Countries And all PISA Edition Years)

For each variable, except gender (shortly analysed in the data section above), Table 12 showcases the global number of observations, minimum and maximum values, all aggregated for all selected countries and all PISA edition years. Since their standardisation (“Z” variables) was operated on that basis (aggregation), the means are equal to 0 and the standard deviations to 1. It also implies that the variables are measured in terms of “relative” values between all selected countries over time, measured in standard deviations from the mean. In a given country and year, a variable value of +1 (-1) indicates a level of one deviation above (below) the all-countries-all-years variable mean value. For well-being, V-Party populism, and GPS populism variables, the values are PCA-based. GPS values are available for 2019 only.

Table 12

Global Main Variable Values (Aggregate Values for all Selected Countries and all Years)

Summary statistics overall: N - Mean - Standard Deviation - Minimum - Maximum		All observations - All years				
Variable (label)	STATA Name	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index	wbi	5,077,231	0.000	1.000	-5.912	6.617
Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value	PV avg edu	4,994,091	0.000	1.000	-4.662	3.774
Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index	VPoPI	5,077,231	0.000	1.000	-1.603	3.281
Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index	GPSPoPI	49	0.000	1.000	-2.334	1.892
Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with intrapolation if required)	z social media i	4,774,420	0.000	1.000	-4.340	3.269
Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with intrapolation if required)	z ESCS i	5,077,231	0.000	1.000	-3.028	1.890
Standardized ("Z") Gini Index	z Giniindex	5,077,231	0.000	1.000	-1.664	3.363

5.4.2. Worldwide Variable Trends Over Time (Main Variables) (Aggregate Values for all Selected Countries)

Figure 9 and Table 13 below provide the same information, but considering each PISA edition and GPS years separately. Therefore, the means and standard deviations can be different from 0 and 1, respectively.

Figure 9

Worldwide Variable Trends over Time (Main Variables)

The variation of the average standardized value for each main variable over time is shown on Figure 9 below. While well-being shows the most intense variation in time along a steep low-high-low change curve, populism is constantly and smoothly increasing over time, except a slight drop in the mid-2000's, while education outcome is following a reverse trend. ESCS index values are following a discrete high-low-high path, to the contrary of the Gini index value (low-high-low profile). Social media use first increases much from a very low value (technology was still recent then), then slower and slower along a tangent, and the mean GPS populism value, available for 2019 only, is equal to 0 by mathematical construct (standardized value).

Table 13

Worldwide Variables Over Time (Main Variables)

Summary statistics by year: N - Mean - Standard Deviation - Minimum - Maximum		Summary statistics for year 2000						Summary statistics for year 2003					Summary statistics for year 2006				
Variable (label)	STATA Name	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	
Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index (with interpolation if required)	wbl	117,512	-0.403	0.880	-5.912	6.617	522,391	-0.087	0.823	-4.332	5.341	694,058	0.247	0.977	-2.753	4.065	
Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value	PV avg edu	117,501	0.073	1.075	-4.429	3.295	522,378	0.089	0.980	-4.062	3.313	682,834	0.007	0.980	-4.662	3.774	
Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index	VPoPI	117,512	-0.223	0.861	-1.588	2.850	522,391	-0.077	0.932	-1.588	2.850	694,058	-0.032	0.968	-1.603	2.870	
Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index	GPSPoPI	0	0	0	
Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with interpolation if required)	z social media i	111,191	-1.375	1.228	-4.340	3.269	500,866	-0.712	1.129	-3.335	2.659	644,940	-0.144	1.066	-2.832	2.049	
Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with interpolation if required)	z ESCS i	117,512	0.188	0.980	-2.468	1.890	522,391	0.045	0.989	-2.342	1.681	694,058	0.038	0.930	-2.390	1.843	
Standardized ("Z") Gini Index	z Giniindex	117,512	-0.060	1.083	-1.664	3.363	522,391	0.006	1.098	-1.448	3.205	694,058	0.061	1.049	-1.578	2.916	

Summary statistics by year: N - Mean - Standard Deviation - Minimum - Maximum		Summary statistics for year 2009						Summary statistics for year 2012					Summary statistics for year 2015				
Variable (label)	STATA Name	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	
Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index (with interpolation if required)	wbl	781,058	0.459	0.762	-1.561	2.789	775,824	0.805	0.722	-0.867	2.292	680,932	-0.417	0.836	-2.404	2.299	
Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value	PV avg edu	781,058	-0.010	0.958	-4.381	3.554	775,824	0.015	0.962	-4.221	3.465	680,930	0.004	0.949	-3.684	3.251	
Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index	VPoPI	781,058	-0.029	0.947	-1.603	2.870	775,824	0.013	0.937	-1.584	2.732	680,932	-0.073	0.988	-1.585	2.732	
Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index	GPSPoPI	0	0	0	
Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with interpolation if required)	z social media i	781,058	0.075	0.840	-2.730	1.439	733,128	0.127	0.743	-2.284	1.105	646,823	0.174	0.685	-1.875	1.164	
Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with interpolation if required)	z ESCS i	781,058	-0.124	1.073	-2.528	1.733	775,824	-0.087	1.061	-2.991	1.859	680,932	-0.012	1.026	-3.028	1.783	
Standardized ("Z") Gini Index	z Giniindex	781,058	0.151	1.096	-1.520	2.643	775,824	0.156	1.052	-1.405	2.600	680,932	-0.013	0.958	-1.434	2.383	

Summary statistics by year: N - Mean - Standard Deviation - Minimum - Maximum		Summary statistics for year 2018						Summary statistics for year 2019					Summary statistics for year 2022				
Variable (label)	STATA Name	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	
Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index (with interpolation if required)	wbl	759,597	-0.609	1.000	-2.712	2.306	0	745,859	-0.422	0.906	-3.893	1.095	
Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value	PV avg edu	687,710	0.007	0.957	-3.448	3.426	0	745,856	-0.106	0.962	-3.637	3.662	
Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index	VPoPI	759,597	0.026	1.080	-1.585	3.281	0	745,859	0.175	1.108	-1.542	3.153	
Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index	GPSPoPI	0	49	0.000	1.000	-2.334	1.892	0	
Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with interpolation if required)	z social media i	687,969	0.257	0.703	-1.444	1.265	0	668,445	0.241	1.246	-3.778	2.104	
Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with interpolation if required)	z ESCS i	759,597	0.045	0.945	-2.228	1.403	0	745,859	0.089	0.937	-2.377	1.372	
Standardized ("Z") Gini Index	z Giniindex	759,597	-0.112	0.841	-1.549	2.672	0	745,859	-0.246	0.814	-1.621	2.398	

Note: the GPS study began in November 2019, between the PISA editions of 2018 and 2022. The GPS data is only available for 2019, whereas the other datasets relate to 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, and 2022.

5.4.3. Variable Trends per Country over Time (Main Variables)

The four following figures illustrate the variable trends over time on a national level (except for gender). Countries are ranked in a descending populism level order, based on the average populism level between the GPS values (collected in late 2019, valid during 2020) and the interpolated values for 2020 from the updated V-Party dataset.

Figure 10

All Variables Trends 49 Countries (Main Variables) - Part I

Figure 11

All Variables Trends 49 Countries (Main Variables) - Part II

Figure 12

All Variables Trends 49 Countries (Main Variables) - Part III

Figure 13

All Variables Trends 49 Countries (Main Variables) - Part IV

The national variable values over time in the 49 selected countries have various profiles that will be analysed in the following main result section, revealing complex relations either in cross-sectional approaches with mediation analyses, panel analyses, or IV regression tests.

5.4.4. Single-variable Detailed Description (Main Variables)

5.4.4.1. Well-being Variable (Standardized Scores)

Figure 14

Well-Being Country Ranking 2020 (Intrapolated Values)

Figure 15

Worldwide Well-Being Trend over Time (highlighted)

Well-being values across time, intrapolated in some cases for countries that took part to 6 or 7 out of 8 PISA editions, show an overall increase from 2000 to 2012, followed by a decrease till 2018 and a slight increase again to reach a similar level as in 2000. Nevertheless, this variation depends much on the country as shown below in Figure 16. A few distinctive profiles are noticeable.

In 2000, well-being in Lithuania (LTU) was the highest ($wbI = 6.617$), then fell to eventually reach a level of more than one standard deviation below the worldwide average value 22 years later. Montenegro (MNE) and Serbia (SRB) have similar profiles, although their startpoint values are respectively a bit more and a bit less than 4 standard deviations above the overall mean. Whereas Romania (ROU) started with the lowest level of well-being ($wbI = -5.912$), which increased to a value of 0.5 in 2012, before decreasing to almost -1 in 2022. In Russia (RUS), the main feature is the collapse from a value slightly above 0 in 2012 to a level of -3.893 in 2022, the lowest score worldwide that year. Finally the case of Albania (ALB) is atypical as well: from about -0.5 in 2000, the well-being index value increased to almost 2.5, which remained constant on that level till 2018, whereas a massive decrease happened worldwide in the same time period, before Tirana saw the national well-being level drop of more than one unit in the following four years.

The situation in 2020, illustrated in Figure 16, is concerning as most countries have a well-being level below the overall average level between 2000 and 2022. Only 11 countries out of 49 (22.45%) see their youth feeling better at school than the 2000-2022 average level and one country only, namely Albania (ALB), has a value above 1.

Figure 16

Heat Map of Well-Being over Time (Intrapolated Standardized Values)

Figure 17

Map of Well-Being Intrapolated Standardised Values by Country in 2020

5.4.4.2. Educational Outcome Variable (Standardized Scores)

Figure 18

Educational Outcome Country Ranking 2020 (Intrapolated Values)

Table 19

Worldwide Educational Outcome Trend over Time (highlighted)

Figure 20

Heat Map of Educational Outcome over Time (Intrapolated Standardized Values)

Figure 21

Map of Educational Outcome Intrapolated Standardised Values by Country in 2020

With a global decrease tendency worldwide over time, educational outcome values tended to become more homogeneous during the time period 2000-2022. In 2020, most countries (34 out of 46 with data - 73.91%) were in the interval of half a standard deviation around the global mean of 0, showing a weak variation then, whereas two decades earlier, countries like the Netherlands (NLD) and Japan (JPN) stood out with higher values and Peru (PER), Brazil (BRA), Indonesia (IDN) or Albania (ALB) with lower values. The latter two countries are still low-value outsiders in 2022.

5.4.4.3. Populism Variable (Standardized Scores)

Figure 22

Populism Country Ranking 2020 (Intrapolated Values)

Figure 23

Worldwide Populism Trend over Time (highlighted)

Figure 24

Heat Map of Populism over Time (Intrapolated Standardised Values)

The V-Party estimates of populism show a global increase trend across the world over time, some countries like Luxembourg (LUX), Norway (NOR), Sweden (SWE) or Uruguay (URY) have stable low values. The highest populism levels are observed in Tunisia (TUN) in early 2000's and since 2012 in Türkiye (TUR), Hungary (HUN), and Serbia (SRB).

5.4.4.4. Social Media Use Variable (Standardized Scores)

Figure 25

Social Media Use Country Ranking 2020 (Intrapolated Values)

Figure 26

Worldwide Social Media Use Trend over Time (highlighted)

Social media use has increased a lot in the first two decades of the 21st century, along with the information technology revolution. In 2020, the standard deviation between countries was equal to 0.9745, with only Iceland (ISL) and Finland (FIN) being twice as much away from the global mean (lower values).

5.4.4.5. Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) index Variable (Standardized Scores)

The ESCS values follow an overall high-low-high trend from 2000 to 2022. It is noticeable that the 4 top countries are Nordic nations, while the bottom 8 lands are located around the equator, but Türkiye (TUR). Iceland (ISL) and Norway (NOR) show constant higher values than other countries and Türkiye (TUR), Peru (PER), and Indonesia (IDN) the lowest ones overall.

Figure 27

Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) Index Country Ranking 2020 (Intrapolated Values)

Figure 28

Worldwide Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) Index Trend over Time (highlighted)

Figure 29

Heat Map of Economic, Social and Cultural Status (ESCS) Index over Time (Intrapolated Standardized Values)

5.4.4.6. Gini index Variable (Standardized Scores)

The Gini Index values measuring outcome inequality follow an overall low-high-low trend from 2000 to 2022. Only Brazil is a clear outsider in 2020 (value of 2.53) and in the previous two decades. Slovenia (SVN), Slovakia (SVK), and Czechia (CZE) show the most stable high levels of outcome equality over time.

Figure 30

Gini Index Country Ranking 2020 (Intrapolated Values)

Figure 31

Worldwide Gini Index Trend over Time (highlighted)

Figure 33

Heat Map of Gini Index over Time (Intrapolated Standardized Values)

5.4.5. Individual level - Inter-Variable Correlation Analysis (Main Variables)

The pair case correlations between the main 6 variables are displayed in the following couple of tables. The values in Table 14 are based upon the observations collected in each of the 8 PISA edition years, whereas the correlation shown in Table 15 are computed with the 23 yearly datasets including the intrapolated values in years standing between any two subsequent PISA edition years, which covers the period 2000-2022. The second series of correctional values is based on the assumption that a linear change in the standardised (“Z” variable) values of each of the main 6 variables is reasonable to consider. Although hypothetical, it is interesting to note the differences between both outcomes (objective data only versus objective and intrapolated data together).

These correlations are not to be confused with causal relationships. Moreover, they are to be considered with great caution as they are calculated for variable pairs only, meaning without any control variables. Nevertheless, directions and values are worth to be noticed as first indications, as well as differences between both correlational matrices.

First, populism is individually negatively correlated with well-being (low values), educational outcome (low versus moderate values), economic, social and cultural status (moderate values), income equality (negative correlation with income inequality) (moderate values), and social media use (moderate values), in both tables.

Second, a higher well-being is individually correlated with a lower populism (low values), a lower educational outcome (low versus moderate values), a lower economic, social and cultural status (low values), a lower outcome equality (a higher outcome inequality) (moderate versus low values), and very weak positive versus negative correlations are observed with social media use.

Third, a better educational outcome is individually associated with less populism (low versus moderate values), less well-being (low versus moderate values), a higher economic, social and cultural status (moderate versus very high values), less outcome inequality (moderate versus high values), and more social media use (low versus moderate values).

Fourth, a higher economic, social and cultural status is individually correlated with reduced outcome inequality (high values), and a more intense use of social media (moderate values), while a higher level of outcome inequality is individually associated with less social media use (moderate values).

Table 14

Variable Pairwise Correlations (6 Main Variables - 8 PISA Edition Years)

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) VPoPI	1.000					
(2) wbI	-0.107	1.000				
(3) PV_avg_edu	-0.192	-0.099	1.000			
(4) z_ESCS_i	-0.485	-0.155	0.379	1.000		
(5) z_Giniindex	0.280	0.265	-0.289	-0.659	1.000	
(6) z_social_media_i	-0.365	0.011	0.150	0.363	-0.287	1.000

Table 15*Variable Pairwise Correlations (6 Main Variables - 23 Years including 8 PISA Edition Years)*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) VPoPI_interp	1.000					
(2) wbI_interp	-0.110	1.000				
(3) PV_avg_edu_int~p	-0.410	-0.251	1.000			
(4) z_ESCS_i_interp	-0.488	-0.060	0.782	1.000		
(5) z_Gini_interp	0.288	0.145	-0.605	-0.601	1.000	
(6) z_social_media~p	-0.351	-0.021	0.345	0.354	-0.256	1.000

5.4.6. National level - Populism Inter-Variable Correlation Analysis (V-Party-GPS)

A robustness check was conducted for populism assessed by the V-Party study, thanks to the GPS dataset. Both V-Party and GPS datasets were used to retrieve expert-coded populism assessment values for the present study. On the one hand, the V-Party study provided values for the period 1970-2019 (Lindberg et al., 2022), with a required update operated mostly regarding elections in or after 2019, especially to build the data used for analyses relating to the 2022 PISA edition year. As a reminder, the populism data corresponding to the PISA edition year 2022 is built upon the election results in 2021 or, if unavailable, in the closest earlier year. As mentioned above (V-Party data section), this is justified by the fact that the assessed populism level potentially linked to education outcome and well-being level of youth is the one that was present during a certain lap of time (at least a few months) in the country before the PISA tests, not the one measured during simultaneous elections, nor very recent elections (i.e. haven taken place only a few months before the PISA tests).

On the other hand, the GPS study started in November 2019 (GPS – Norris, 2019), meaning that its data reflected the populism situation in 2020 and probably much in 2021 as well. Hence, with both studies' datasets overlapping in 2021, although the GPS source was a one-time collection, it was used to compute a robustness correlation test with the 2022 V-Party populism data. Figure 33 illustrates the coherence between V-Party and GPS populism evaluations of the political situation in 2022. The correlation coefficient is equal to 0.726 and is accepted as sufficient for the robustness check for the V-Party dataset, assuming that this value is impacted by differences between both populism assessment studies in terms of asked questions or expert and indicator selection process and results, for example.

Figure 33

Scatter Plot and Correlation between V-Party and GPS Values to Assess Populism in 2022

5.5. Analyses Results

This section contains the results of the statistical tests of the models testing the present study's hypotheses.

5.5.1. Cross-Sectional Data Analyses

This section is about the results from the cross-sectional observations between populism and educational outcomes and well-being. I estimated a total of 18 ordinary least squares (OLS) regression models across eight waves of PISA data, to measure temporal variations in these relationships.

The analytical framework consists of two models, where Model A examines well-being outcomes as the dependent variable regressed on populism, followed by control variables. Additionally Model B with educational outcomes as the dependent variable. To ensure robustness and also to explore the comparison between populism values between the V-Party populism index and GPS populism index, I additionally analysed 2022 values with the GPS populism index (GPSPoPI). Notably, GPS is cross-sectional by origin, with data collected only in 2019. Therefore, the GPSPoPI 2019 values are used with the 2022 measures with other variables such as well-being and other control variables. As well as, geopolitical region is included in the regression for understanding heterogeneity across regions.

Comprehensive results are available in Appendix G and H.

5.5.1.1. Model A - Dependent Variable: Well-being Index (Hypothesis 1)

The correlation between well-being index (wbi) and populism (VPoPI) is statistically significant across eight years and nine models ($p < 0.001$). The correlation is positive in most models, except for 2003, 2006, and 2022 (using GPSPoPI) where the correlation is negative. The average coefficient across 8 years is 0.049. The correlation of educational outcomes with well-being is statistically significant across the 8 years ($p < 0.001$) and negative in association, which is contradictory based on the literature. Social media use is positively correlated ($p < 0.001$) with well-being in 5 out of 9 models. Except for 2006, ESCS index is negatively correlated with well-being, which is a counterintuitive result. Interestingly, in the first 5 years inequality is positively correlated with well-being, implying a standard deviation increase in inequality corresponding to an increase in well-being with its outcome coefficient, whereas in the last 3 years, including both GPSPoPI and VPoPI for 2022, it is negatively correlated ($p < 0.001$). There is a difference from one geopolitical region to another in terms of well-being as highlighted by the varying but statistically significant correlation of geopolitical with well-being, as well as showcased by the interaction effect of geopolitical region with populism and educational outcomes, respectively ($p < 0.001$).

5.5.1.2. Model B - Dependent Variable: Educational Outcomes (Hypothesis 2)

Overall the correlation of populism and educational outcomes is statistically significant in all of the 9 regression outputs. The direction of correlation between populism (VPoPI) and educational outcomes (PV_avg_edu) has varied across the eight years. In 2000, 2015 and 2022 (using VPoPI), 3 out of 9 times the correlation coefficient is positive, which implies that one standard deviation increase in populism corresponds to an increase in educational outcomes by its given coefficient. Whereas, in 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2018 and 2022 (using GPSPoPI), the correlation is negative, implying a standard deviation increase in populism corresponding to a decrease in educational outcomes by its given coefficient, which is also consistent with the expected direction of these variables. Interestingly, in 2022, GPS shows a negative correlation between populism and educational outcomes, as opposed to a negative correlation shown by and V-Party. The average value of the GPSPoPI and VPoPI coefficient in 2022 is 0.000375. The average of all coefficients across the 8 cycles is -0.0130894.

Interestingly, the correlation between well-being (wbi) and educational outcomes across the 9 models is negative, with an 8 year average coefficient of 0.142. The correlation of social media ($z_social_media_i$) is negative in 2000 and 2015, with an 8 year average coefficient of 0.0395. The correlation of ESCS index (z_ESCS_i) is consistently positive across models, whereas Gini index is consistently negative across models. It is statistically insignificant in 2009 and 2022, using both GPSPoPI and VPoPI. Furthermore, in all models except for 2012 heterogeneity is observed across regions with the interaction term of VPoPI and region, which means that the correlation VPoPI and educational outcome differs from one geopolitical region to another, statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, in most cases the interaction of region and well-being is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

5.5.1.3. Model F - Baron and Kenny Mediation Analysis (Hypothesis 4)

Based on the mediation analysis, the results across eight years as shown in Table 16 below illustrates that well-being consistently mediates the relationship between populism and educational outcome in a positive and statistically significant manner. In this context, direct effects show the influence of populism on education after controlling for well-being (i.e., part of the effect not explained by well-being). The indirect effect captures the pathway from populism to well-being and then from well-being to education, indicating how much of this relationship is carried through the mediator. The total effect is the overall relationship between populism and educational outcomes, which combines both direct and indirect effects.

Table 16

Baron and Kenny Mediation Analysis

Year	Effect	Coefficien	Z-Score	P - Value
2000	Total	-0.02784	-6.57	0
	Direct	-0.03812	-8.8	0
	Indirect	0.010261	10.15	0
2003	Total	0.009716	5.16	0
	Direct	-.0388509	-19.74	0
	Indirect	.0485669	59.31	0
2006	Total	-0.04503	-24.98	0
	Direct	-0.05202	-29.26	0
	Indirect	0.009794	59.51	0
2009	Total	0.021483	16.33	0
	Direct	0.012413	9.31	0
	Indirect	0.009069	60.65	0
2012	Total	0.006538	4.32	0
	Direct	-0.00023	-0.15	0.878
	Indirect	0.006772	40.79	0
2015	Total	-0.00916	-6.68	0
	Direct	-0.02499	-17.46	0
	Indirect	0.01583	41.51	0
2018	Total	0.012661	12.06	0
	Direct	0.002213	2	0
	Indirect	0.013907	38.91	0
2022	Total	0.045346	39.72	0
	Direct	0.036459	31.53	0
	Indirect	0.008887	40.75	0

The mediation analysis results reveal dynamic and evolving relationships between populism, well-being, and educational outcomes, with well-being consistently serving as a significant positive mediator throughout all years examined. Interestingly, the direct effects demonstrate temporal variation, with direct effects alternating between negative and positive coefficients across different years. It was negative in 2000, 2003, 2006, and 2015. Whereas, it is positive in 2009, 2012, 2018, and 2022. Notably, complete mediation effects are to be seen in 2012. It indicates that well-being was the primary mechanism through which populism influenced education.

The fluctuation in the directional effects can be understood in the light of the cross sectional-nature of this analysis, where each year represents the situation for a distinct snapshot of the socio-political and education landscape. Given this inherent dynamic nature of populism, well-being and education, it makes sense that the relationship between the variables flip directions across years. However, the mediating effect of well-being remains consistently positive, meaning well-being maintains its mediating influence regardless of the political climate.

5.5.2. Panel Data Fixed Effects Analysis: Education and Well-Being Outcome

This section examines two fixed effects panel models using the standardised variables (z-scores) across 49 countries and 22 years with 982 observations. It's important to note that the interpretation of all coefficients in the analysis is based on the z-scores. In addition to the Baron & Kenny mediation analysis carried out cross-sectionally in Result I, Instrumental Variable regression on the panel data is carried out in this section to check for the robustness of well-being mediating effects on educational outcomes.

5.5.2.1. Model C - Outcome Variable: Well-Being Index (Robustness for hypothesis 1)

This fixed effects regression explains about 10.4% of the within-country variation in education outcomes over time. The Between R-squared (0.21%) is very low. The Overall R-squared (2.7%) is also low, but this is not the primary measure of model fit in fixed effects estimation. The Within R-squared is the most relevant statistic, as our model is designed to capture within-country changes rather than between-country differences. The intraclass correlation is moderate ($\rho = 71.5\%$), while the F-statistic is 21.64 ($p = 0.001$) also confirms joint significance of control variates.

In this model VPoPI is seen to be negatively correlated with the well-being index, as one standard deviation increase in populism index corresponds to a 0.54 standard deviation decline in well-being, significant at the 1 percent level ($p = 0.001$). It suggests the increase in populism correlated to a decrease in well-being among children. As compared to Model 1, one standard deviation increase in educational outcomes, corresponds to a 0.38 standard deviation increase in well-being. ($p=0.045$). The socioeconomic status and Gini index, both are statistically significant and positively associated with well-being. One standard deviation increase in the Gini index (increased inequality) corresponds to a 0.437 standard deviation increase in well-being ($p = 0.000$), which reflects a counterintuitive point that income equality shares a positive correlation with well-being among children. Similarly, one standard deviation increase in socioeconomic status, correlates with a 0.24 standard deviation increase in well-being ($p=0.023$). Social media usage is statistically significant at 1 percent level, and one standard deviation increase in usage corresponds to a 0.098 standard deviation increase in well-being.

5.5.2.2. Model D - Outcome Variable: Educational Outcome (Robustness for hypothesis 2)

The fixed effects panel regression for educational outcomes demonstrates a within R-square of 7.98% in the dependent variable and overall R-squared of 52.43%, reflecting that much of the explanatory power derives from between-country differences. The Between R-square is much larger (58.75%) which indicates cross-country differences in average levels of dependent variables are well explained by added covariates. As the fixed effects models particularly explain within-country temporal variation, the within-R-square is most relevant for interpretation (Wooldridge, 2010). A high intraclass correlation ($\rho = 91.67\%$) signifies that 91.67% of the total variance in the educational outcome attributes to unobserved country-specific features, which strongly justifies the fixed effects specification over pooled OLS. The F-statistic of 16.10 ($p = 0.000$) confirms the joint significance of all explanatory variables and the validity of the model.

Examining the coefficient of VPoPI (V-Party Populism Index) results in a statistically significant negative correlation with educational outcomes (SE = 0.011, $p = 0.042$), significant at the 5 percent level. This indicates that a one standard deviation increase in the populism index corresponds to a 0.023 standard deviation decrease in educational outcomes. The coefficient of wBI (well-being Index) shows a positive correlation with educational outcomes (SE = 0.006, $p = 0.045$), also significant at the 5 percent level, although the magnitude is relatively small, as one standard deviation increase in the well-being index corresponds to a 0.011 standard deviation increase in educational outcomes.

Income inequality, measured with the Gini index, is negatively associated with educational outcomes, meaning one standard deviation increase in national level inequality, correlates with a 0.048 standard deviation decrease in educational outcomes. (Note: on a 0-1 scale, 1 corresponds to perfect inequality and 0 corresponds to perfect equality). It suggests that higher inequality is associated with lower educational outcomes. The socioeconomic status (ESCS index) demonstrates the expected positive association with educational outcomes (SE = 0.018, $p = 0.010$), which reflects that one standard deviation increase in the socioeconomic status, corresponds to a 0.047 standard deviation increase in educational outcomes. Notably, social media use shows the strongest statistical significance at 1 percent level (SE = 0.005, $p = 0.000$), suggesting that one standard deviation increase in social media usage is associated with 0.028 standard deviation increase in educational outcomes.

5.5.2.3. Comparative Analyses and Key Findings

The models presented above showcase a contrast between educational outcomes and well-being, in the sense that educational outcomes possess a strong between-country heterogeneity (with 91.7% of variance attributable to country fixed effects), whereas well-being shows greater within-country temporal variation (within R-squared = 10.4%). This tends to show that educational outcomes are more associated by stable institutional and cultural factors, whereas well-being responds more dynamically to changing conditions. The magnitude of correlational coefficient shows that populism has a 23-fold larger correlational effect on well-being than education. Significantly, both educational outcomes and well-being have a statistically significant correlation with each other. Educational outcome's coefficient on well-being (Model C: $\beta = 0.386$) and well-being's coefficient on educational outcomes (Model D: $\beta = 0.011$). This result could be used to hypothesise that educational outcomes and well-being have an asymmetric bi-directional correlation due to their statistically significant but varying coefficient magnitudes.

Furthermore, the negative correlation of inequality and education versus positive association with well-being and equality is notable. While the negative correlation of education and national inequality makes intuitive sense and also aligns with research that shows economic inequality impacts children's educational outcomes. (Cai, X., Cheng, Z., & Jiao, Y., 2025), the positive correlation of inequality with well-being appears counterintuitive. One justification of this relationship could be the presence of complex, non-linearities captured by standard Gini measures, or the relative measure of the well-being index, rather than an absolute measure. Additionally, it could also be hypothesized that countries with a higher baseline well-being can sustain greater inequality levels.

The consistent positive association of social media use with both educational outcomes and well-being challenges the dominant narrative in the literature reflecting harmful effects of social media on young people's well-being and development. However, recent research has produced mixed evidence, with some studies reporting advantages with social media use, such as increased self-esteem and opportunities for self-disclosure, while clothes sources demonstrate social media uses vary substantially between individuals (Best, Manktelow, & Taylor, 2014; Beyens et al., 2020). The positive correlations with well-being and educational outcomes in my research may reflect confounding factors rather than causal relationships; it can be hypothesized that students with greater social media access are likely to have superior access to digital infrastructure, higher socioeconomic status and enhanced access to online educational resources. Further research is required to better investigate this relationship, and my findings represent more of an artifact of digital divide dynamics than actual benefits of social media use itself.

5.5.3. Model E - Fixed Effects IV Estimation (Hypothesis 3)

We estimate the causal effect of well-being index (endogenous variable) on average educational performance using a fixed effects IV regression strategy. It is to be noted, since Montenegro, Indonesia, Romania and Argentina don't have data on social media, these countries were by default excluded by STATA due listwise deletion. The instrument, populism, is highly relevant in the first stage regression, as it strongly predicts the well-being index, with a coefficient of -0.55, significant at the 1 percent level ($p=0.000$). It implies that one standard deviation increase in the populism index is associated with 0.55 standard deviation decline in well-being. The first stage F-statistic is 71.8, well above the Stock-Yogo critical value of 16.4 for a single endogenous regressor, and the Anderson LM test rejects under-identification ($\chi^2(1) = 66.9$ ($p = 0.000$)). These diagnostics help us indicate that the model is correctly identified and that weak instrument bias is unlikely to be a concern. As the model is exactly identified with only one instrument for one endogenous variable, no overidentification test is available.

In the second stage, the coefficient of the well-being index is positive 0.054 ($SE = 0.021$, $p = 0.009$) and statistically significant at the 1 percent level. This signifies that, within groups over time, one standard deviation increase in well-being causes a 0.053 standard deviation increase in educational outcome. Across the exogenous regressors, one standard deviation increase in inequality (Gini index) corresponds to a decrease of 0.066 standard deviation in educational outcomes ($p=0.000$), as well as one standard deviation increase in social media has a positive association of increasing educational outcomes by 0.024 standard deviation, ($p=0.000$). However, the ESCS index is significant at the 10 percent level (0.071) and has a positive coefficient of 0.035 standard deviation.

Overall, for the 45 countries, over 8 years ($N=978$) IV results show that in the first stage, populism and well-being are negatively associated, as populism increases, well-being decreases. In the second stage, well-being is positively associated with educational outcomes. Meaning, higher well-being leads to higher educational outcomes. Together, increase in populism indirectly reduces educational outcomes through their negative effect on well-being. Formally, the IV estimates identify the local average treatment effect, which means for cases where populism shifts well-being, the resulting variation in well-being has a positive causal effect on education.

6. CONCLUSION

This thesis attempted to examine the relationship between population, children's well-being and educational outcomes across 45 countries. This was done by a cross sectional approach spanning across the eight PISA editions: 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018 and 2022. Secondly, with a panel data approach, generated by interpolating the eight predictions, and stretching it across 22 years (from 2000 - 2022) The research was guided by a central question: **What is the influence of populism on children's well-being and educational outcomes?** Followed by four hypotheses which are analysed cross-sectionally with OLS models, fixed effects panel models for the panel dataset, instrumental variables estimation and mediation analysis performed cross-sectionally for eight PISA editions.

Hypothesis 1: Higher levels of populism in society are associated with decreased well-being indicators among children.

The analysis provides statistically significant correlation across all tested models between populism and well-being. The direction of the results is mixed across models but predominantly provides supportive evidence for Hypothesis 1. The cross-sectional analysis across eight PISA editions (Model A x9) revealed a mixed temporal pattern, with the relationship between populism and well-being showing positive correlations in most years, meaning increased populism, associated with increased well-being. Whereas, Negative correlations, which match the hypothesis, are taking place in 2003, 2006, and 2022 (using GPS populism index for robustness). The average coefficient across eight years was 0.049, which is small but statistically significant.

The fixed effects panel analysis (Model C) has been used on the panel dataset to also complement the analysis with robustness and provide more conclusive evidence supporting the hypothesis. The country fixed effects highlight more conclusive evidence that supports the hypothesis. The within-country variation shows a statistically significant negative relationship (β : -0.54, $p < 0.001$). This effect demonstrates that populism has a meaningful adverse effect for children's psychological well-being, which is consistent with expert opinion discussed in the literature section of the thesis.

The divergence between cross-sectional and panel results shows the importance of controlling for unobserved country heterogeneity. The fixed effects specification captures the dynamic relation between the key variables more accurately by isolating the temporal changes in the equation.

The control variables also support the hypothesis as they are statistically significant: social media use is consistently positively correlated with well-being in five out of nine cross-sectional OLS models ($p < 0.001$), with fixed effects panel model confirming this association with a small coefficient value (β : -0.098, $p < 0.001$) This is challenging the conventional narratives about social media's detrimental effects on children's well-being. Another counter-intuitive correlation is presented with the inequality measure, Gini index which is positively correlated to well-being. (β : 0.437, $p < 0.001$). Socioeconomic status, ESCS index is also statistically significant (β : 0.24, $p = 0.023$). These results confirm the statistical significance across all models, including control variables. Similarly, statistically significant interaction effects with geopolitical regions are found. While the cross-sectional analysis is showing statistically significant results

with temporal variations across eight years in the direction of populism and well-being, the fixed effects models support the hypothesis

Hypothesis 2: Higher levels of populism in a society are associated with decreased educational outcomes among children.

Like the first hypothesis, this hypothesis about the levels of populism being associated with decreased educational outcomes has been shown by strong empirical support despite some temporal variations in the direction for the OLS models (Model B x9). The association between populism and educational outcomes across all models are statistically significant and negative. However, there are directional inconsistencies in 2000, 2015 and 2022 (using GPS populism index for robustness). In these years populism and well-being are positively correlated. However, the average coefficient across all OLS models is β : -0.0131, as predicted theoretically.

The fixed effects panel regression (Model D) provides definite support for the hypothesis, by demonstrating a statistically negative correlation between populism and educational outcomes ($\beta = -0.023$, $p = 0.042$). This represents a modest but statistically significant decline in educational outcomes.

The control variables, such as social media use showed mixed cross-sectional results, with negative correlations in 2000 and 2015, and for the rest, it is positively correlated with educational outcomes with an average across eight years of $\beta = 0.039$. Panel results confirm positive correlation ($\beta = -0.028$, $p = 0.00$) This may imply that students who have better access to digital infrastructure may have better access to extra learning help. Inequality (Gini Index) is not significant in 2009 and both 2022 models with VPoPI and GPSPoPI (for robustness). However, consistently negatively correlated with education across the OLS and fixed effects panel model. Similarly, socioeconomic status (ESCS) is also consistently positively correlated in all models. The interaction effects of geo-political region and well-being is also statistically significant, indicating the varying relationship across different world regions and political contexts.

Hypothesis 3: Decreased well-being among children is associated with poorer educational outcomes.

The relationship between well-being and educational outcomes was consistently statistically significant across all models. Notably, to address the potential endogeneity concerns inherent in the well-being and educational relationship, as both variables may be determined by unobserved factors, populism was used as an instrument for estimating an IV regression model. The most robust causal evidence for this hypothesis. Using populism as a highly relevant instrument for well-being, the results showcase a positive causal relation between well-being and educational outcomes. These results confirm and support our hypothesis.

The control variables, such as the Gini index for inequality, show a negative correlation with educational outcomes, as well as socioeconomic status (ESCS) with positive correlation, all of these are statistically significant. Additionally, social media use maintained its positive association with educational outcomes, also statistically significant.

Hypothesis 4: The relationship between populism and educational outcomes is mediated by children's well-being.

The design of understanding populism's influence on education through well-being was the fundamental idea, which was formally tested by the Baron and Kenny mediation analysis, this was designed to test across eight PISA editions, and the IV regression was thought to be a complementary robustness check.

Nevertheless, the mediation effect was statistically significant across all eight years, with temporal variations in the direction of the relationship between the key variables. This can be understood by the cross-sectional changes in the dynamics in different time phases. Notably, in 2012, full mediation was observed, suggesting populism primarily affected educational outcomes through well-being in that year.

Overall, consistency of the mediating effect of well-being between populism and educational outcomes are shown, which supports our hypothesis.

7. DISCUSSION

As mentioned in the results section, due to the hierarchical structure of the data, as the data from the PISA test such as plausible values of mathematics and reading, social media use, ESCS index are student level data, merging them with country level data of V-Party populism and Gini would result into the classic Moulton (1990) problem of downward biased standard errors and biased estimates due to within group correlation of residuals. To address this, the PISA variables were collapsed on country-year level averages from 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018 and 2022 and then the gaps were interpolated from 2000 to 2022. Therefore, the panel fixed effects results should be interpreted accordingly as they represent national level estimates, rather than individual estimates.

Furthermore, the limitation of the intrapolated data is the assumption of smooth temporal trends in the given data, especially in populist party strength, well-being and educational outcome: the limitation is explained by the potential discontinuous mobilisation patterns with rapid rises and declines that intrapolation can't capture. It is also possible that populist surges occur between two actual data points (for example between 2000 and 2003), in this case interpolation may assign moderate values which can weaken the actual relationship between populism and the outcome variable. However, despite these limitations, the interpolation enables the construction of a coherent longitudinal dataset, which makes it possible to assess the relationship between our variables of interest, which would otherwise remain obscured.

The findings underscore an urgent need for more systematic data collection. In this context, my suggestion is to conduct annual measurements of populism, ideally through continued and expanded efforts such as the V-Party dataset. While V-Party recommends at least four experts per party and the Global Party Survey recommends five, in practice these thresholds were not always met in the actual database. Therefore, the suggestion is to ensure the surveys adhere to the set standards by involving the recommended number of experts for precision and better data reliability. Similarly, the comparability of PISA data across waves is at times undermined by changes in the question formats or response scales, making it difficult to compare the same kind of information over time. Having consistent data for generating a world-wide populism index annual report would provide governments and policymakers with timely evidence.

The cross-sectional OLS estimates provide preliminary evidence of associations between populism, youth and well-being. However, these results may be interpreted with caution due to potential identification problems. As historical traditions in education, cultural attitudes towards authority or institutional quality may simultaneously influence populist support and youth outcomes. Additionally, the temporal consistencies across the PISA waves also suggest that correlation shifts over time, indicating that populism's influence on the outcome variable is conditional on broader contexts. The limitations also extend to classical error or systematic biases that can occur from expert coded assessments.

The panel results should therefore be seen as complementary to the 18 cross-sectional OLS model, while offering a robustness check. However, the potential limitations from the panel data analysis have to do with the assumption that populism's influence can be captured on student's well-being and education within a difference of a semester. While this assumption was used, it offered the best approach for operationalising our main variables of interest.

The IV specifications attempt to address endogeneity by instrumenting well-being with populism. While the instrument is statistically strong, its validity remains open to debate and further investigation. Populism may affect education directly through education reforms, teacher morale or curriculum content, depending on the context. Therefore, the IV estimates at best identify the local average treatment effect, applying only to the populations whose well-being is responsive to populism in the manner identified in this research. Consequently, the results cannot be generalized as evidence of a universal causal mechanism. The suggestion for further research in this context is to better connect research from psychology, especially children's psychology with policy relevant research, so that research can truly uncover the mechanisms through which the populist narrative can influence children. The research would also benefit from having more information about a child's well-being beyond the school experience and at home for example, which could not be included due to lack of data.

Counterintuitive findings are seen with social media use, which diverges from the claims in literature. Social media use was found to be positively correlated with educational outcomes and well-being, despite being portrayed as harmful for children's well-being by experts. One possible explanation could be that social media use may proxy for better digital connectivity which actually supports children's access to educational and well-being support. Further research is required to disentangle the true relationship. Interestingly, inequality and well-being's negative correlation also seems to be paradoxical in nature, given that income inequality is typically understood as detrimental for social outcomes. This may suggest that subjective well-being at school is less directly shaped by income distribution patterns. Nevertheless, integrating psychological research with inequality assessments is an interesting dimension to explore.

I acknowledge these data limitations. Nevertheless, the current findings provide valuable evidence for previously unexplored relationships between populism, well-being and educational outcomes. The consistency of findings across multiple specifications for robustness checks, such as cross-sectional, fixed effects, instrumental variables and mediation analysis, do suggest that the observed results are not mere artifacts of the missing interpolation procedure. If it was the case, we would expect discrepancies across methodological approaches. Instead, the convergence across models strengthens our confidence in the genuine underlying relationships between our variables of interest. It of course calls for further investigation and more comprehensive datasets. The research thus demonstrates a proof of concept, and the findings provide sufficient evidence to justify scholarly and policy attention to the intersection of populism and child development. The scope for further research should therefore move beyond the proof of concept and examine the given relationships more specifically with greater detail of the mechanisms through which politics shapes children's educational outcomes and well-being, which can widen the avenues for evidence-based policy research

8. POLICY RECOMMENDATION

The empirical results reveal statistically significant relationships between populism, children's well-being and educational outcomes that demand policy intervention. As the populist narrative propagates worldwide, documented in the results, followed by decline in children's well-being and academic achievement. Given education's fundamental role in shaping children's development and future ideological position, safeguarding educational spaces becomes essential for individual welfare and societal resilience.

To counter populism's detrimental effects on children's well-being, policy interventions must operate at multiple levels: within classrooms, through community engagement and via institutional safeguards that protect schools as a space for learning and developing critical thinking. These recommendations can take place across schools while bringing communities, teachers and students together. The policy recommendations including teacher training programmes emerge as a crucial lever in this case. As children spend much of their time at school, pre-service and ongoing professional development must integrate the following:

1. Emotional Intelligence Training: Teachers require systematic training in recognising and managing their own biases and emotional reactions that may unconsciously influence student perceptions and dynamics. The idea here is to primarily bring more awareness into educational spaces about the consequences of politically polarised narratives on the educator's position and how it may affect teacher-student relationships. As research demonstrates that teachers with higher emotional intelligence can better support students against external stressors (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009). However, when teachers themselves are influenced by populist narratives, their role as mentors can be compromised, as they may unintentionally propagate such ideologies within the classroom. The training must extend into evidence-based therapeutic approaches, where mandatory mindfulness-based regulation workshops for supporting trauma-informed pedagogy among teachers is carried out. Followed by providing educators with specialised certification adapted for educational contexts in terms of managing stress and well-being in the classroom.

2. Secondly, these teacher training programmes should be complemented by involving children and their communities. This recommendation is to actively promote social cohesion and promote tolerance for cultural, ethnic, religious or socioeconomic differences. This can be done through cultural integration within schools, where students and their families are involved in regular cultural events taking place in the school premises. These initiatives can counteract the polarising effects of populist narratives, by supporting a space for social contact and collaboration. Such a space in the schools, can help build collective empathy, and reinforce a shared sense of community responsibility. Furthermore, school community partnerships, including advisory and transparent communication forums, can create institutional safeguards by monitoring educational content for political bias while promoting trust and cooperation between schools and local communities.

3. Youth Civic and Media Literacy: Students need training in identifying misinformation, hate speech and discrimination and most of all awareness on the harmful effects of social media, fake news and discriminative narratives. Integrated media literacy curricula can help bring critical evaluation skills, these should be done simultaneously with promoting student-led community projects. In this sense, government

supported online portals that can distinguish credible from false information can supplement school-based instruction.

Recognizing that policymakers themselves may function from populist positions, the implementation strategy of these recommendations put children's well-being and development at the forefront, which is both politically acceptable, feasible and internationally endorsed by the agenda 2030. The urgency lies in the call for action, based on facts and evidence and to protect the bedrock of society: the children.

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Appendix I - V-Party Technical Details

Appendix J – GPS Technical Details

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Appendix L - Details regarding the GPS-Based Computation of National Levels of Populism per Indicator

Appendix A

Overview of elections and PISA edition years (4 parts)

Election years colour coding:

Outside PISA years	Same as a PISA year
PISA Year	Used election year

PISA Year		PISA Year		PISA Year		PISA Year		PISA Year		PISA Year
PISA Window		April – May		March – May						
PISA Main Topic		Reading		Math		Science		Reading		Math

#	Country Name (Code)	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
1	Albania (ALB)			1997				2001				2005				2009 JUN 28			
	USED election year results						1997			2001			2005			2005			2009
2	Argentina (ARG)					1999		2001		2003 APR 27		2005		2007		2009 JUN 28		2011	
	USED election year results						1999			2001			2005			2007			2011
3	Australia (AUS)				1998			2001			2004			2007			2010		
	USED election year results						1998			2001			2004			2007			2010
4	Austria (AUT)					1999			2002				2006 OCT 1		2008				
	USED election year results						1999			2002			2002		2008				2008
5	Belgium (BEL)					1999				2003 MAY 18				2007			2010		
	USED election year results						1999			1999			2003			2007			2010
6	Brazil (BRA)			1998					2002				2006 OCT 1				2010		
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2002			2006			2010
7	Bulgaria (BGR)			1997				2001				2005				2009 JUL 5			
	USED election year results						1997			2001			2005			2005			2009
8	Canada (CAN)			1997			2000 NOV 27				2004		2006 JAN 23		2008			2011	
	USED election year results						1997			2000			2004		2008			2011	2011
9	Chile (CHL)			1997				2001				2005				2009 DEC 13			
	USED election year results						1997			2001			2005			2005			2009
10	Croatia (HRV)	1995					2000 JAN 3			2003 NOV 23				2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1995			2000				2003		2007			2011
11	Czech Republic (CZE)				1998				2002					2006 JUN 2-3			2010		
	USED election year results						1998			2002				2002		2006			2010
12	Denmark (DNK)				1998			2001				2005		2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1998			2001			2005		2007			2011	2011
13	Estonia (EST)					1999				2003 MAR 2				2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1999			1999				2003		2007		2011	2011
14	Finland (FIN)					1999				2003 MAR 16				2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1999			1999				2003		2007		2011	2011
15	France (FRA)			1997					2002					2007					2012 JUN 17
	USED election year results						1997			2002				2002		2007			2007
16	Germany (DEU)				1998				2002			2005				2009 SEP 27			
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2005			2005			2009
17	Greece (GRC)		1996				2000 APR 9				2004			2007		2009 OCT 4			2012 MAY 6
	USED election year results						1996			2000				2004		2007			2009
()	Hong Kong (HKG - DISCARDED)			1998			2000 SEP 10				2004				2008				2012 SEP 9
	USED election year results						1998			2000					2004				2008
18	Hungary (HUN)				1998				2002				2006 APR 23				2010		
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2002			2006			2010
19	Iceland (ISL)					1999				2003 MAY 10				2007		2009 APR 25			
	USED election year results						1999			1999				2003		2007			2009
20	Indonesia (IDN)					1999					2004					2009 APR 9			
	USED election year results						1999			1999						2004			2009
21	Ireland (IRL)			1997					2002					2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1997			2002				2002		2007			2011
22	Israel (ISR)					1999				2003 JAN 28			2006 MAR 28			2009 FEB 10			
	USED election year results						1999			1999			2003			2006			2009
23	Italy (ITA)		1996					2001					2006 APR 9-10		2008				
	USED election year results						1996			2001				2001		2008			2008
24	Japan (JPN)		1996				2000 JUN 25			2003 NOV 9		2005				2009 AUG 30			2012 DEC 16
	USED election year results						1996			2000						2005			2009
()	Jordan (JOR - DISCARDED)			1997						2003 JUN 17				2007			2010		
	USED election year results						1997			1997				2003		2007			2010
25	Latvia (LVA)				1998				2002				2006 OCT 7				2010	2011	
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2002			2006			2011
26	Lithuania (LTU)		1996				2000 OCT 8				2004				2008				2012 OCT 28
	USED election year results						1996			2000					2008				2008
27	Luxembourg (LUX)					1999					2004					2009 JUN 7			
	USED election year results						1999			1999						2004			2009
28	Mexico (MEX)			1997			2000 JUL 2			2003 JUL 6			2006 JUL 2			2009 JUL 5			2012 JUL 1
	USED election year results						1997			2000			2003			2006			2009
29	Montenegro (MNE)				1998			2001	2002				2006 JUN 3			2009 MAR 29			2012 OCT 14
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2002			2006			2009

Country colour coding:

Selected country
Discarded country

Remarks

- Jordan (JOR) was discarded due to insufficient election results details (only 0% to 14.5% of the lower chamber seats were expert-assessed in the V-Party study)
- Hong Kong (HKG) was discarded due to insufficient election results details (only 33.3% to 51.4% of the lower chamber seats were expert-assessed in the V-Party study)

Election years colour coding:

Outside PISA years	Same as a PISA year
PISA Year	Used election year

	PISA Year		PISA Year		PISA Year
	March - May		March - May		March - May
	Science		Reading		Math

Latest Election Year Before 2000	Latest V-Party Included Election Year	Election year covered by the update of the V-Party Dataset	Remark
1	2017	2021	
2	2019	2021	
3	2019	N/A	
4	2019	N/A	
5	2019	N/A	
6	2018	N/A	
7	2017	2021	
8	2019	2021	
9	2017	2021	
10	2016	2020	
11	2017	2021	
12	2019	N/A	
13	2019	N/A	
14	2019	N/A	
15	2017	N/A	In 2012, Jun 10 & Jun 17
16	2017	2021	
17	2019	N/A	
1998	2016	2021	DISCARDED (weak data)
18	2018	N/A	In 2006, Apr 9 & Apr 23
19	2017	2021	
20	2019	N/A	
21	2016	2020	
22	2019	2021	
23	2018	N/A	
24	2017	2021	
1997	2013	(2000)	DISCARDED (weak data)
25	2018	N/A	
26	2016	2020	In 2012, Oct 14 & Oct 28
27	2013	2018	
28	2018	2021	
29	2016	2020	

#	Country Name (Code)	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
1	Albania (ALB)	2013		2013		2017	2017			2021	2021		
2	Argentina (ARG)	2013		2015 OCT 25		2017	2017	2019		2021	2019		
3	Australia (AUS)	2013		2013	2016		2016	2019			2022		
4	Austria (AUT)	2013		2013		2017	2017	2019			2019		2024
5	Belgium (BEL)		2014				2014	2019			2019		2024
6	Brazil (BRA)		2014				2014	2019			2018		
7	Bulgaria (BGR)	2013	2014			2017	2017			2021	2022	2023	2024
8	Canada (CAN)			2015 OCT 19			2015	2019		2021	2021		
9	Chile (CHL)	2013		2013		2017	2017			2021	2021		
10	Croatia (HRV)			2015 NOV 8	2016		2016		2020		2020		2024
11	Czech Republic (CZE)	2013		2013		2017	2017			2021	2021		
12	Denmark (DNK)			2015 JUN 18			2015	2019			2022		
13	Estonia (EST)			2015 MAR 1			2015	2019			2019		2023
14	Finland (FIN)			2015 APR 19			2015	2019			2019		2023
15	France (FRA)			2012		2017	2017				2022		2024
16	Germany (DEU)	2013		2013		2017	2017			2021	2021		
17	Greece (GRC)			2015 SEP 20			2015	2019			2019		2023
()	Hong Kong (HKG - DISCARDED)			2012	2016		2016			2021	2021		
18	Hungary (HUN)		2014				2014	2018 APR 8			2022		
19	Iceland (ISL)	2013		2013	2016	2017	2017			2021	2021		2024
20	Indonesia (IDN)		2014				2014	2019			2019		2024
21	Ireland (IRL)			2011	2016		2016		2020		2020		2024
22	Israel (ISR)	2013		2015 MAR 17			2015	2019	2020	2021	2022 NOV 1		
23	Italy (ITA)	2013		2013			2013	2018 MAR 4			2022		
24	Japan (JPN)		2014			2017	2017			2021	2021		2024
()	Jordan (JOR - DISCARDED)	2013		2013	2016		2016		2020		2020		2024
25	Latvia (LVA)		2014				2014	2018 OCT 6			2022		
26	Lithuania (LTU)			2012	2016		2016		2020		2020		2024
27	Luxembourg (LUX)	2013		2013			2013				2018		2023
28	Mexico (MEX)			2015 JUN 7			2015	2018 JUL 1		2021	2021		2024
29	Montenegro (MNE)			2012	2016		2016		2020		2020		2023

Country colour coding:

Selected country
Discarded country

Remarks

- Jordan (JOR) was discarded due to insufficient election results details (only 0% to 14.5% of the lower chamber seats were expert-assessed in the V-Party study)
- Hong Kong (HKG) was discarded due to insufficient election results details (only 33.3% to 51.4% of the lower chamber seats were expert-assessed in the V-Party study)

Election years colour coding:

Outside PISA years	Same as a PISA year	PISA Year	PISA Year	PISA Year	PISA Year	PISA Year	PISA Year	PISA Year	PISA Year
PISA Year	Used election year	PISA Window	April – May	Math	March – May	Science	March – May	Reading	March – May
		PISA Main Topic	Reading	Math	Science	Reading	Math		

#	Country Name (Code)	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
30	Netherlands (NLD)				1998		1998		2002	2003 JAN 22			2006 NOV 22			2006	2010		2012 SEP 12
	USED election year results									2002			2003			2006			2010
()	New Zealand (NZL - DISCARDED)					1999			2002			2005			2008			2011	
	USED election year results						1999			2002			2005			2008			2011
31	Norway (NOR)			1997				2001				2005				2009 SEP 14			
	USED election year results						1997			2001			2005			2005			2009
32	Peru (PER)	1995					2000 JUN 3	2001					2006 APR 9					2011	
	USED election year results						1995			2001			2001			2006			2011
33	Poland (POL)			1997				2001				2005		2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1997			2001			2005			2007			2011
34	Portugal (PRT)				1999			2002				2005				2009 SEP 27		2011	
	USED election year results						1999			2002			2005			2005			2011
35	Romania (ROU)		1996				2000 DEC 10				2004				2008				2012 DEC 9
	USED election year results						1996			2000			2004			2008			2012
36	Russia (RUS)				1999					2003 DEC 7				2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1999			1999			2003			2007			2011
37	Serbia (SRB)			1997			2000 SEP 24			2003 DEC 28				2007	2008				2012 MAY 6
	USED election year results						1997			2000			2003			2008			2012
38	Slovakia (SVK)				1998				2002				2006 JUN 17				2010		2012 MAR 10
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2002			2006			2010
39	Slovenia (SVN)		1996				2000 OCT 15				2004				2008			2011	
	USED election year results						1996			2000			2004			2008			2011
40	South Korea (KOR)		1996				2000 APR 13				2004				2008				2012 DEC 19
	USED election year results						1996			2000			2004			2008			2012
41	Spain (ESP)		1996				2000 MAR 12				2004				2008			2011	
	USED election year results						1996			2000			2004			2008			2011
42	Sweden (SWE)				1998				2002				2006 SEP 17				2010		
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2002			2006			2010
43	Switzerland (CHE)				1999					2003 DEC 10				2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1999			1999			2003			2007			2011
()	Taiwan (TWN - DISCARDED)				1998			2001			2004	2005			2008				2012 JAN 14
	USED election year results						1998			2001		2005			2008				2012
44	Thailand (THA)		1996					2001				2005		2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1996			2001			2005			2007			2011
45	Tunisia (TUN)					1999					2004					2009 OCT 25		2011	
	USED election year results						1999			1999			2004			2004			2011
46	Turkey (TUR)					1999			2002					2007				2011	
	USED election year results						1999			2002			2002			2007			2011
47	United Kingdom (GBR)			1997				2001				2005						2010	
	USED election year results							1997				2005				2005			2010
48	United States of America (USA)				1998		2000 NOV 7		2002		2004		2006 NOV 7		2008		2010		2012 NOV 6
	USED election year results						1998			2002			2004			2008			2010
49	Uruguay (URY)				1999						2004					2009 OCT 25			
	USED election year results						1999			1999			2004			2004			2009

Country colour coding:

Selected country
Discarded country

Remarks

- New Zealand (NZL) was discarded due to the unavailability of GINI data
- Taiwan (TWN) was discarded due to the unavailability of GINI data
- Thailand (THA) saw its 2014 election annulled by the Constitutional Court (<https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/2442>)

Election years colour coding:

Outside PISA years	Same as a PISA year
PISA Year	Used election year

PISA Year		PISA Year		PISA Year	
March - May	Science	March - May	Reading	March - May	Math

#	Country Name (Code)	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
30	Netherlands (NLD)					2017				2021		2023	
	USED election year results			2012			2017				2021		
()	New Zealand (NZL - DISCARDED)		2014			2017			2020			2023	
	USED election year results			2014			2017				2020		
31	Norway (NOR)	2013				2017				2021			
	USED election year results			2013			2017				2021		
32	Peru (PER)				2016				2020	2021			
	USED election year results			2011			2016				2021		
33	Poland (POL)			2015 OCT 25				2019				2023	
	USED election year results			2011			2015				2019		
34	Portugal (PRT)			2015 OCT 4				2019			2022		2024
	USED election year results			2011			2015				2019		
35	Romania (ROU)				2016				2020				2024
	USED election year results			2012			2016				2020		
36	Russia (RUS)				2016					2021			
	USED election year results			2011			2016				2021		
37	Serbia (SRB)		2014		2016				2020		2022	2023	
	USED election year results			2014			2016				2020		
38	Slovakia (SVK)				2016				2020			2023	
	USED election year results			2012			2016				2020		
39	Slovenia (SVN)		2014				2018 JUN 3				2022		
	USED election year results			2014			2014				2018		
40	South Korea (KOR)				2016				2020				2024
	USED election year results			2012			2016				2020		
41	Spain (ESP)			2015 DEC 20	2016			2019				2023	
	USED election year results			2011			2016				2019		
42	Sweden (SWE)		2014				2018 SEP 9				2022		
	USED election year results			2014			2014				2018		
43	Switzerland (CHE)			2015 OCT 18				2019				2023	
	USED election year results			2011			2015				2019		
()	Taiwan (TWN - DISCARDED)				2016				2020				2024
	USED election year results			2012			2016				2020		
44	Thailand (THA)		2014					2019				2023	
	USED election year results			2011			2011				2019		
45	Tunisia (TUN)		2014					2019			2022		
	USED election year results			2014			2014				2019		
46	Turkey (TUR)			2015 NOV 1			2018 JUN 24					2023	
	USED election year results			2011			2015				2018		
47	United Kingdom (GBR)			2015 MAY 7		2017		2019					2024
	USED election year results			2010			2017				2019		
48	United States of America (USA)		2014		2016		2018 NOV 6		2020		2022		2024
	USED election year results			2014			2016				2020		
49	Uruguay (URY)		2014					2019					2024
	USED election year results			2014			2014				2019		

Latest Election Year Before 2000	Latest V-Party Included Election Year	Election year covered by the update of the V-Party Dataset	Remark
30	2017	2021	
1999	2017	2020	DISCARDED (no GINI)
31	2017	2021	
32	2016	2021	In 2000, Apr 8 & Jun 3
33	2019	N/A	
34	2019	N/A	
35	2016	2020	In 2000, Nov 26 & Dec 10
36	2016	2021	
37	2016	2020	
38	2016	2020	
39	2018	N/A	
40	2016	2020	
41	2019	N/A	
42	2018	N/A	
43	2019	N/A	
1998	2016	2020	DISCARDED (no GINI)
44	2019		2014 election annulled
1999	2019	N/A	
46	2018	N/A	
47	2019	N/A	
48	2018	2020	
49	2019	N/A	

Country colour coding:

Selected country
Discarded country

Remarks

3. New Zealand (NZL) was discarded due to the unavailability of GINI data
4. Taiwan (TWN) was discarded due to the unavailability of GINI data
5. Thailand (THA) saw its 2014 election annulled by the Constitutional Court (<https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/2442>)

Appendix B

Details of the updates of the V-Party dataset due to the time limitation of the V-Party study

Moreover, regarding the time limit of the V-Party study, as elections took place between the latest V-Party expert-coding (in most cases in 2019) and before 2022 in 25 of the 49 selected countries, missing election results (seat shares) considered for the 2022 PISA edition were added to the data. The populism level of the lower chamber, using post-V-Party seat shares, was evaluated in these cases using the populism level of the same parties as assessed by the V-Party experts in the most recent elections reported in the dataset (as depicted in Appendix A). Two online sources were used to fetch the missing data: the ElectionGuide website (International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES), 2025) and the free online collaborative encyclopaedia Wikipedia (Wikimedia Foundation, 2025).

For Albania (ALB), in 2001, the 46 seats for Union for Victory Coalition (UVC) were reallocated to the Democratic Party of Albania (PDS) since no expert-coded data was provided for the UVC, while it was provided for the PDS, which was the main party of the UVC coalition.

The lower chamber composition used for assessing the level of populism in Argentina (ARG) for the PISA 2022 edition was the one observed before the 2021 elections, as it changed on December 9, 2021, which was very close to the 2022 PISA test dates. The Justicialist (Peronist) Party had a total of 91/257 seats (https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Justicialist_Party&oldid=1052224071), the Renewal Front Party had a total of 11/257 seats (https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Renewal_Front&oldid=1053659873), the Civic Coalition ARI has a total of 11/257 seats (https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Civic_Coalition_ARI&oldid=1060706307), the Republican Proposal had a total of 53/257 seats, and the Radical Civic Union had a total of 46/257 seats (https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Argentine_Chamber_of_Deputies&oldid=1053792110).

The 2021 elections in Bulgaria (BGR) saw the main and newly created party, We Continue the Change (Prodalzhavame promyanata), win 67/240 seats in the lower chamber (<https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3960>). Nevertheless, this party did not exist previously, which resulted in the missing expert-assessed level of populism relating thereto in the V-Party study. Hence, the 2021 national level of populism in Bulgaria, used for the 2022 PISA edition, was based on the 2017 populism evaluation of only 49.6% of the total seats.

In Croatia (HRV) in 2016 (<https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/2971>), a total of 54 seats were won by the coalition formed by the Social Democratic Party of Croatia (SDP – 38 seats, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_Democratic_Party_of_Croatia), the Croatian People's Party – Liberal Democrats (HNS – 9 seats, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Croatian_People%27s_Party_%E2%80%93_Liberal_Democrats), the Croatian Party of Pensioners (HSU – 2 seats, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Croatian_Party_of_Pensioners#Legislative), and the Croatian Peasant Party (HSS – 5 seats, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Croatian_Peasant_Party_#Parliamentary). In 2020 (<https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3510>), a total of 41 seats were won by the Restart Coalition (Restart koalicija) formed by the Social Democratic Party of Croatia (SDP – 33 seats), the Croatian People's Party – Liberal Democrats (HNS – 1 seat), the Croatian Party of Pensioners (HSU – 1 seat), the Croatian Peasant Party (HSS – 2 seats), the Civic Liberal Alliance (GLAS – 1 seat, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/>

[Civic Liberal Alliance](#)), and the Istrian Democratic Assembly (IDS – 3 seats, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Istrian_Democratic_Assembly#Parliament_\(Sabor\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Istrian_Democratic_Assembly#Parliament_(Sabor))). The 2020 national level of populism in Croatia, used for the 2022 PISA edition, was based on the 2016 V-Party populism evaluations combined with the 2020 seat shares.

In the Czech Republic (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Czech_parliamentary_election#Results) (CZE), in 2021, the Party Tradition Responsibility Prosperity 09 (TOP 09, part of the Spolu coalition – https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/TOP_09) won 14/200 seats, the Czech Social Democratic Party (CSSD) did not win any seat (0/200), the Civic Democratic Party (ODS, part of the Spolu coalition – [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Civic_Democratic_Party_\(Czech_Republic\)#Election_results](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Civic_Democratic_Party_(Czech_Republic)#Election_results)) won 34/200 seats, the Christian Democratic Union/People's Party (KDU-ČSL, part of the Spolu coalition – https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/KDU-%C4%8CSL#Legislative_elections) won 23/200 seats, the Mayors and Independents – Your Option (SN-VA – https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mayors_and_Independents#Chamber_of_Deputies) won 33/200 seats, the Communist Party of Bohemia and Moravia (KSCM) did not win any seat (0/200), the Action of Dissatisfied Citizens (ANO – [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ANO_\(political_party\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ANO_(political_party))) won 72/200 seats, and the Freedom and Direct Democracy (SPD – https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Freedom_and_Direct_Democracy) won 20/200 seats.

For Luxembourg (LUX – 60 seats), the 2018 election results were retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Luxembourg_general_election. The most recent populism assessment by the V-Party experts was conducted in 2013. Since the new Pirate Party (0/60 seats in 2013) was not evaluated, and won 2 seats out of 60 in 2018, the availability of populism data for the lower chamber decreased from 96.7% of the seats in 2013 to 93.3% of the seats in 2018.

For Montenegro (MNE – 81 seats), the 2020 election results were retrieved from Wikipedia websites. The Socialist People's Party of Montenegro (SNP CG) won 3/81 seats in 2016 and 5/81 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Socialist_People's_Party_of_Montenegro#Parliamentary_elections), the Democratic Party of Socialists of Montenegro (DPS) won 35/81 seats in 2016 and 29/81 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Democratic_Party_of_Socialists_of_Montenegro), the Social Democratic Party of Montenegro (SDP CG) won 4/81 seats in 2016 and 2/81 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_Democratic_Party_of_Montenegro), the New Serb Democracy (NOVA) won 8/81 seats in 2016 and 9/81 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/New_Serb_Democracy), the Movement for Changes (PzP) won 5/81 seats in 2016 and 5/81 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Movement_for_Changes#Electoral_performance), the Democratic Alliance (DEMOS) won 4/81 seats in 2016 and 1/81 seats in 2020 ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DEMOS_\(Montenegro\)#Parliamentary_elections](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DEMOS_(Montenegro)#Parliamentary_elections)), the United Reformist Action (URA) won 2/81 seats in 2016 and 3/81 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_Reform_Action#Parliamentary_elections), the Democratic People's Party of Montenegro (DNP) won 4/81 seats in 2016 and 5/81 seats in 2020 ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Democratic_People%27s_Party_\(Montenegro\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Democratic_People%27s_Party_(Montenegro))).

The 2021 election results for Peru (PER – 130 seats) were retrieved from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3635>. The Alliance for Progress of Peru (APEP, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alliance_for_the_Progress_of_Peru) won 9/130 seats in 2016 and was constituted by these parties:

- Alliance for Progress (APP) won 9/130 seats in 2016 and 15/130 seats in 2021 ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alliance_for_Progress_\(Peru\)#Congress_of_the_Republic](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alliance_for_Progress_(Peru)#Congress_of_the_Republic));
- National Restoration (RN) won 0/130 seats in 2016 and did not participate (0/130 seats) in the 2021 election ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Restoration_\(Peru\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Restoration_(Peru)));
- We Are Peru (SP) won no seat (0/130) in 2016 and 5/130 seats in 2021 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/We_Are_Peru – but no populism data in the V-Party study for this party after 2001).

Furthermore, the Popular Action (AP) won 5/130 seats in 2016 and 16/130 seats in 2021 (https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Acci%C3%B3n_Popular#Resultados_electorales), the Frente Amplio (Broad Front for Justice, Life and Liberty) won 20/130 seats in 2016 and 0/130 seats in 2021 ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broad_Front_\(Peru\)#Elections_to_the_Congress_of_the_Republic](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broad_Front_(Peru)#Elections_to_the_Congress_of_the_Republic)), the Peruvians for Change (PPK) won 18/130 seats in 2016 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Peruvians_for_Change) and 0/130 seats in 2021 ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Contigo_\(political_party\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Contigo_(political_party))). The Popular Alliance ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Popular_Alliance_\(Peru\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Popular_Alliance_(Peru))) won 5/130 seats in 2016, then was dissolved after this election (0/130 seats in 2021) and was composed of the Peruvian Aprista Party (PAP – https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/American_Popular_Revolutionary_Alliance) and the Christian People's Party (PPC – [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christian_People%27s_Party_\(Peru\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christian_People%27s_Party_(Peru))).

The 2020 election results for the Romanian Chamber of Deputies were extracted from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Romanian_parliamentary_election#Chamber_of_Deputies. In 2020, members of the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats (ALDE (20/329 seats in 2016) – [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alliance_of_Liberals_and_Democrats_\(Romania\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alliance_of_Liberals_and_Democrats_(Romania))) ran on the PRO Romania list (PRO – https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PRO_Romania#Legislative_elections), but did not win any seats (0/330). Finally, the Save Romania Union (USR) won 30/329 seats in 2016 and 38/330 seats in 2020 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Save_Romania_Union#Electoral_history).

The results and seat shares of the 2020 elections were retrieved for Ireland (IRL – 160 seats) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3454> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Irish_general_election#Results, for Lithuania (LTU – 141 seats) from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Lithuanian_parliamentary_election#Results, for New Zealand (NZL – 120 seats, country later discarded because of missing Gini data) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3298> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_New_Zealand_general_election#Results, for Serbia (SRB – 250 seats) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3279> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Serbian_parliamentary_election#Results, for Slovakia (SVK – 150 seats) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3274> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Slovak_parliamentary_election#Results, for South Korea (KOR – 300 seats) from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_South_Korean_legislative_election#Results, and for Taiwan (TWN – 113 seats, country later discarded because of missing Gini data) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3347> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Taiwanese_legislative_election#Results and for the United States of America (USA) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3300> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_United_States_House_of_Representatives_elections.

The results and seat shares of the 2021 elections were retrieved for Germany (DEU – 736 seats) from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_German_federal_election#Results, for Iceland (ISL – 63 seats) from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Icelandic_parliamentary_election#Results, for Israel (ISR – 120 seats)

from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Israeli_legislative_election#Results, for Mexico (MEX – 500 seats) from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Mexican_legislative_election#Results, for the Netherlands (NLD – 150 seats) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3629> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Dutch_general_election#Results, for Norway (NOR – 169 seats) from <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3630> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Norwegian_parliamentary_election#Results, and for Russia (RUS – 450 seats) on <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3647> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2021_Russian_legislative_election#Results.

Appendix C

Details of the updates of the V-Party dataset regarding the 2016 election in Russia (RUS) and the 2018 election in the United States of America (USA)

According to the V-Party data for the 2016 election in Russia, Just Russia (SR) won 7/449 seats. Nevertheless, the website <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/2694> reports that Just Russia won 7/450 seats with 3,275,053 votes (the same number of seats but a different total number of seats in the Russian Duma), while the page https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2016_Russian_elections allocates, on the one hand, 7/225 constituency seats with 5,017,645 constituency votes and, on the other hand, 16/225 party-list seats with 3,275,053 party-list votes to Just Russia, with a total of 23/450 seats, as confirmed on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A_Just_Russia_%E2%80%93_For_Truth#2016_Duma_elections. On https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Results_of_the_2016_Russian_legislative_election_by_constituency, it is confirmed that Just Russia obtained 7/225 constituency seats in 2016 for the following regions: Yakutia, Chuvashia, Penza Oblast, Rostov Oblast, Yaroslavl Oblast, Moscow (Leningradsky mandate), and Saint Petersburg (North-East mandate). In conclusion, the data from V-Party for 2016 for Just Russia (7/449 seats) was replaced by a total of 23/450 seats.

According to the V-Party dataset for the United States of America (USA) in 2018, the Democratic Party won 235/476 seats, and the Republican Party won 241/476 seats. This is a double mistake that can be corrected thanks to the data available on <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/2421> (2016 election) and on <https://www.electionguide.org/elections/id/3074> (2018 election). First, the total number of seats of the House of Representatives was 435. Nevertheless, the (wrong) figure 476 indicates how the mistake was made: 476 is equal to 241 (the correct Republican Party number of seats in 2016... but also wrongly maintained in 2018 in the V-Party dataset) added to 235 (the correct number of seats of the Democratic Party in 2018). Second, in 2018, the Republican Party won 200/235 seats instead of 241/476 seats. These numbers were duly corrected for this study. The correct figures in 2018 are 235/435 seats for the Democratic Party and 200/435 seats for the Republican Party.

Appendix D

Details of the updates of the GPS dataset (missing values)

The missing GPS data was fetched on respective Wikipedia webpages to update the GPS data, for Brazil (BRA – 2018 elections) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Brazilian_general_election#Results, for Chile on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2017_Chilean_general_election#Chamber_of_Deputies_election (CHL – 2017 elections), for Jordan (JOR – 2016 elections, country discarded due to insufficient data) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2016_Jordanian_general_election#Results, for Luxembourg (LUX – 2018 elections) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Luxembourg_general_election#Results, for Latvia (LVA – 2018 elections) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Latvian_parliamentary_election, for Sweden (SWE – 2018 elections) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Swedish_general_election#Results, for Thailand (THA – 2019 elections) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2019_Thai_general_election#Results, and for Taiwan (TWN – 2016 elections, country discarded due to insufficient data) on https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2016_Taiwanese_legislative_election.

Appendix E

Details of the updates of the GPS dataset for Germany (DEU)

This update was conducted with the information found on the Wikipedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2017_German_federal_election#Results webpage. Here is an overview of the update regarding the 2017 election for the 709 seats in the German Bundestag:

Party name	Original GPS Seat Share (%)	Corrected Seat Number	Corrected Seat Share (%)
Alliance 90/The Greens	11.20	67	9.45
Alternative for Germany	15.70	94	13.26
Christian Democratic Union	33.40	200	28.21
Christian Social Union in Bavaria	7.70	46	6.49
Free Democratic Party	13.40	80	11.28
Social Democratic Party	25.60	153	21.58
The Left	11.50	69	9.73
Total	118.50	709	100.00

Appendix F

List of parties with missing values for some indicators in the GPS dataset

The list of parties with missing values for some indicators in the GPS dataset (values replaced by the worldwide mean value for the relating indicator) is as follows (mentioning country, party name, percentage of seat share, and GPS indicator number):

Argentina (ARG):

- Civic Front for Santiago (2.3% seat share) GPS V15
- Front for the Renewal of Concord (1.6% seat share) GPS V10, GPS V15
- Union for Córdoba (1.9% seat share) GPS V15

Hungary (HUN):

- Independents (0.5% seat share) GPS V4, V18
- National Self-Government of Germans in Hungary (0.5% seat share) GPS V4, V6, V7, V8, V9, V12, V13, V14, V15, V16, V17, V18, V19, V20, V21

Italy (ITA):

- Associative Movement Italians Abroad (0.2% seat share) GPS V4, V9, V19
- South American Union of Italian Emigrants (0.2% seat share) GPS V8, V9, V12, V14, V17, V21

Luxembourg (LUX):

- Party for Complete Democracy (0.0% seat share) GPS V4, V5, V6, V10, V13
- The Green Alternative (15.0% seat share) GPS V4, V5

Montenegro (MNE):

- Albanians Decisively (1.2% seat share) GPS V12, V18, V20
- Bosniak Party (2.5% seat share) GPS V12, V20
- Democratic Montenegro (9.9% seat share) GPS V10, V12
- Key Coalition (11.1% seat share) GPS V10, V13, V15, V19

Peru (PER):

- Alliance for the Progress of Peru (6.9% seat share) GPS V13
- Popular Action (3.8% seat share) GPS V13

Russia (RUS):

- Russian Ecological Party (0.0% seat share) GPS V9, V18

Slovakia (SVK):

- Network (6.7% seat share) GPS V15, V17, V18, V19

Spain (ESP):

- Unidas Podemos (9.1% seat share) GPS V11

Thailand (THA):

- Bhumjaithai Party (10.2% seat share) GPS V4, V10, V21
- Charthai Pattana Party (2.0% seat share) GPS V4, V7, V8, V10, V12, V19, V20, V21
- New Economics Party (1.2% seat share) GPS V12, V20
- Prachachart Party (1.4% seat share) GPS V12
- Puea Chat Party (1.0% seat share) GPS V4, V12, V13
- Thai Liberal Party (2.0% seat share) GPS V10, V12

Tunisia (TUN):

- Ennahda Movement (31.8% seat share) GPS V12

Value colour coding:

0.2502809	Significant positive value *** (p-value<0.001)
0.2502809	Significant positive value ** (p-value<0.01)
0.2502809	Significant positive value * (p-value<0.05)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value *** (p-value<0.001)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value ** (p-value<0.01)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value * (p-value<0.05)
-0.0038222	Non significant value
0.0838223	Positive value. For information only (non-significant)
-0.0887503	Negative value. For information only (non-significant)

Variables	Label
wbi	Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index (with intrapolation if required)
VPopI	Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index
GPSPoPI	Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index (data collected in 2019)
z_social_media_i	Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with intrapolation if required)
PV_avg_edu	Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value
z_ESCS_i	Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with intrapolation if required)
z_gender	Gender (base 1 Female)
z_Giniindex	Standardized ("Z") Gini Index
region	Politico-geographic region (see bottom of table)

Note: the six categories of the "region" (V-Party politico-geographic region) variable are:

- 1: Eastern Europe and Central Asia
- 2: Latin America and the Caribbean
- 3: The Middle East and North Africa (including Israel and Turkey)
- 4: Sub-Saharan Africa

- 5: Western Europe and North America (including Australia)
- 6: Asia and Pacific (excluding Australia - see 5)

LINEAR REGRESSION		Year 2015					Year 2018					Year 2022 (V-Party populism)					Year 2022 (GPS populism)					Average 2022 value (between V-Party and GPS values)		Average 8-year value (2000-2003-2006-2009-2012-2015-2018-2022V-P/GPS)					
DV is Well-Being (wbi)		Number of obs	646,822				Number of obs	616,078				Number of obs	668,302				Number of obs	668,302											
Nb populism: V Party (VPopI) 2000 -> 2022 & GPS (GPSPoPI_2019) in the 2nd 2022 analysis		F(18, 646803)	> 99999.00				F(18, 616059)	> 99999.00				F(18, 668283)	> 99999.00				F(18, 668283)	> 99999.00											
		Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0											
		R-squared	0.5278				R-squared	0.4015				R-squared	0.4167				R-squared	0.4426											
		Root MSE	0.55371				Root MSE	0.75654				Root MSE	0.72134				Root MSE	0.70509											
STATA Variable Name		Robust					Robust					Robust					Robust												
wbi		Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t
VPopI		0.1335369	0.0015825	84.38	0.000	0.0960730	0.0015438	62.23	0.000	0.2373025	0.0013475	176.1	0.000	-0.4148030	0.002181	-190.19	0.000	-0.4148030	0.002181	-190.19	0.000	-0.0887503	0.0496161			-0.0887503	0.0496161		
z_social_media_i		-0.3017599	0.0026398	-114.31	0.000	-0.2049595	0.0016079	-127.47	0.000	0.0273785	0.0008666	31.59	0.000	0.1402661	0.0006617	211.97	0.000	0.1402661	0.0006617	211.97	0.000	0.0838223	0.0347533			0.0838223	0.0347533		
PV_avg_edu		-0.2007761	0.0027174	-73.89	0.000	-0.2761330	0.002959	-93.32	0.000	-0.2091156	0.002349	-89.02	0.000	-0.2202011	0.0021679	-101.57	0.000	-0.2202011	0.0021679	-101.57	0.000	-0.2146584	0.1684255			-0.2146584	0.1684255		
z_ESCS_i		-0.3640823	0.0024325	-149.67	0.000	-0.4011750	0.0042151	-95.17	0.000	-0.4136253	0.0029148	-141.91	0.000	-0.3709747	0.0022533	-164.64	0.000	-0.3709747	0.0022533	-164.64	0.000	-0.3923000	-0.2453020			-0.3923000	-0.2453020		
z_gender		-0.0122520	0.0013765	-8.9	0.000	-0.0029743	0.0019306	-1.54	0.123	-0.0033505	0.0017674	-1.9	0.058	-0.0013520	0.0017291	-0.78	0.434	-0.0013520	0.0017291	-0.78	0.434	-0.0023513	0.0059518			-0.0023513	0.0059518		
z_Giniindex		-0.0136667	0.0010545	-12.96	0.000	-0.1970279	0.0016503	-119.39	0.000	-0.0879193	0.0017995	-48.86	0.000	-0.2689043	0.0014048	-191.41	0.000	-0.2689043	0.0014048	-191.41	0.000	-0.1784118	0.0350288			-0.1784118	0.0350288		
region (base 1)																													
2		0.4235196	0.0060464	70.04	0.000	1.1407510	0.0074041	154.07	0.000	0.5556085	0.0041965	132.4	0.000	0.4450130	0.0036717	121.2	0.000	0.4450130	0.0036717	121.2	0.000	0.5003108	0.6928870			0.5003108	0.6928870		
3		2.5795330	0.0051994	496.12	0.000	3.0617660	0.0033499	913.99	0.000	3.9852800	0.0066419	600.02	0.000	4.6372260	0.0067147	690.61	0.000	4.6372260	0.0067147	690.61	0.000	4.3112530	1.5602675			4.3112530	1.5602675		
5		1.0835530	0.0024779	437.3	0.000	1.2459320	0.0022302	558.66	0.000	1.1400790	0.00241	473.06	0.000	0.6537617	0.0029258	284.76	0.000	0.6537617	0.0029258	284.76	0.000	0.8969204	0.6420864			0.8969204	0.6420864		
6		-1.3957350	0.0142617	-97.87	0.000	0.0138988	0.027668	0.5	0.615	5.1333730	0.0124473	412.41	0.000	0.6773971	0.0035672	189.9	0.000	0.6773971	0.0035672	189.9	0.000	2.9053851	0.3069158			2.9053851	0.3069158		
VPopI		0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)												
region#c.VPopI																													
2		-0.4040822	0.0028741	-140.6	0.000	-0.1967891	0.0021362	-92.12	0.000	-0.5649148	0.0017909	-315.43	0.000	0.3007845	0.0022205	135.46	0.000	0.3007845	0.0022205	135.46	0.000	-0.1320652	-0.1510158			-0.1320652	-0.1510158		
3		-1.9006180	0.0034854	-545.31	0.000	-1.2258510	0.0035494	-345.37	0.000	-2.0411450	0.0037071	-550.61	0.000	-5.0267410	0.0088822	-565.93	0.000	-5.0267410	0.0088822	-565.93	0.000	-3.5339430	-0.8994895			-3.5339430	-0.8994895		
5		-0.1951510	0.00209	-93.37	0.000	-0.2674233	0.0018163	-147.24	0.000	-0.5963630	0.0018953	-314.65	0.000	0.0560111	0.0024328	23.02	0.000	0.0560111	0.0024328	23.02	0.000	-0.2701760	0.2150912			-0.2701760	0.2150912		
6		2.5462780	0.0257913	98.73	0.000	1.4582040	0.0564794	25.82	0.000	-8.0228030	0.0247654	-323.95	0.000	2.8441440	0.0083676	339.9	0.000	2.8441440	0.0083676	339.9	0.000	-2.5893295	0.2213776			-2.5893295	0.2213776		
PV_avg_edu		0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)												
region#c.PV_avg_edu																													
2		0.3090945	0.0030912	99.99	0.000	0.3738489	0.0034637	107.93	0.000	0.2453725	0.0026381	93.01	0.000	0.2621896	0.0023905	109.68	0.000	0.2621896	0.0023905	109.68	0.000	0.2537811	0.2290947			0.2537811	0.2290947		
3		0.3395609	0.0033714	100.72	0.000	0.2759987	0.0029589	93.28	0.000	0.2090312	0.0023481	89.02	0.000	0.2201671	0.0021662	101.64	0.000	0.2201671	0.0021662	101.64	0.000	0.2145592	0.2242870			0.2145592	0.2242870		
5		0.1990952	0.0028356	70.21	0.000	0.2998702	0.003166	94.72	0.000	0.2174222	0.0027569	78.87	0.000	0.2302565	0.0025724	89.51	0.000	0.2302565	0.0025724	89.51	0.000	0.2238394	0.1778286			0.2238394	0.1778286		
6		0.0257588	0.0048112	5.35	0.000	0.4352715	0.0066546	65.41	0.000	0.2486895	0.003179	78.23	0.000	0.4215426	0.0031509	133.79	0.000	0.4215426	0.0031509	133.79	0.000	0.3351161	0.0626894			0.3351161	0.0626894		
cons		-1.0070180	0.0035282	-285.42	0.000	-1.6497260	0.0032113	-513.73	0.000	-1.2165160	0.0023701	-513.28	0.000	-0.935044	0.0021388	-437.41	0.000	-0.935044	0.0021388	-437.41	0.000	-1.0760102	0.5243235			-1.0760102	0.5243235		
Note: VPopI/GPSPoPI_2019 omitted because of collinearity.																													
Note: PV_avg_edu omitted because of collinearity.																													

Note: the average values for 2022 are derived from two sources: (1) the 2022 regression analysis using V-Party data and (2) the 2022 regression analysis using GPS data. These values are for informational purposes only and should be interpreted with caution, as their statistical significance was not tested.

Note: the 8-year average values are based on eight sources: (1-7) the first seven regressions covering the years 2000-2018, and (2) the average values for 2022 (refer to the note above). These values are for informational purposes only and should be interpreted with caution, as their statistical significance was not tested.

Appendix H

Comprehensive 9 Cross-Sectional OLS Regressions - Educational Outcome (DV.) on Populism (Indep.V.) (2 parts)

Value colour coding:

0.2502809	Significant positive value *** (p-value<0.001)
0.2502809	Significant positive value ** (p-value<0.01)
0.2502809	Significant positive value * (p-value<0.05)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value *** (p-value<0.001)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value ** (p-value<0.01)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value * (p-value<0.05)
-0.0038222	Non significant value
0.0838223	Positive value. For information only (non-significant)
-0.0887503	Negative value. For information only (non-significant)

Variables	Label
PV_avg_edu	Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value
VPopI	Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index
GPSPoPI	Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index (data collected in 2019)
wbl	Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index (with intrapolation if required)
z_social_media_i	Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with intrapolation if required)
z_gender	Gender (base 1 Female)
z_ESCS_i	Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with intrapolation if required)
z_Giniindex	Standardized ("Z") Gini Index
region	Politiico-geographic region (see bottom of table)

Note: the six categories of the "region" (V-Party politico-geographic region) variable are:

- 1: Eastern Europe and Central Asia
- 2: Latin America and the Caribbean
- 3: The Middle East and North Africa (including Israel and Turkey)
- 4: Sub-Saharan Africa

- 5: Western Europe and North America (including Australia)
- 6: Asia and Pacific (excluding Australia - see 5)

LINEAR REGRESSION		Year 2000					Year 2003					Year 2006					Year 2009					Year 2012				
DV is Education Outcome		Number of obs	110,275				Number of obs	499,276				Number of obs	633,716				Number of obs	781,054				Number of obs	733,128			
Nb populism: V Party (VPopI) 2000 -> 2022 & GPS (GPSPoPI_2019) in the 2nd 2022 analysis		F(16, 110,258)	2139.73				F(17, 499,258)	8722.51				F(18, 633,697)	7677.63				F(18, 781,035)	12173.51				F(18, 733,109)	9938.98			
		Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0				Prob > F	0			
		R-squared	0.233				R-squared	0.2073				R-squared	0.1665				R-squared	0.2024				R-squared	0.1754			
		Root MSE	0.92041				Root MSE	0.85791				Root MSE	0.87921				Root MSE	0.8559				Root MSE	0.86844			
STATA Variable Name		Robust					Robust					Robust					Robust									
PV_avg_edu	Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t		Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t		Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t		Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t		Coefficient	std. err.	t	P> t		
VPopI	0.2108180	0.0128497	16.41	0.000		-0.1495469	0.0072655	-20.58	0.000		-0.0693661	0.0036718	-18.89	0.000		-0.0595901	0.0034097	-17.48	0.000		-0.0233602	0.0026198	-8.92	0.000		
wbl	-0.1396497	0.0092293	-15.13	0.000		-0.1285694	0.0106424	-12.08	0.000		-0.0746583	0.0017174	-43.47	0.000		-0.0793693	0.0020184	-39.32	0.000		-0.2321571	0.0032447	-71.55	0.000		
z_social_media_i	-0.0216003	0.0036040	-5.99	0.000		0.0662315	0.0020956	31.61	0.000		0.0588966	0.0021167	27.83	0.000		0.1685352	0.0028257	59.64	0.000		0.0436010	0.0039827	10.95	0.000		
z_gender (base 1)	-0.1195594	0.0055532	-21.53	0.000		-0.1174596	0.0024334	-48.27	0.000		-0.1283587	0.0022125	-58.02	0.000		-0.1258872	0.0019398	-64.90	0.000		-0.1235243	0.0020308	-60.83	0.000		
z_ESCS_i	0.2229503	0.0054676	40.78	0.000		0.1213797	0.0037819	32.10	0.000		0.1948447	0.0039877	48.86	0.000		0.2154119	0.0026262	82.02	0.000		0.1829498	0.0028927	63.24	0.000		
z_Giniindex	-0.0878594	0.0072135	-12.18	0.000		-0.0276261	0.0034836	-7.93	0.000		-0.0573931	0.0027116	-21.17	0.000		0.0007221	0.0024055	0.30	0.764		0.0364286	0.0023042	15.81	0.000		
region (base 1)																										
2	0.0880141	0.0310081	2.84	0.005		6.5746720	0.3647203	18.03	0.000		-0.1950336	0.0247556	-7.88	0.000		-0.7886402	0.1117856	-66.92	0.000		-1.0340190	0.1115855	-89.25	0.000		
3	0.0443802	0.0365992	1.21	0.225		-0.0806148	0.0221694	-3.64	0.000		0.3002329	0.0134836	22.27	0.000		-0.8722048	0.0280412	-31.10	0.000		-0.8456022	0.0139943	-60.42	0.000		
5	0.7138071	0.0168452	42.37	0.000		0.1346430	0.0108073	12.46	0.000		0.1087019	0.0034547	31.47	0.000		0.2393018	0.0034460	69.44	0.000		0.0107848	0.0043119	2.49	0.013		
6	0.4404381	0.0356225	12.36	0.000		-0.0957807	0.0137365	-6.97	0.000		0.3330568	0.0130392	25.54	0.000		0.1387332	0.0128199	10.82	0.000		0.2821949	0.0124459	22.67	0.000		
VPopI		0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)				
region/c.VPopI																										
2	-0.3866243	0.0174687	-22.13	0.000		0.5997446	0.0225071	26.65	0.000		0.1943968	0.0058664	33.14	0.000		0.2411852	0.0043003	56.09	0.000		-0.0039492	0.0045127	-0.88	0.382		
3	0.0000000	(omitted)				-0.0866536	0.0124256	-6.97	0.000		-0.2416961	0.0068602	-35.23	0.000		0.4553688	0.0117244	38.84	0.000		0.2728487	0.0070505	38.70	0.000		
5	-0.2595018	0.0132571	-19.57	0.000		0.1175560	0.0069264	16.97	0.000		0.0471098	0.0037054	12.71	0.000		0.0878549	0.0036452	24.10	0.000		0.0293116	0.0032351	9.06	0.000		
6	-0.2322912	0.0240874	-9.64	0.000		0.3532326	0.0161544	21.87	0.000		2.9568630	0.0970682	30.46	0.000		0.1870937	0.0093059	20.10	0.000		-0.0102314	0.0151785	-0.67	0.500		
wbl		0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)				
region/c.wbl (base 1)																										
2	0.1670061	0.0244298	6.84	0.000		-6.0153840	0.3200431	-18.80	0.000		0.0433601	0.0226162	1.92	0.055		0.9123258	0.0106345	85.79	0.000		0.5563036	0.0061826	89.98	0.000		
3	0.0000000	(omitted)				0.0000000	(omitted)				-0.4772286	0.0138671	-34.41	0.000		0.8055754	0.0192333	41.88	0.000		0.5376712	0.0083408	64.46	0.000		
5	0.3548791	0.0117981	30.08	0.000		0.0767721	0.0112784	6.81	0.000		0.0631998	0.0041279	15.31	0.000		0.0386389	0.0035229	10.97	0.000		0.2222033	0.0042535	52.24	0.000		
6	-0.1499256	0.0154463	-9.71	0.000		-0.1011106	0.0113363	-8.92	0.000		0.7424263	0.0327624	22.66	0.000		-0.4478286	0.0073052	-61.30	0.000		-0.9567672	0.0244574	-39.12	0.000		
cons		-0.4227658					0.1942572					0.0887442					-0.0743742					0.2164828				

Note: VPopI omitted because of collinearity.

Note: wbl omitted because of collinearity.

Note: 3.region/c.wbl omitted because of collinearity.

Value colour coding:

0.2502809	Significant positive value *** (p-value<0.001)
0.2502809	Significant positive value * (p-value<0.01)
0.2502809	Significant positive value (p-value<0.05)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value *** (p-value<0.001)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value ** (p-value<0.01)
-0.2566333	Significant negative value * (p-value<0.05)
-0.0038222	Non significant value
0.0838223	Positive value. For information only (non-significant)
-0.0887503	Negative value. For information only (non-significant)

Variables	Label
PV_avg_edu	Standardized ("Z") Average Education Outcome Plausible Value
VPoPI	Standardized ("Z") V-Party Populism PCA-derived Index
GPSPoPI	Standardized ("Z") GPS Populism PCA-derived Index (data collected in 2019)
wbi	Standardized ("Z") Well-Being PCA-derived Index (with interpolation if required)
z_social_media_i	Standardized ("Z") Social media use (with interpolation if required)
z_gender	Gender (base 1 Female)
z_ESCS_i	Standardized ("Z") ESCS Index (with interpolation if required)
z_Giniindex	Standardized ("Z") Gini Index
region	Politico-geographic region (see bottom of table)

Note: the six categories of the "region" (V-Party politico-geographic region) variable are:

- 1: Eastern Europe and Central Asia
- 2: Latin America and the Caribbean
- 3: The Middle East and North Africa (including Israel and Turkey)
- 4: Sub-Saharan Africa

- 5: Western Europe and North America (including Australia)
- 6: Asia and Pacific (excluding Australia - see 5)

LINEAR REGRESSION					Year 2015					Year 2018					Year 2022 (V-Party populism)					Year 2022 (GPS populism)					Average 2022 value		Average 8-year value	
DV is Education Outcome					Number of obs 646,822					Number of obs 616,078					Number of obs 668,302					Number of obs 668,302					Average 2022 value		Average 8-year value	
Nb populism: V-Party (VPoPI) 2000 > 2022 & GPS (GPSPoPI 2019) in the 2nd 2022 analysis					F(18, 646,803) 9211.78					F(17, 616,060) 5199.55					F(17, 668,284) 5918.55					F(18, 668283) > 99999.00					(between V-Party and GPS values)		(2000-2003-2006-2009-2012-2015-2018-2022V-P/GPS)	
STATA Variable Name					Robust					Robust					Robust					Robust								
PV_avg_edu					Coefficient std. err. t P> t					Coefficient std. err. t P> t					Coefficient std. err. t P> t					Coefficient std. err. t P> t					Coefficient		Coefficient	
VPoPI					0.0060723 0.0022073 2.75 0.006					-0.0234922 0.0019316 -12.16 0.000					0.0261320 0.0019326 13.52 0.000					-0.0186313 0.0025662 -7.26 0.000					0.0037504		-0.0130894	
wbi					-0.1729197 0.0023186 -74.58 0.000					-0.1102419 0.0018219 -60.51 0.000					-0.2048125 0.0024711 -82.88 0.000					-0.2047176 0.0026324 -77.77 0.000					-0.2047651		-0.1427913	
z_social_media_i					-0.0642957 0.0028755 -22.36 0.000					0.0144844 0.0018548 7.81 0.000					0.0529228 0.0010387 50.95 0.000					0.0475848 0.0011027 43.15 0.000					0.0502538		0.0395133	
z_gender (base 1)					-0.0870806 0.0021298 -40.89 0.000					-0.1070831 0.0022604 -47.37 0.000					-0.0856320 0.0021877 -39.14 0.000					-0.0858085 0.0021885 -39.21 0.000					-0.0857203		-0.1118341	
z_ESCS_i					0.0650938 0.0025970 25.07 0.000					0.1308991 0.0030991 42.24 0.000					0.3462235 0.0033669 102.83 0.000					0.3285534 0.0032174 102.12 0.000					0.3373885		0.1838647	
z_Giniindex					-0.0687710 0.0025764 -26.69 0.000					-0.0997727 0.0024617 -40.53 0.000					-0.0050366 0.0028693 -1.76 0.079					-0.0038948 0.0027703 -1.41 0.160					-0.0044657		-0.0385922	
region (base 1)																												
2					-0.0708793 0.0067971 -10.43 0.000					0.0089843 0.0071837 1.25 0.211					0.2837029 0.0073175 38.77 0.000					0.2413387 0.0071820 33.60 0.000					0.2625208		0.6057024	
3					-16.2409000 0.1596913 -101.70 0.000					0.1484740 0.0130650 11.36 0.000					-0.0329625 0.0200759 -1.64 0.101					-0.0877428 0.0239993 -3.66 0.000					-0.0603527		-2.2008347	
5					0.3282959 0.0048036 68.34 0.000					0.2993980 0.0055657 53.79 0.000					0.2414824 0.0047585 50.75 0.000					0.2187274 0.0043985 49.73 0.000					0.2301049		0.2581234	
6					-1.4353730 0.0231467 -62.01 0.000					-1.1061820 0.0246495 -44.88 0.000					1.8789120 0.0504465 37.25 0.000					0.3440958 0.0058682 58.64 0.000					1.1115039		-0.0414261	
VPoPI					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)								
region#c.VPoPI																												
2					-0.1462702 0.0042547 -34.38 0.000					-0.0215696 0.0042615 -5.06 0.000					0.0538029 0.0048452 11.10 0.000					0.0754593 0.0040722 18.53 0.000					0.0646311		0.0676931	
3					13.8706200 0.1394484 99.47 0.000					0.0378114 0.0058873 6.42 0.000					0.1144430 0.0091600 12.49 0.000					0.3917488 0.0268057 14.61 0.000					0.2530959		1.8201744	
5					-0.0444088 0.0034028 -13.05 0.000					0.0152231 0.0029995 5.08 0.000					0.0210933 0.0028729 7.34 0.000					0.0418054 0.0031309 13.35 0.000					0.0314494		0.0030743	
6					2.9753430 0.0386324 77.02 0.000					2.9894100 0.0479611 62.33 0.000					-2.8117630 0.0947941 -29.66 0.000					-0.8154746 0.0286613 -28.45 0.000					-1.8136188		0.9257251	
wbi					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)								
region#c.wbi (base 1)																												
2					1.1438800 0.0164465 69.55 0.000					0.2233480 0.0112159 19.91 0.000					0.4882089 0.0117201 41.66 0.000					0.4588479 0.0109014 42.09 0.000					0.4735284		-0.3119540	
3					10.3600200 0.1030228 100.56 0.000					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000 (omitted)					0.0000000		1.4032548	
5					0.1757697 0.0042278 41.57 0.000					0.1483840 0.0038374 38.67 0.000					0.2148416 0.0030923 69.48 0.000					0.2091452 0.0032325 64.70 0.000					0.2119934		0.1614800	
6					-0.0033758 0.0096557 -0.35 0.727					0.1876661 0.0056536 33.19 0.000					0.0359775 0.0187255 1.92 0.055					0.8964996 0.0146153 61.34 0.000					0.4662386		-0.0328346	
cons					-0.0895528 0.0038228 -23.43 0.000					-0.1175035 0.0040219 -29.22 0.000					-0.3320212 0.0040960 -81.06 0.000					-0.3022504 0.0038191 -79.14 0.000					-0.3171358		-0.0652310	
Note: VPoPI/GPSPoPI_2019 omitted because of collinearity.																												
Note: wbi omitted because of collinearity.																												
Note: 3.region#c.wbi omitted because of collinearity.																												

Note: the average values for 2022 are derived from two sources: (1) the 2022 regression analysis using V-Party data and (2) the 2022 regression analysis using GPS data. These values are for informational purposes only and should be interpreted with caution, as their statistical significance was not tested.

Note: the 8-year average values are based on eight sources: (1-7) the first seven regressions covering the years 2000-2018, and (2) the average values for 2022 (refer to the note above). These values are for informational purposes only and should be interpreted with caution, as their statistical significance was not tested.

Appendix I

V-Party Technical Details

Using the V–Dem methodology (Coppedge, Gerring, et al., 2020) from January 2020 to 2021, 711 experts rated the policy positions and organizational capacity of political parties across elections in 178 countries. Specifically, as the general rule, experts coded data before a given election and for all major parties that reached more than 5% of the vote share.

The expert-coded data was aggregated using V–Dem’s Bayesian Item Response Theory measurement model (Pemstein et al., 2020), unless noted otherwise. The result is data on 3467 political parties across 3151 elections; in total, 11898 party-election year units. Typically, at least 4 coders provided their assessment per observation. Nevertheless, for some countries, the number of experts was equal to or smaller than 3, which was not an exclusion criterion for this study.

In some countries, political parties formed a firm, longstanding pre–electoral alliance, which makes it difficult to disentangle them (for example CDU and CSU in Germany). In this case, the longstanding alliance (*e.g.* “CDU/CSU” in Germany), meaning the most common practice among the major party/parties of the alliance, was assessed and not the individual parties. In case of loose, election-specific alliances, individual parties were evaluated.

Furthermore, in case of more than one lower chamber election per year, only the results of the last election in a year were considered, and experts coded the party characteristics relevant then.

A selection criterion for the present study was the availability of V-Party expert-assessed populism for at least 50% of the total seats of the national lower chamber for each considered election, with three exceptions described below. Unfortunately, from the original set of countries, two countries were discarded due to regular insufficient data: Hong Kong (HGK – from 33.3% to 51.4% of the lower chamber seats were expert-assessed) and Jordan (JOR – from 0% to 14.5%).

In Bulgaria (BGR) and Peru (PER), new parties ran the 2021 elections alongside longer-established parties. Since these new parties were not expert-coded in the V-Party study, which ended in 2019, less than 50% of the seats in the lower chamber were expert-coded for the respective 2021 national elections only (considered for the 2022 PISA edition): 49.6% in Bulgaria and 42.3% in Peru. However, as this rate is exceptionally low for that single year and due to the limitations of the V-Party study, Bulgaria and Peru were not discarded.

Last exception, in Romania (ROU), 49.9% of the total seats of the lower chamber only were assessed for populism by the V-Party experts in the 2000 election (considered for the 2003 PISA edition). Again, since this exceptionally low rate – just below the exclusion threshold – was observed for that year only, Romania was not discarded.

Appendix J

GPS Study Technical Details

The 10 largest political parties with representation in the current lower (or single) house of the national parliament were assessed, in independent nations with more than 100,000 citizens holding national legislative elections, irrespective of the degree of party competition. Questions with 0–10-point scales were designed to monitor each political party's overall position on their left-right stance towards the economy, social liberalism or conservative values, their use of populist or pluralistic rhetoric, and their position towards a range of current policy issues, including the environment protection, international affairs and foreign policies, immigration policies, and political processes.

Experts were also requested to evaluate their familiarity with each party, their personal ideological values, and background characteristics (*e.g.* age, gender, country of citizenship). For some countries, the number of experts was equal to or smaller than 4, which was not an exclusion criterion for this study.

Appendix K

Details regarding the V-Party-Based Computation of National Levels of Populism per Indicator

Let us consider an example, for a given indicator, in a given country i , in year t , with 3 (n) parties (e.g. parties A, B, and C), having won respectively 20, 30, and 40 seats (total 90 seats) in a 100 ($N_{i,t}$) seat lower chamber. The respective seat shares are 20/100, 30/100, and 40/100. With associated expert-assessed populism levels of -0.2, 0.5, and 1.5 for the A, B, and C parties in this example, the V-Party level of populism for the given indicator in that country i , in year t , is computed by the following formula:

$$V \text{ Populism level}_{i,t} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^n (\text{populism level party}_{n,i,t} * \text{seat share party}_{n,i,t}) * N_{i,t}}{\sum_{n=1}^n \text{seats party}_n}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{In the example, V Populism level} &= (-0.15 * 20/100 + 0.5 * 30/100 + 1.5 * 40/100) * 100 / (20+30+40) \\ &= (-0.03 + 0.15 + 0.6) * 100 / 90 \\ &= 0.72 * 100 / 90 \\ &= 0.8 \end{aligned}$$

where i stands for the country (49 selected countries)

where t stands for the PISA edition year (8 PISA edition years from 2000 to 2022)

where n is the number of expert-assessed parties in the country i , in the year t

where $N_{i,t}$ is the total number of seats in the lower chamber in the country i , in the year t

In some countries, the total cumulated seat share did not reach 100.0% (e.g. in Albania (ALB), respectively 80.6%, 85.0%, 92.1%, 92.1%, 98.6%, 95.7%, 99.3%, and 97.9% for the 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2015, 2018, and 2022 PISA edition years, among many examples). The above formula compensated for this phenomenon by evaluating each country's national level of populism in a given year based on the assumption (which is an approximation) that the composition of its lower chamber was fully and proportionally represented by all expert-assessed parties in the given country and year, considering their seat share among the total cumulated seat share. This method was preferred over the option of hypothesizing the populism level of unassessed parties being minimal, null, maximal, or equal to the national or worldwide average.

Appendix L

Details regarding the GPS-Based Computation of National Levels of Populism per Indicator

Let us consider an example, for a given indicator, in a given country i , in 2019, with 3 (n) parties (e.g. parties A, B, and C), having won respectively 20, 30, and 40 seats (total 90 seats) in a 100 ($N_{i,t}$) seat lower chamber. The respective seat shares are 20/100, 30/100, and 40/100. With associated expert-assessed populism levels of -0.2, 0.5, and 1.5 for the A, B, and C parties in this example, the GPS level of populism for the given indicator in that country i , in 2019, is computed by the following formula:

$$GPS\ Populism\ level_i = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^n (populism\ level\ party_{n,i} * seat\ share\ party_{n,i}) * N_i}{\sum_{n=1}^n seats\ party_n}$$

In the example, GPS Populism level = $(-0.15 * 20/100 + 0.5 * 30/100 + 1.5 * 40/100) * 100 / (20+30+40)$
= $(-0.03 + 0.15 + 0.6) * 100 / 90$
= $0.72 * 100 / 90$
= 0.8

where i stands for the country (49 selected countries)

where n is the number of expert-assessed parties in the country i , in 2019

where N_i is the total number of seats in the lower chamber in the country i , in 2019

In some countries, the total cumulated seat share did not reach 100.0% (98.1% in Argentina (ARG) or 93.9% in Belgium (BEL), among many examples). The above formula compensated for this phenomenon by evaluating each country's national level of populism in 2019 based on the assumption (which is an approximation) that the composition of its lower chamber was fully and proportionally represented by all expert-assessed parties in the given country, considering their seat share among the total cumulated seat share. This method was preferred over the option of hypothesizing the populism level of unassessed parties being minimal, null, maximal, or equal to the national or worldwide average.

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